

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D5.7 Analysis: Public health responses and impact - update M33

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

Project

Acronym	COVINFORM
Title	Coronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation dynamics Research and Modelling
Coordinator	SYNYO GmbH
Reference	101016247
Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Programme	HORIZON 2020
Topic	SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2C Behavioural, social and economic impacts of the outbreak response
Start	01 November 2020
Duration	36 months
Website	https://covinform.eu
Consortium	<p>SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO), Austria</p> <p>Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA), Israel</p> <p>Samur Proteccion Civil (SAMUR), Spain</p> <p>Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC), Italy</p> <p>SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS), Germany</p> <p>Trilateral Research LTD (TRI UK), UK</p> <p>Trilateral Research LTD (TRI IE), Ireland</p> <p>Kentro Meleton Asfaleias – Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), Greece</p> <p>Factor Social Consultoria em Psicossociologia e Ambiente LDA (FS), Portugal</p> <p>Austrian Red Cross (AUTRC), Austria</p> <p>Media Diversity Institute (MDI), UK</p> <p>Societatea Națională de Cruce Rosie Din România – Romanian Red Cross (SNCRR), Romania</p> <p>University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN), Belgium</p> <p>Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA), Italy</p> <p>University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC), Spain</p> <p>Swansea University (SU), UK</p> <p>Gotenborg University (UGOT), Sweden</p>

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors, and in no way represents the view of the European Commission or its services.

Deliverable

Number	D5.7
Title	Analysis: Public health responses and impact – update M33
Lead beneficiary	MDA
Work package	WP5
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Nature	Report (RE)
Due date	31.07.2023
Submission date	27.07.2023
Authors	<p>Rut Van Caudenberg, UANTWERPEN Hannah Robinson, UANTWERPEN Lore Van Praag, UANTWERPEN Chaim Rafalowski, MDA Itamar Laist, MDA</p>
Contributors	<p>Neda Deneva, SYNYO Viktoria Adler, SYNYO Vanessa Moser, SYNYO Vanessa Götz, SYNYO James Edwards, SINUS Isabella Tautscher, SINUS Ioannis Bagkatzounis, KEMEA Ioannis Konstantopoulos, KEMEA Elena Ambrosetti, SAPIENZA Carla Ventre, UCSC Beatriz Rosa, FS Benjamin Trump, FS José Manuel Palma-Oliveira, FS Rebeca Chaby, FS Manuel Tamayo Sáez, URJC Isabel Bazaga Fernández, URJC Antonio Rodríguez González, URJC Marina Ghersetti, UGOT Bengt Johansson, UGOT Zainab Mehdi, TRI Diana Beljaars, SU Sergei Shubin, SU</p>

Reviewers**Antonio Rodríguez González, URJC****Document history**

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	10.06.2023	Initial country reports received
0.2	26.06.2023	Final country reports (after feedback and changes) received
0.3	12.06.2023	Submission for internal review
1.0	27.07.2023	Submission of the deliverable

Executive Summary

This report presents an analysis of COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of the public health response. The report focuses on specific public health responses and their impacts on COVID-19, comprising ten country reports: Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Portugal, Italy, Spain, Sweden, the UK and Wales. These reports provide an overview of how the pandemic was managed in terms of public health responses, including changes over time and lessons learned.

This report has focused on the following four dimensions of public health response:

1. Comparative definitions and operationalization of health vulnerabilities, including pre-existing conditions and comorbidities, mental health vulnerabilities, and social precarity
2. Social and cultural factors influencing public health responses
3. Institutional, legal, and data collection factors influencing public health responses
4. Public health communication and epidemiological outcomes
5. Impacts of COVID-19 on health care workers

To explore the public health responses overtime, the following time points were considered:

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020

T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination influenced measures

T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022

The information included in this report is complemented by country frameworks (Annex 2). The frameworks consist of nested systems (Resource Systems and Units, Governance Systems, Actor Systems/Users; a description of the Interaction Area and Outcomes). This is connected to social, economic, and political settings and related ecosystems.

Contents

- Executive Summary 5
- 1 Introduction..... 8
- 2 Methodology 9
- 3 Country Reports 11
 - 3.1 Austria 11
 - 3.2 Belgium..... 14
 - 3.3 Germany 19
 - 3.4 Greece 30
 - 3.5 Italy 34
 - 3.6 Portugal 40
 - 3.7 Spain 47
 - 3.8 Sweden 54
 - 3.9 England 62
 - 3.10 Wales..... 67
- 4 Summary..... 71
- References..... 75
- Annex 1 Country Report Template..... 956
- Annex 2 Country Frames 957
- Annex 3 Cross-country Indicators 139

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
WHO	World Health Organization
ICU	Intensive Care Unit(s)
LTHCW	Long-term Healthcare Worker(s)
FPS	Federal Public Service
GP	General Practitioners
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
SHI	Social Health Insurance
PHI	Private Health Insurance
HCW	Healthcare Worker(s)
LTI	Long-term Insurance
ECDC	European Center for Disease Prevention and Control
DM	Decision Maker(s)
LTC	Long Term Care

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents an analysis of COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of WP5: public health response. The report focuses on specific public health responses and their impacts on COVID-19. It is based on ten country reports, which provide an overview of how the pandemic was managed in terms of public health responses, including changes over time and lessons learned. The country reports are based on expert interviews and references to country reports for T5.1, D5.1, and D5.5. Furthermore, the report includes frames for each country at the end, which were developed based on the T5.1 country report, D5.5, data from the dashboard, and updated with the latest information which became available after D5.5 was submitted. These frames include some important indicators at country-level taken from the dashboard developed in the context of WP2 and provide an overview of the main themes addressed in the D5.7 country reports, considering different time periods during the pandemic.

For WP5, the research questions are as follows:

- RQ1: How have COVID-19 public health responses been received, implemented and adapted across diverse local contexts and groups?
- RQ2: How have vulnerabilities and structural health inequalities been addressed and/or exacerbated by COVID-19 public health responses?
- RQ3: How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted health care workers across diverse contexts and care settings?

The country reports from this deliverable will be used as the basis for the D5.8 deliverable to address the research questions through cross-country analysis and synthesis.

The current report studies 10 COVINFORM countries: Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Sweden, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Wales, and England. The report starts off with an introductory chapter (Chapter 1), followed by an overview of the methods used to carry out the empirical research (Chapter 2). Here, particular attention is paid to the structure of the country reports completed by COVINFORM partners, and the governance framework (Ostrom's SES framework) adopted to accompany the country reports across all countries. In chapter 3, the country reports are presented. The final chapter (Chapter 4) provides a summary of the key findings across the COVINFORM countries organised around the predefined chapter themes. The key findings will be explored in further detail in the D5.8 deliverable "*Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts*" due in M35.

2 Methodology

The COVINFORM overarching research questions are:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practised?
- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response to certain vulnerable groups?
- RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

This deliverable addresses the overarching research questions in relation to WP5 *Public Health Responses and Impact Assessment*. The COVINFORM team is doing this by providing an update of the initial analysis of the findings presented in D5.3 report “*Analysis: Public health responses and impact*”. The analysis presented here utilises the data from D5.3, but also incorporates in a coherent and systematised way data from D5.1 report “*Baseline report: Public Health Responses*” and D5.5 report “*Baseline report: Public Health Responses, an update*”. Updated information has been incorporated from additional sources. In addition, the report incorporates data from the WP5 expert interviews conducted with health care workers and public health decision/policy makers, which were also analysed in D5.3. *Analysis: Public Health Responses and Impact*. As such, the empirical material presented in this report contains information from the previous deliverables, as well as updated information and to some extent new data. The data has been organised in country reports and so-called country frames for all the 10 countries, completed by COVINFORM partners.

The country reports, presented in Chapter 3, follow standardised questions template (Annex 1), which are in line with the Research questions and with the country frames. That way each country report represents an updated coherent and focused summary of the findings relevant for WP5. The template for the country report includes questions concerning the following aspect: planning of the response, crisis management responsibility, implementation and response, barriers to the crisis management in the field of public health, public reaction to the crisis management, including social and cultural factors influencing the response. As a key factor of analysis to the COVINFORM project we also explored vulnerabilities acknowledged by governments and how they changed over time, the emergence of new vulnerabilities, responses in relation to vulnerable groups and how they were supported, and any new vulnerabilities that were created because of response measures. All these aspects are traced over time, prior the pandemic, in the beginning when the pandemic hit, and during the different stages, including introduction of vaccination, and the spread of the Omicron, following and explaining in more details data introduced in the country frames.

Each country report is accompanied with a governance framework (known as Ostrom’s SES framework) also referred to as country frame in this deliverable. The country frames can be found in Annex 2. Known for being an empirically applied conceptual framework, the purpose of the framework is to analyse complex social systems. The analysis approach does not have a methodological guide, which means this enables flexibility in how it may be adapted to diverse contexts. The frameworks consist of nested systems (Resource Systems and Units, Governance Systems, Actor Systems/Users; a description of the Interaction Area and Outcomes). This is connected to social, economic, and political settings and

related ecosystems. An explanation of the SES framework methodology can be found in D3.2: “Multi-site research design and methodological framework”.

In this deliverable, as well as in all of COVINFORMS Dx.7 deliverables, we used the SES framework to organise the data that we have collected over the course of the project in a systematic manner. We chose three different points in time (see below) to illustrate what has been done in terms of governmental crisis response and how this has changed over time. As such, the country frames are a visualisation of the cornerstones of governmental pandemic response and its changes over time, following the logic of the Ostrom model. Finally, the SES approach and the country frames will allow to contextualise the COVINFORM case studies (WP3) in a national setting as the same methodology is used.

The Ostrom model consists of five sub-systems below which we have operationalised as follows:

Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to a country and to manage a (health) crisis.

Governance Systems (GS) – describes the basic structure of how a country is governed in relation to a (health) crisis.

Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis management in a country.

Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the governmental crisis response.

Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. In this concrete case it mostly describes measures taken to manage the health crisis (e.g., lockdowns, etc.).¹

This deliverable has taken into consideration three different phases: pre-pandemic, T1 – initial stages from 2020 until vaccination rollout had an effect on measures, and T2, from Omicron appearance until now. In this way, it focuses on temporality and change during the COVID-19 pandemic in order to understand the impact of the pandemic and its measures, key findings and best practices.

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020

T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures

T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022

Annex 3 presents a table with the cross-country indicators also provided in the country frames, in three moments in time, as collected for the dashboard.

¹ In the country frames T0 the Interaction area is empty as T0 indicates the time prior to COVID-19. Hence, no interaction was taking place yet.

3 Country Reports

The following ten country reports present the basis for the analysis of the COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of WP5: public health response. These country reports will be taken up in the D5.8 deliverable to answer the overarching research questions in a cross-country analysis and synthesis.

3.1 Austria

Public health system and main actors

The Austrian healthcare system is composed of structures and actors with shared responsibilities on national level, sub-national level and self-administration bodies (social insurance). These actors further contribute to financing the health system. The Federal Government, with legislative and executive jurisdiction, assumes a central role. The Federal Ministry of Labour Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection (BMSGPK) is responsible for general healthcare policy and protection of public health in particular. It drafts legislation and functions as a decision maker, a supervisory authority, and also as a coordinator among the key actors in the healthcare system. In the hospital area, legislative and executive responsibilities lie with the individual provinces. The states (Bundesländer) are responsible for hospitals and other public health facilities. Health insurance bodies (ÖGK and others) provide coverage for almost 99% of the population. Other key actors are AGES which controls and regulates infectious disease spread, medication use, etc, and the Oberste Sanitätsrat, which is an advisory body to the Ministry. In addition, a National Vaccination Committee, composed of medical experts and national and state administrative representatives, advised on vaccine use and safety.

The available resources for planning the pandemic

In 2019, current health expenditure in Austria calculated according to SHA amounted to 41,483 million euros or 10.4% of gross domestic product (GDP). In addition, investments in the health sector accounted for 2,675 million euros. In the period from 2004 to 2019, current health expenditure (at current prices) increased by an average of 3.9% (Statistik Austria, 2021). The health expenditure as a share of GDP is 10.4 % and 74.0 % of current health expenditure is public health expenditure.

In Austria, health system expenses are relatively high compared to the EU average. In 2015, approximately 74% of all expenses were financed from public funds and around 26% from private sources. Over 99% of the Austrian population is covered with health insurance and compulsory contributions are required from all employed people. Unemployed people, retired people, people receiving minimum income, and asylum seekers are also insured by different bodies. However, persons without legal residence must pay out-of-pocket. Emergency services are freely available to everyone.

Health crisis preparedness plans, the changes over time and the public reaction

Austria has an acting Austrian epidemic act. It also has an National Influenza Plan from 2006, which was considered outdated/ Vulnerable groups are only included in a generic way in the National Influenza Plan.

Crisis management implementation

At the time of the COVID-19 outbreak, there was no national pandemic plan. There was only the National Influenza Plan, which has not been updated since 2006, and was therefore considered not suitable for the COVID-19 pandemic. The only instrument which was in force during the pandemic was the Austrian Epidemic Act 1950 which has not undergone any major changes since its emergence. The first package of measures introduced by the Austrian government was released on March 15, 2020 (including the first lockdown). The COVID-19 Act contained several COVID-19 specific legislative instruments and was the fastest law ever enacted since the existence of the Second Republic (Pollak, Kowarz, and Partheymüller, 2020).

In Austria, the COVID-19 pandemic caused political upheaval, with major changes in the political leadership since the outbreak, particularly in the roles of the Federal Chancellor and the Minister of Health. In addition, the Austrian population had to endure a harsh regime of measures, especially lockdowns. The delta variant led to overcrowding in intensive care units (ICUs) and the introduction of a triage system in some provinces in November 2021. Measures taken to prevent its spread included the 2G rule, lockdowns for unvaccinated people, and universal vaccination (Pollak et al. 2021). According to the experts, the vaccination strategy was generally judged to be not very successful. There were also mixed feelings about the implementation of the contact tracing system. However, testing has been an overall success in Austria.

At the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis, an overwhelming majority of citizens supported the measures taken by the government, such as closing businesses, imposing curfews, and punishing non-compliance with the new rules (Partheymüller, Plescia, Kritzing, 2020). At the same time citizens expressed scepticism about possible new measures that were particularly aimed at the targeted "surveillance of the individual citizen", which related to the testing strategy and contact tracing. Data protection is held in very high regard by the population in German-speaking countries and were also subject during the conducted expert interviews:

- One of the interviewees pointed out that disaggregated data collection, especially related to the identification of risk and vulnerability indices, was very weak in Austria due to the strict data protection law. Public health institutions such as in the UK and Denmark managed to adapt their digital environment before the strict regulations on data collection and processing, also at European level, came into force.
- There was also tension between the protection of data and the protection of health. Health data is identified as a special form of data and is therefore not easily accessible, also for public health institutions. Because of this reason, it was not simple to identify e.g., health vulnerabilities.

Initially, the public reacted overall positively to the measures taken by the government (Kittel et al. 2020). There was also a high level of perceived solidarity among the population (ibid.). In March, the proportion of those who would have liked to see stricter measures and rules exceeded the ones who would like to see them relaxed. However, satisfaction decreased steadily the longer the measures were in place, especially after June 2020 with the decrease in registered cases. Trust in public institutions also changed over time. Institutions that are responsible for public security and health, like the Police, the Austrian Military, and the Public Health System, and which enjoyed a high level of trust in Austria even before the corona crisis, have lost very little trust throughout the pandemic, whereas trust in political institutions, such as the parliament, steadily declined.

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

Like in other countries, Austria's approach to vulnerable groups during the pandemic from a health perspective was foremost focused on protecting the population from contracting the virus and on preventing severe outcomes. At the beginning of the pandemic, especially elderly people, chronically ill and people with immune deficiency diseases as well as pregnant women were considered as vulnerable. The measures to protect and support certain vulnerable groups were focused primarily on physical distancing, and later access to vaccines. The elderly were considered at a higher risk of severe outcomes, therefore special measures were taken for social distancing. Visits in nursing homes and to hospitals were forbidden for a period. Later, visits were allowed, but under strict testing conditions. Vaccination also happened in waves, prioritising those vulnerable groups. People who are considered as high-risk due to their health status, were protected by the general law on social insurance (Sozialversicherungsgesetz) by granting them the right to home office, paid leave, and protective gear. These measures were not mandatory for employers. Pregnant women had additional rights to protection at their workplace and to early maternity leave.

While the focus on the elderly, chronically ill and people with immune deficiency diseases, as well as pregnant women, aimed at protecting them from COVID-19, the measures resulted in ignoring other health conditions, slowing down prevention, and exacerbating mental health problems in certain groups. Collateral health vulnerabilities occurred in Austria. Cancer patients experienced delays in their treatment (Reuter-Oppermann et al., 2020). There was a decrease in prevention and new early diagnosis of potentially curable diagnosed gynaecological and breast cancer (Tsibulak et al., 2020); Non-emergency surgeries were delayed, for example heart operations had to be postponed ever more often in the course of the pandemic due to the overload of Corona patients in the intensive care units, as of the President of the Austrian Society for Cardiac and Thoracic Vascular Surgery stated (OTS, 2021).

Another vulnerable group which was affected disproportionately by the COVID-19 measures were people with psychological disorders, as those who already had a history of mental health disorders or treatments reported higher anxiety and / or depression levels, plus only a third of those who had received treatment before the pandemic continued to do so during lockdown (Simon et al., 2021). As mental health has deteriorated for many during COVID-19 but there are not enough therapy sites that are fully paid for by insurance, the Austrian Regional Health Insurance (ÖGK) pleaded to increase insurance paid therapy by 20.000 extra places on treatment programs (Holzmüller, 2021).

Regarding the elderly, although in the beginning of the pandemic and especially during the lockdowns they expressed higher levels of loneliness (Stolz et al., 2020), uncertainty and worries, they proved to be quite resilient and less affected by the restrictions as previously assumed (Pfabigan et al., 2022). However, residents of nursing homes were more at risk compared to elderly living at home, and represented one third of all COVID-19 deaths (Kurzthaler et al., 2020).

The pre-existing disparities in regards to long term care-takers, also became more apparent during the pandemic, placing them at higher risk. Care workers faced scarcity of masks and security gear, and a sudden travel restriction (for those commuting from neighbouring countries) causing them to lose their income entirely or suffer from physical and emotional stress due to prolonged shifts (Schmidt et al., 2020). In order to alleviate the HCW dropout Austria installed a 100 million Euro LTC support fund (Schmidt et al., 2020), and facilitated the possibility of transnational mobility. Yet, those measures are

criticised to be “short-term solutions that fail [...] to acknowledge the fundamental flaws and inequalities of a care model that relies primarily on female migrant workers and wage differentials within Europe.” (Leibfingher et al., 2020) Thus, informal care takers lacked support and live-in personal carers lacked political acknowledgement (Leichsenring et al., 2021). A report from 2021 found that many care workers leaving the sector due to poor payment, bad working conditions and exhaustion elicited from the pandemic (The Social Employers 2022).

People with physical disabilities, especially those who are blind or visually impaired, reported that carers who belong to certain support services and normally help them with their day-to-day tasks decreased home visits due to risk of infection or to child-care responsibilities after school-closures. That caused staff shortages within support services. Additionally, people with physical disabilities often faced recklessness and discrimination towards them. Blind or visually impaired people reported verbal abuse, especially on public transport, since it was not so easy for them to keep their distance from others due to their limitations and without the help of their carers. They also mentioned a lack of support in public spaces, e.g., because broken traffic lights for visually handicapped people were not fixed or level differences at construction zones were no longer adjusted.

The overloaded and overstretched medical system did not only affect the patients, but also the medical staff. Medical staff faced issues such as financial problems, lack of close partners, longer working hours, violence in patient care and stigmatisation due to the caretaking of COVID-19 patients all leading to them being at a high risk for burnout (Leibfingher, et al., 2021). Furthermore, medical or care staff did not have enough protective equipment in the early phase of the pandemic and criticised having received insufficient information on the specifics of the COVID-19 infection, making them especially vulnerable to psychosomatic health issues (insomnia, digestive issues, headache) (Lenger et al., 2023; Siebenhofer et al., 2021).

Health vulnerableness often overlaps with socio-economic vulnerabilities. For example, persons with a migration background experienced additional disadvantages. A considerable share of COVID-19 infected persons are from a migration background, which most likely result from dense housing conditions, language or cultural barriers (Baltaci, 2020). In the early phase of the pandemic, key information on security and hygiene measures as well as national regulations were not immediately translated into different languages, which complicated the communication with people concerned. Moreover, people with a migration background are overrepresented in systemically important professions, like care work, agricultural work, food industries and retails, which lead to a higher risk of exposure to the virus (Krejca, 2020).

3.2 Belgium

Public health system and main actors

Belgium has a compulsory health insurance system based on proportional social security contributions from taxable income (Kulesher & Forrestal, 2014). The system is structured to provide the majority of care through private, not-for-profit organisations under state framework (Gerken & Merkur, 2010), (European Commission, 2019). The Belgian health system is managed by the Federal Public Service (FPS) and three community Ministries of Health (Hanover Comms, 2020). Regional governments are responsible for certain areas such as maternity and child health, health promotion, some elderly care, and hospital accreditation standards (Vandijk & Annemans, 2009). Primary health

care is provided by general practitioners (GPs), physiotherapists, nurses, and other healthcare professionals (Gerken & Merkur, 2010).

In 2017, the expenditure on health in Belgium was EUR 3554 per capita, which represents 10.3% of GDP (OECD, 2019). In 2015, there were 113 general practitioners per 100,000 inhabitants (European Commission, 2019). However, the wages of many health workers, such as assistant nurses (zorgkundige), are relatively low compared to the average Belgian wage (Le Bacq, 2010).

Health crisis preparedness plans

Prior to COVID-19, pandemic preparedness was the responsibility of federal government actors and the public health institute Sciensano (Desson et al. 2020). Belgium has a National Pandemic Influenza Plan from 2006 that emphasises tailored communication strategies for different audiences, yet the plan lacks specificity on vulnerable populations, recovery, and evaluation of mitigation measures. (Belgisch Raadgevend Comité voor Bio-ethiek 2009). An advisory report was issued in 2009 regarding the 2006 plan. (See [D5.5](#))

Crisis management implementation

An overview of COVID-19 measures implemented in Belgium can be found [here](#) (in Dutch). The Belgian government and federated entities have been responsible for managing the country's COVID-19 response. The Prime Minister, Health Minister, COVID-19 Commissioner Pedro Facon, and Minister of Security and Internal Affairs Annelies Verlinden have been key decision-makers throughout the pandemic. Epidemiologists from Sciensano and other health risk experts have provided critical guidance and advice to decision-makers throughout the pandemic. (Desson et al., 2020) The Governors of Belgian provinces and Mayors of cities have also played an important role in implementing and enforcing COVID-19 restrictions at the local level.

The Expert Committee on Management Strategy (GEMS), consisting of 24 medical experts, has provided recommendations to the government on COVID-19 management strategies. The Interfederal Task Force on Testing Policy has been responsible for developing and implementing testing policies across the country (Facon, 2020).

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

Belgium is a small country in the heart of Europe with a high population density and the COVID-19 pandemic has put tremendous pressure on its public health system. Hospitals in Belgium expanded ICU capacity and created new emergency care shifts to cope with the surge in COVID-19 patients and normal care activities were paused to prioritise COVID-19 patients. Additional hygiene measures and procedures were instituted to prevent the spread of the virus. In spring 2020, there was a shortage of personal protective equipment (PPE) which created difficulties for health workers where the initial distribution of face masks to health workers was slow and chaotic (Desson et al., 2020). Problems were encountered with care homes due to a lack of PPE, which was highlighted in the Amnesty International report in 2020 (Amnesty International België, 2020). The slow implementation of lockdown also created problems for vulnerable groups and the division of responsibilities at the federal, regional, and local level led to confusion and inefficiency in the COVID-19 response. The creation of a caretaker government also added to these issues.

The Working Group on the Social Impact of the COVID-19 crisis (WG SIC) was established in the spring of 2020 to monitor and evaluate the socio-economic impact of the pandemic, while the Taskforce for Vulnerable Groups has focused on the impact on different vulnerable groups. (FPS Social Security, 2020) In July 2020, 500 million euros were invested in healthcare workers' wages over two years, 100 million for better working conditions, and 400 million previously approved for extra personnel. In November 2020, hospital staff received COVID-19 compensation: 985 euros incentive bonus, and staff in other care centres received a one-time "consumption cheque" of 300 euros before tax (VAZG, 2020b). A structural wage increase for Flemish health workers was announced and rolled out in the summer of 2021 (Andries, 2020).

Belgium is also changing its pandemic preparedness structure based on the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic. The testing and tracing strategies were evaluated by a special committee report in September 2021 (De Kamer 2021, 132–34). The EDC report evaluated SARS-CoV-2 testing policy in Belgium from June to December 2021 (ECDC 2022). Sciensano published a thematic report on vaccination coverage and epidemiological impact of the COVID-19 vaccination campaign in Belgium in October 2021 (Sciensano, 2021). The Vaccination Task Force report in March 2022 delved into vaccination challenges (Task Force Vaccinatie 2022).

Belgium's complex government structure complicates crisis management, according to respondents in interviews conducted in autumn 2021. The crisis has largely been managed by national and regional levels, with little local crisis management occurring. However, this was expected to change with the end of the federal phase of crisis management. Respondents expressed confusion about who was responsible for collaboration processes. One respondent acknowledged that the centralisation of control in the pandemic's early stages restricted the use of local knowledge and expertise.

"It is not easy, crisis management in Belgium, because of a whole series of factors, including the complex structure of the country. The number of task forces, crisis cells, working groups at the national level, regional level... I can't keep track of them." (Public Health_1, Belgium)

Respondents discussed data issues, particularly the pressure to release data, concerns about stigmatisation and ownership of data.

"There has been, and still is, a lot of pressure on Sciensano to make open data. Because people wanted figures, detailed figures. So we have always tried to be as transparent as possible, and to present data in detail. There is a lot of pressure for figures, and we are sometimes afraid that those figures will not always be interpreted correctly [...] especially if you have more sensitive figures about COVID in vulnerable groups, vulnerable neighbourhoods, etc." (Public Health_1, Belgium)

Both public health experts agreed that local crisis management would become increasingly important in the future. One (Public Health_1, Belgium) emphasised the need to give people at the local level the necessary tools to plan and implement local-level policy, stating, *"They should be given guidelines on what to do, who to call if something happens, and where to get our data."* The importance of local-level collaborations in public health responses was also stressed (Public Health_2) but it was also noted that it was necessary to have people *"who can break free from their institutional ties"* and *"go right through the red tape"* in emergency scenarios.

Regarding the role of national crisis management, interviewees agreed that there needs to be clarity about who coordinates general crisis management and defines the role of the national crisis level. It was stated (Public Health_1, Belgium) that most people agreed there needs to be “*a certain level of national crisis management*”, but the extent of their role needs to be further specified. According to (Public Health_2, Belgium) national level-framework needs to “*outline a general framework*”, but it should “*not go too far in detail*”, to leave space for flexibility and local-level adaptation. “*Within that framework, you have to be as local as possible.*”

The same respondent (Public Health_2, Belgium) also stressed the need for operational research to inform and guide decision-making. He suggested that data should be made available immediately to world-class researchers, who can then use it to steer decision-making.

“We also have to learn to do operational research. Yes, now the studies [about COVID-19] are coming and they are going to tell us what was going on, a year ago. That's fine, and I'd like to know, but it could have been done earlier.”

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

During the pandemic, broadly speaking two categories of vulnerability were acknowledged in public health strategies in Belgium: i) medically or clinically vulnerable people, referring to people who are considered at higher risk of falling seriously ill or dying from COVID-19, and ii) socially vulnerable people, referring to vulnerability relating to individuals' or groups' social position in society. Regarding the first category, the main at-risk groups that are considered in public health documents include the elderly, adults with type 2 diabetes; adults with severe chronic cardiovascular, lung or kidney disease; and adults with decreased immunity and/or cancer (VAZG, 2020). Different types of social vulnerability that are identified in documents from the Belgian Vulnerable Groups Task Force relate to occupational vulnerability, vulnerability resulting from material and social deprivation, vulnerable families with children, and vulnerability due to homelessness and legal status (Task Force Kwetsbare Groepen, 2020). While social vulnerability is acknowledged, medical vulnerability is more consistently defined and referred to in policy documents and COVID-19 responses. A clear example of this is the Belgian COVID-19 vaccination strategy where medical vulnerability (defined in terms of age and medical risk factors) was the most important type of vulnerability used to guide prioritisation in the order in which people have been vaccinated.

As far as healthcare workers are concerned, many of them have faced extraordinarily high workloads, stress and risk infection as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The drastic transformation of health workers' working reality also created a great deal of physical and psycho-emotional pressure (UHasselt, 2020). This was already apparent during the first wave, but it became even more pronounced during the second wave. Health workers have become fatigued and have been reported to fall ill more frequently (De Standaard, 2020). During the vaccination roll-out, healthcare workers were acknowledged as a vulnerable group in the sense that they were included in the first priority group to get vaccinated, together with residents and employees of residential care centres.

In the beginning of the pandemic, the focus was almost exclusively on the medical aspect of COVID-19 and on limiting the circulation of the virus as much as possible. Furthermore, policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic were very much geared towards the middle class and failed to take into account more vulnerable groups. This led to a delay in addressing the needs of specific groups. Respondents

cited the difficulty of balancing uniform guidelines with adapting measures to people's needs. *“Especially in the beginning, when society was completely locked down, it [the measures] was just really tailor-made for families that live in a big house, so to speak.”*, a general practitioner explained. *“(…) During the full national lockdown, they did not take it [vulnerability] into account at all.”* (Public Health_3, Belgium). A public health policy maker highlighted that also the first relaxation measures were ideal for middle class families living in suburban areas with large backyards, but problematic for more vulnerable groups living in small apartments in the city:

“When you look at the measures from back then (…) at one point they said ‘the garden centres will reopen, you can have a BBQ.’ But, of course, when you’re someone living in the city, unless you live in a house with a backyard, well, these measures make no sense. So you don’t reach that part of the population. In the beginning, they paid much too little attention to this.” (Public Health_1, Belgium)

As the pandemic progressed, more attention was paid to social vulnerability as well. For instance, the Task Force for Vulnerable Groups introduced several measures to specifically address the needs of groups of people facing material and social deprivation and to protect the health and wellbeing of those without secure housing (Task Force Kwetsbare Groepen, 2020). These measures included an extension of facilities to offer shelter and psycho-medical-social support for homeless people and offering food aid to anyone living below the poverty threshold regardless of their legal status (ibid.).

Another group of people that initially did not receive a lot of attention in COVID-19 responses were children and young people. *“In the beginning they did not pay a lot of attention to what the impact of the lockdown would be on children (…) Let alone on children in precarious situations, because that adds another dimension [of vulnerability] to it”*, a public health policy maker (Public Health_1, Belgium) explained. However, especially due to the impact of school closures, relatively quick measures were taken to help vulnerable families with children, including investments into ICT material and support for socially vulnerable children and young people in order to try to ‘seal the digital gap’ (ibid.). Furthermore, keeping the schools open became an absolute priority, especially in the Flemish context.

While, next to medical and clinical vulnerability, social vulnerability was taken into account more as the pandemic progressed, there was still a huge difference in the impact of and the possibility to comply with the measures for different groups of people. Indeed, the experts criticised the fact that the feasibility of the measures was hardly taken into account. In this context, they discussed, for instance, the impact of quarantine measures in the case of high-risk contact for large families. Especially when one household member after the other tested positive for COVID-19, this often resulted in an extended period of quarantine for the entire family:

“There was this family with six children who all took turns testing positive, every seven days. So they all had to stay inside. So they spent an entire summer vacation inside in a two bedroom apartment. Yes, I think that’s being vulnerable in a different way. None of them became super ill, but they did spend the entire time locked up in an apartment.” (Public Health_4, Belgium)

For some people going into quarantine also meant losing income, which caused a lot of frustration and stress. *“That’s something we also noted”*, a general practitioner stated, *“that some people were like ‘I cannot comply with this [measure], because then I cannot pay the bills’”*. (Public Health_3, Belgium).

Apart from the impact of the pandemic, and particularly school closures, on children, the impact on the parents of those children was something the interviewees also noticed: *“parents of young children who really are reaching their limit, with all those lockdowns and school closures”* (Public Health_4, Belgium). In that sense, parents of small children who often had to juggle childcare with professional responsibilities were considered a ‘new form of vulnerable group’.

Furthermore, due to the restriction of physical encounters, a lot of things suddenly had to happen online. According to one interviewee (Public Health_3, Belgium) COVID-19 has impacted patients' ability to access health services, with fear of getting infected and isolation being significant barriers. Mental health care and specialised care were also affected, and some patients faced delays in treatment. His practice utilised teleconsulting and video consulting to improve patient access. Furthermore, efforts were made to encourage vaccination, but language and technological barriers and vaccine hesitancy among younger patients remained challenges. This not only affected people with limited digital skills or limited knowledge of the language(s) of the online platforms, but also entirely excluded people without official documents or a national insurance number.

“Everything became digital, ‘ah yes, you have to fill in an e-form and then you can make an appointment with the number on your e-form.’ But they don’t have an identity card so they can’t fill in the e-form. And then they come to our practice the next day and [we have to say] ‘no, you have to do it online’ ...” (Public Health_3, Belgium)

As this quote from a general practitioner illustrates, the impossibility to use the digital alternatives severely limited these people’s access to crucial services, including healthcare services. A similar issue was found during the initial stages of the vaccination roll-out, when people were required to make an appointment online. *“In the beginning we were dealing with people of 80 years old, 85 years old. When on top of that they don’t master Dutch, how do you expect these people to register to get vaccinated?”*, a public health policy maker (Public Health_2, Belgium) noted. Finally, for certain groups the COVID-19 pandemic also created feelings of loneliness, sometimes aggravating already existing mental health issues. General practitioners noticed a lack of self-care and a rise in suicide attempts. In this context young single recently-arrived migrants without any family or friends nearby were considered a particularly vulnerable group: *“they’re here alone, they have no friends. Sometimes they have those gatherings where they meet each other in a sort of café, but that wasn’t allowed. So they were all alone.”* (Public Health_4, Belgium).

It was suggested that it is important to involve local leaders in community engagement to improve outreach to non-native speakers.

(Public Health_3, Belgium) *“Yes, there are missed opportunities, I think, to reach those non-native speakers specifically. But that's also difficult because we now have so many languages. [...] These are also things that you might be able to do from within the community itself, that if you approach those key figures from the community, they can provide more education about it. I think it would help a lot if you were to focus more on community health workers. Instead of a picture of Marc van Ranst [Belgian virologist] getting vaccinated.”*

3.3 Germany

Public health system and main actors

In principle, the German healthcare system offers nearly-universal insurance coverage and care access. Coverage is split into public social health insurance (SHI) and private health insurance (PHI) (OECD & WHO, 2019). Around 90% of Germans use statutory healthcare (SHI), which provides a standardised benefits package. It is mostly financed through labour-income-dependent contributions, supported by a government subsidy. There is also a risk adjustment mechanism that disseminates funds to overview the actual costs for morbidity.

Responsibilities for health system governance is shared between national and sub-national levels (Commission Services & Economic Policy Committee, 2019). Generally, the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG) is responsible for health policymaking, whereas the states (Länder) are responsible for the local interpretation and implementation of regulations, as well as medical education, inpatient capacities, and capital investments for hospitals. The major decision-making body in the statutory health insurance system is the Federal Joint Committee, which is formed by the German Hospital Federation and the National Association of Health Insurance Funds, as well as doctors' and dentists' associations (Commission Services & Economic Policy Committee, 2019). The Federal Joint Committee is in charge of the translation of legislative objectives and the formulation of legislative objectives in general, specifically issuing directives for payers, providers, patients and manufacturers. For organograms, please see Busse & Blümel (2013).

Patients are free to choose any doctor under contract with their sickness fund; SHI normally has collective contracts which cover provision of all doctors within a region. Usually, primary care is provided by private doctors, most of whom work in an individual practice. The number of physicians has risen over the past decade, with 414 per 100,000 inhabitants in 2015, which is well above the EU average of 344. The same is the case for hospital beds: the country has the highest number of hospital beds per-capita for curative care in the EU: in 2015, 611 compared to the EU average of 402. The SHI covers inpatient and outpatient hospital care, preventive services, dental and mental healthcare, physician services, physical therapy, optometry, medical aids, prescription drugs (unless explicitly excluded by law), rehabilitation, palliative and hospice care, maternal leave and pregnancy care as well as sick leave compensation. The preventive services include check-ups in the following: dental care, child, basic immunisations, chronic diseases, cancer screening (Commission Services & Economic Committee, 2019).

Whereas the German healthcare system is generally regarded as effective, some healthcare workers (HCW) respondents interviewed during the course of the project indicated that communication channels between institutions on the national, state, municipal, and local levels were sometimes ineffective, with the higher levels failing to solicit or take into account information about conditions on the ground on lower levels:

"[As a crisis develops] it would be a good idea in all practices [and institutions] to just simply ask how things actually look on the ground!" (WP5_SINUS_7)

In Germany, long-term insurance (LTC) is also compulsory. There are 5 degrees of care defined by LTC insurance, which are based on the assessment of capacities, such as mobility, cognitive and communicative abilities, illness or therapy-related activities, self-reliance, social contacts, etc. (Commission Services & Economic Policy Committee, 2019). As in the healthcare system in general, patients who exceed allowed expenditures must cover the difference (though in principle, social assistance is accessible for those without private means).

The legal foundations for pandemic planning in Germany are the 2001 Protection against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG); the 2015 crisis management strategy; and the 2017 National Pandemic Plan. The 2017 National Pandemic Plan encompasses general health system governance, medical responses, non-pharmaceutical interventions, hygiene measures, and risk communication, on the legal basis of the Protection Against Infection Act (RKI, 2017). It identifies three basic stages in an epidemic/pandemic:

- “Containment”, during which public health authorities should focus on preventing the introduction and spread of the virus, e.g., via detection and surveillance, contact tracing and quarantine, and the imposition of travel restrictions.
- “Protection”, during which the virus has already begun to spread uncontrollably and authorities should focus on protecting the capacity of the healthcare system and the wellbeing of individuals and groups most at risk of a severe progression, e.g., via imposition of non-pharmaceutical interventions (hygiene measures, social distancing measures, etc.) and provision of emergency support to healthcare institutions.
- “Mitigation”, during which the virus is already widespread and authorities should focus on improving their knowledge of at-risk groups and developing targeted interventions; continuing to work to ensure the healthcare system can support those with severe progressions; improving means of surveillance and monitoring; improving communications measures and community engagement to develop bottom-up resilience; and (when possible) maximising vaccine uptake.

The 2015 crisis management strategy, on the other hand, establishes basic decision-making bodies – i.e., inter-ministerial task forces – for crises including pandemics. Protocol in a pandemic is to form a joint Federal Ministry of Health (BMG) and Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) task force (Krisenstab BMI/BMG), which is responsible for advising the Federal Government and implementing policies set by the Government. Every ministry is represented on the joint task force by liaison officers. Other bodies with which the task force coordinates include the Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Response (BBK), the Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW), and the Robert Koch Institute (RKI), particularly the RKI Standing Committee on Vaccination (STIKO).

Crisis management implementation

The first case of COVID-19 in Germany was recorded on January 27, 2020. In accordance with the crisis management strategy and National Pandemic Plan, in February 2020, a joint BMG/BMI task force was established to run point on pandemic governance. On 4 March, the Robert Koch Institute updated the National Pandemic Plan in response to the pandemic (RKI 2020b). On 11 March, the Chancellor asked the population to voluntarily restrict their social activities to help control the disease’s spread. On 16 March, a lockdown was announced, extending until 16 April. On March 25, the Bundestag identified the COVID-19 pandemic as an incident of national significance. On 28 March, the Federal Government passed the First Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance (Gesetz zum Schutz der Bevölkerung bei einer epidemischen Lage von nationaler Tragweite), which assigned the BMG extraordinary powers to control the pandemic.

In Germany, a number of interviews were conducted with healthcare workers (HCWs) active in the Mannheim area. The interviewees universally reported that the first months of the pandemic brought

heavier workloads, feelings of responsibility and inadequacy, confusion, anxiety, and stress. However, some interviewees also indicated that they were able to adapt surprisingly quickly:

"The additional workload was tremendously greater overnight." (WP5_SINUS_7)

"It was a very stark upheaval for us. Because suddenly we couldn't deal with old people or those in need of care as we would with normally – it was very painful for everyone" (WP5_SINUS_5)

"At the beginning it was difficult to realise how dangerous the disease might be for the patients, my staff, and myself, so we implemented all hygiene rules immediately. But after one month already, a certain calm has set in" (WP5_SINUS_4)

By April 2020, case rates began to decrease, and the national-level hard lockdown was phased out. Certain social distancing restrictions were kept in place throughout Summer, with restrictiveness dialled up and down on a state-by-state level in response to local key statistics (infection, hospitalisation, death, etc.). On 14 May, the Federal Government adopted the Second Act for the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance, which focused on improving testing capacities, better supporting HCWs and health institutions, and improving the state of scientific knowledge on the pandemic. Throughout Summer 2020, a focus on testing and tracing was maintained, with the introduction of the Corona-Warn-App as a highlight.

In October 2020, a second wave hit Germany, precipitating a second national-level hard lockdown on 2 November, originally extending until 19 December. On 18 November, the government adopted the Third Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance, which formalised the authorities' power to introduce more or less restrictive measures in accordance with prevailing conditions. There was some controversy with regard to whether to maintain lockdowns over the Christmas and New Year holidays; the different states adopted somewhat different approaches, but for the most part, restrictive measures were maintained (e.g., limits on social gatherings, shuttering of non-essential businesses and traditional Christmas markets, etc.).

As in established markets as a whole, the most significant development of Winter 2020 was the approval and rollout of vaccinations. On 9 December, the Robert Koch Institute issued preliminary recommendations for the prioritisation of vaccines, identifying six risk groups: Level 1: persons aged 80 and over; residents in senior and long-term care facilities; and HCWs and other care workers with an especially elevated risk of exposure. Level 2: persons aged 75-79; persons with Down Syndrome, dementia, or certain other psychological hindrances; and HCWs and other care workers with an elevated risk of exposure. Level 3: persons aged 70-74; persons with pre-existing medical conditions that are highly likely to lead to a more severe COVID-19 progression; residents and personnel in collective accommodations; persons in close contact with pregnant women; persons in close contact with HCWs and other care workers in Levels 1 or 2; HCWs and other care workers with a moderate risk of exposure. Level 4: persons aged 65-69; persons with pre-existing medical conditions that are moderately likely to lead to a more severe COVID-19 progression; persons in close contact with HCWs and other care workers in Level 3; HCWs and other care workers with a low risk of exposure; teachers and child carers; persons in precarious working or living situations. Level 5: persons aged 60-64; other occupational groups with an elevated risk of exposure. Level 6: the general population aged 59 and below.

On 21 December, the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine was approved, and on 27 December, the Moderna vaccine was approved. By end-of-year, ca. 200,000 Germans had been given their first vaccine – primarily members of groups at risk of contracting a severe progression of the disease.

Health crisis preparedness plans

Public health system: the public health system was not altered on a structural level. The First, Second, and Third Acts on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance did assign powers to the relevant authorities that were in accordance with the broad provisions of the 2001 Protection against Infection Act and the 2017 National Pandemic Plan, but for which there had been no perceived need to spell out in as great of detail. The Second Act furthermore consists of provisions to improve preventative testing under the statutory health insurance system (SHI); improve working conditions for HCWs, especially those involved in geriatric care; improve communications between the Robert Koch Institute and public health services; and improve flexibility and reduce bureaucracy within the insurance system, for the insured and healthcare providers alike. These can be considered substantial, if not structural, changes to the public health system.

National Pandemic Plan: the National Pandemic Plan was updated by the Robert Koch Institute on 4 March 2020. The update entailed recommendations specific to each of the three stages in pandemic management:

- “Containment” phase: enhanced early detection; intensified focus on society-wide and targeted testing; introduction of contact tracing apps (with adequate data protection and accompanying user sensitisation).
- “Protection” phase: consideration of hard lockdowns and other social distancing measures stricter than had been previously anticipated; importance of mask-wearing and ventilation.
- “Mitigation” phase: anticipated need for variant surveillance; redoubled focus on vaccine development, including anticipated need for booster vaccines; consideration of novel (pharmaceutical) treatment approaches; intensified focus on adaptive public health communication.

On 14 December 2021, the Federal Government broadened the scope of pandemic planning by convening a Coronavirus Expert Council (Corona ExpertInnenrat der Bundesregierung). Over the course of the next year, the Coronavirus Expert Council issued several official statements on aspects of pandemic management. The 11th Statement, “Pandemic Preparedness for Autumn/Winter 2022/2023”, issued on 8 June 2022, augments the National Pandemic Plan with recommendations for an anticipated COVID-19 wave in Autumn/Winter 2022/2023. The Statement reconfirms the threefold approach of containment, protection, and mitigation, but further distinguishes between two modes of containment: 1) testing and individual containment, appropriate for periods of “low disease severity and lower death rates”; vs. 2) general containment, i.e., social distancing, appropriate for periods with a combination of high infection rates and/or high disease severity, in which there is a chance that critical health infrastructure could be overwhelmed.

Further modifications in pandemic planning in Germany are likely. On 30 June 2022, the BMG released a comprehensive report, *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies*, which contains several critiques of pandemic planning during 2020-2022. For instance, the *Evaluation* clarifies that the transition from the containment to protection phases should be undertaken as soon as clusters of infections that cannot be traced back to prior known cases emerge, and finds that this transition was not implemented consistently (BMG 2022, pg. 45). The *Evaluation* further critiques the

National Pandemic Plan for insufficient consideration of complex social and cultural factors such as migration status/background: “the only reference to migration aspects was that culturally-determined lack of compliance [with health-protective regulations and recommendations] can be expected. In a sense, this reduces migrants to [an assumption of] non-adherence, without seeing their special needs” (pg. 98). The *Evaluation* recommends that social determinants should be explicitly included in pandemic plans in the future (pg. 99).

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

Crisis management strategies shifted in significant ways in Germany during the pandemic. Vaccines were offered to the six risk groups according to the following schedule: Level 1: 27 December 2020; Level 2: 1 February 2021; Level 3: 1 March 2021; Level 4: 22 March 2021; Level 5: 6 April 2021; Level 6: 7 June 2021. Healthcare workers interviewed in the Mannheim area gave mixed assessments of the German vaccination strategy. On the one hand, several respondents reported that the introduction of vaccines brought a great deal of relief to their patients and communities, as well as their colleagues:

“Here in Mannheim, patients came from Rhineland-Palatinate and elsewhere – on one weekend there were more than 200! We have now done about 4000 vaccinations, it has been such a great joy. The patients were happy and brought us food and drink out of gratitude, that made us feel great satisfaction. Theatres and cinemas were closed anyway, so we just surrounded ourselves with people in a different way” (WP5_SINUS_4)

On the other hand, several respondents criticised the decision to make vaccination mandatory for HCWs and/or the perceived lack of tolerance for questioning or divergent opinions on vaccination:

“That was a lot of pressure and almost compulsion. There was a form from the health office, you were practically forced to get vaccinated” (WP5_SINUS_5)

“There were only pro-arguments [about vaccination], I would have liked it to be balanced, so that you can form your own opinion” (WP5_SINUS_6)

“The fact that there was no discussion tolerated to the left or right, I find that so suspect [...] Discussion must be possible! You can't just wipe away all the questions!” (WP5_SINUS_2)

In tandem with vaccination, the federal government pursued a strategy of gradually more targeted testing, tracing, and containment. During January and February 2021, restrictive social distancing regulations remained in place in most regions during most timeframes. On 30 January 2021, the Corona Quarantine Ordinance (Corona-Quarantäneverordnung) was adopted, providing clear guidelines on quarantine for individuals who test positive. Throughout Q1 and Q2 2021, access to free or low-cost antigen and PCR tests improved nationwide, and the Corona-Warn-App was iteratively improved and promoted. On 8 May 2021, the federal government adopted the COVID-19 Protective Measures Exemption Ordinance (COVID-19-Schutzmaßnahmen-Ausnahmenverordnung), which authorised so-called “2G/2G+/3G” regulations, i.e., exemptions from social distancing rules for the vaccinated (Geimpfte), recovered (Genesene), and tested (Getestete). These regulations were implemented on a state-by-state level. During Q3 2021, this strategy was continued (here, it should be noted that the *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies* found that coordinated interdisciplinary research on the effectiveness of non-pharmaceutical interventions in general was largely absent in Germany [pg. 26-27]). In Q4 2021, in response to a rise in rates of infection, hospitalisation, and death, the BMG introduced compulsory testing in care facilities, increased the pace of booster vaccination, and recommended the states to more consistently implement 2G regulations. The trend of elevated infection rates continued into Q1 2022, leading the BMG to further

increase the pace of booster vaccination, and STIKO to recommend a second mRNA booster vaccine for vulnerable groups and medical care workers.

By March 2022, key indicators began to improve. In April, most remaining general restrictions were lifted, though masks remained mandatory in hospitals and public transportation. In May, 2G rules were lifted on a national level, though states retained the option of implementing them in response to local outbreaks. In June, Germany saw an increase in infection and death rates, however, this did not significantly impact federal policy. In October, another increase in infection rates led the government to tighten some restrictions, such as mask-wearing in public transportation; however, the response was subdued. By Winter 2022, public-facing experts such as virologist Christian Drosten concluded that COVID-19 had evolved into an endemic, signalling the perceived “end” of the pandemic as such in Germany.

The public reaction to the crisis management

The University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring project conducted regular cross-sectional surveys from March 2020 until December 2022, covering several dimensions of public reactions to German COVID-19 policy. A summary of trends on key variables follows (Universität Erfurt et al., 2022):

Trust in health institutions: peaked at an average rating of 5.05 (scale of 1 to 7) in the 24 March 2020 survey wave; gradually declined to a low of 3.68 in the 23 March 2021 survey wave; then rose to hover around a value of 4, rising to 4.20 in May 2022 and dropping back to 3.96 in the final survey wave on 1 December 2022.

Trust in the federal government: achieved its peak, an average rating of 4.54 (scale of 1 to 7), in the survey wave of 7 April 2020, the first in which the question was asked; declined steadily to a low of 3.00 in the 23 March 2021 survey wave; rose and dipped several times between summer 2020 and winter 2021, rising to 3.73 in the 14 December 2021 survey wave and then settling at between 3.20 and 3.60 for the remainder of the pandemic, dropping to 3.28 in the final survey wave on 1 December 2022

Frequency of mask-wearing: rose quickly from an initial frequency of 2.25 (scale of 1 to 5) in the 14 April 2020 survey wave, the first in which the question was asked, to 4.23 in the 12 May 2020 survey wave; remained between 4.20 and 4.66 until the 15 March 2022 survey wave, then dropped to 3.35 in the final survey wave on 1 December 2022.

Agreement with the statement “I find the COVID-19 measures excessive”: peaked at around 3.5 (scale of 1 to 7) during the first lockdown (10 March 2020 survey wave), then again in mid-2021, reaching a high of 3.69 in the 18 May 2021 survey wave; then hovered between around 2.8 and 3.5 for the remainder of the pandemic, reaching 3.39 in the final survey wave on 1 December 2022.

Readiness to protest against COVID-19 measures: remained rather steady at between 1.9 and 2.2 (scale of 1 to 7) from 12 May 2022 until winter 2022, peaking at 2.31 in the final survey wave on 1 December 2022.

Belief in conspiracy theories in general (mean of 5 items: important things are happening in the world that the public is never told about; politicians do not tell us their true motives; government agencies closely monitor citizens; events that at first glance seem unrelated are the result of secret activities;

secret organisations influence political decisions): remained rather steady at between around 3.7 and 4.2 from 17 March 2020 until 2 November 2022.

We can conclude that in general, public acceptance of and compliance with COVID-19 measures was moderate to high throughout the pandemic in Germany. However, agreement with the statement “I find the COVID-19 measures excessive” did tend to rise gradually over the course of the lockdown periods (March to late April 2020; late 2020 to early 2021) and during the period of 2G/2G+/3G regulations, indicating frustration. Interviews conducted with HCWs in the Mannheim region confirm this, with most respondents assessing hard lockdowns as inhumane and counterproductive:

"First of all: no lockdown! [...] People are social beings, there's no way around it, and everyone needs contact" (WP5_SINUS_5)

"No more isolation! That makes you depressed and it's unbearable, that's when you get sick all the more, and that was often the case" (WP5_SINUS_6)

"[The curfew] was very, very moronic and had no effect at all" (WP5_SINUS_7)

Another aspect that HCW interviewees critiqued was a paternalistic approach to pandemic governance – in particular, risk communication – and a perceived lack of tolerance for discourse and diverging opinions:

"Please educate people better instead of driving them crazy with fear. That would be the most important thing" (WP5_SINUS_7)

"I don't like the fact that I'm not allowed to decide this for myself, I don't think that's right. It's not logical either, in big offices with everyone in one room, it's no different from us in terms of contagion" (WP5_SINUS_1)

"What was most shocking was that there was no discussion at all, it was imposed. The pressure was terrible, and that's the only reason I finally did it, I would have liked to wait until everything was clearer" (WP5_SINUS_2)

These critiques mirror the talking points of the so-called “lateral thinker” (*Querdenker*) movement, which from summer 2020 on garnered significant media attention. However, it should be noted that none of the HCWs interviewed identified as members of this movement or reported having taken part in protests. The interviewees’ attitude toward governmental measures can best be described as questioning and critical acceptance, rather than outright rejection. This accords with the COSMO survey finding that at no time did more than around 15% of the population indicate that they were somewhat or very ready to join a protest against governmental measures.

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

The German federal government’s initial definition of “at-risk groups” focused on factors that increased the chance of a severe progression of COVID-19. A 6 March 2020 paper issued by the Robert Koch Institute defines the follow groups as at risk (RKI 2020a):

- Older persons (risk level rising in correlation with age from the threshold of 50-60 years on) item
- Smokers item
- Persons with specific pre-existing medical conditions: Heart conditions; Lung conditions; Chronic liver disease; Diabetes; Cancer; Weakened immune system

Over the course of 2020 and 2021, official definitions of vulnerability expanded to encompass factors that increased the chance of exposure to the SARS-CoV-2 virus, including working in healthcare and

other front-line occupations. The STIKO's January 2021 "Decision of the STIKO on the 1st update of the COVID-19 vaccination recommendation" identified the following risk clusters:

- Persons at risk for a severe progression of COVID-19 (see above)
- Persons with an elevated risk of infection in front-line occupations (HCWs, educators, retail workers, etc.)
- Persons with an elevated risk of infection due to other conditions (residents and personnel in care homes and collective accommodations, persons with cognitive hindrances, low-wage and short-contract workers, itinerant workers, migrant workers, etc.)

In keeping with the protection concept elaborated in the National Pandemic Plan, measures were taken to protect these vulnerable groups, including prioritised access to tests, protective equipment, care facilities, and vaccines, as well as intermittent targeted regulations such as visiting restrictions and mandatory testing and masking in hospitals and care homes. The most consequential example was the prioritisation of vaccine offers, which followed a six-stage schedule as described above, with groups assessed as most vulnerable offered vaccines starting on 27 December 2020 and those assessed as least vulnerable offered vaccines starting on 7 June 2021.

With regard to the risks faced by HCWs in particular, interviewees working in the Mannheim area indicated that they and their colleagues suffered not only from heightened risk of exposure to SARS-CoV-2, but also from overwork, burnout, depression, and various other physical and psychological hardships that added up to create an inhospitable working environment:

"We lost a lot of good staff because many could no longer stand the conditions in the maternity wards" (WP5_SINUS_1)

"The people who worked there were all over the place to the point of burnout, to the point of depression, they were all so drained that it's no wonder that the number of nurses is decreasing, all throughout the hierarchy, because the conditions are totally inhumane" (WP5_SINUS_2)

"We ourselves were under difficult conditions, you got less air with the mask, I am asthmatic myself, it was very hard [... and] the daily testing was extremely annoying" (WP5_SINUS_6)

Many (particularly female) interviewees furthermore criticised the well-known disparity between the expectations placed on them and their level of remuneration and recognition:

"If I were to go by what we earn, I'd rather work in other fields. It's out of proportion to the work we do" (WP5_SINUS_3)

"I don't want to badmouth the IT professionals and the bankers or managers here, but it has been shown during the pandemic how little nurses earn, and that there are far too few because of that. They're all doing their best, but you can't treat people like that! They need a real income" (WP5_SINUS_4)

"Completely undervalued! That stayed quite the same despite all the talk. I was angry about it, because in reality nobody cared at all [...] We nursing professionals got a few financial supplements as a thank-you, but that was it. Morally, we are still [treated as] the stupid ones. We live in Germany, where more than half of the people are old, and without us nothing works, but it is shameful how we are seen. A few words of respect doesn't help. It's hard work in every way, but that doesn't come across publicly" (WP5_SINUS_5)

It should be noted here that while German public health measures targeted the general population, with special measures taken to support the medically vulnerable groups, the government

implemented a wide range of other measures targeting economic and psychosocial vulnerabilities (see D4.7). However, based on the testimony of interviewees, the economic and psychosocial support offered to HCWs was inadequate.

The *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies* offers an implicit (sometimes explicit) critique of the lack of attention given by policymakers to certain other vulnerable groups. For instance, as mentioned above in the section on pandemic planning, the Evaluation identifies migrant and migration-background populations as potentially impacted by information deficits and cultural barriers to adherence to regulations and recommendations (pg. 98). One HCW interviewee in the Mannheim area adds that social distancing, and particularly quarantine, could be retraumatising for vulnerable migrants such as female and minor refugees:

"The Corona crisis has made their situation even worse; the level of mindfulness needed to prevent re-traumatization could often not be guaranteed at all [...] It was a nightmare when such people were locked in quarantine for two weeks. It was [especially] terrible for the women, and terrible for us to witness this. Traumatised women who had fled alone, women with small children, locked in a room, without toys, without TV, without anything. The loneliness. The stress. What a nightmare!" (WP5_SINUS_2)

The *Evaluation* also acknowledges that pandemic response measures sometimes aggravated certain vulnerabilities and/or resulted in the emergence of new vulnerabilities. It cites several studies in Germany and other countries on the psychosocial impact of the pandemic and social distancing measures, especially on women and younger people, and recommends that in the future, digital therapeutic resources should be offered and a minimum level of social contact must be guaranteed, even if this means allowing some regulatory flexibility. The *Evaluation* particularly emphasises the psychosocial and developmental impacts of school closures on children and youth, stressing that policymakers must take these impacts seriously, especially given the current lack of decisive evidence on the effectiveness of school closures in hindering the spread of the disease. HCWs interviewed in the Mannheim area confirmed the severity of psychosocial impacts on children and young people:

"You saw what happened in many families, the violence often escalated, there was no escape [...] and to tell children that they might be responsible for the death of their grandma, that's outrageous and leaves bad damage" (WP5_SINUS_2)

"Their needs have definitely not been considered! [...] what is a child supposed to understand about this? Because of Corona your mommy left, because of Corona your grandma died, because of Corona you can't do anything anymore. [...] Like an evil witch who is everywhere!" (WP5_SINUS_3)

"There was severe damage because weak children in social hotspots could not be picked up by the parents and were stuck in a narrow living space. When 3-4 children in a confined space have to be suddenly taken care of by a single mother at home, it is a severe disadvantage" (WP5_SINUS_4)

Several interviewees also mentioned the elderly – especially those suffering from some degree of dementia – as a group especially at risk of detrimental psychological impacts, which could also lead to physical consequences:

"Many have perished from loneliness or galloping dementia. [...] I know people in old people's homes who met secretly in the basement so they wouldn't be so alone. They hid it from the staff because they would have gotten sanctions, they organised a Christmas tree, also secretly" (WP5_SINUS_3)

"The measures intervened very heavily in the psychological situation of the people. Here, much more visitation after testing would have been possible, we now know that the isolation caused severe damage and that this should be avoided at all costs" (WP5_SINUS_4)

"Not only because of age, but because they got so blatantly scared. My grandma wouldn't even talk to me on the phone anymore because she was afraid of getting infected through the phone. That's tragic, isn't it?" (WP5_SINUS_5)

"It is very difficult for many elderly residents, especially those with dementia, when they cannot recognize faces [through the mask]. It makes them afraid and uncomfortable and less confident [...] Especially the war generation, the older ones, they've already experienced everything, they didn't feel like they could take all that, all those measures. I often heard the harsh sentence: this is not how I imagined my last years!" (WP5_SINUS_6)

With regard to women, the *Evaluation* confirms the importance of ensuring protection against domestic violence, notes that in some cases, the pandemic appears to have led to the "re-traditionalisation" of gender norms in heterosexual partnerships, and indicates that some economic aid instruments primarily benefited male workers. One interviewee in the Mannheim area spontaneously echoed this finding:

"Women had to do the main part everywhere, after all. An even split of the work for men and women is not a given – women bear the main burden in the household and taking care of the children, and men tend to take refuge in work more" (WP5_SINUS_4)

"Women had to do the main part everywhere after all, half the work for men and women is not a given, women bear the main burden in the household and taking care of the children and men tend to take refuge in work more." (WP5_SINUS_4)

Other Mannheim area interviewees working in obstetrics specifically mentioned negative impacts on pregnant women:

"I know women who have had to travel to 6 clinics until someone took them in for birth, and that's in severe labour. It's dramatic" (WP5_SINUS_1)

"[The mask requirement] is a crime in childbirth, where providing oxygen to the mother and the newborn is essential [...] I have to say that I was very disappointed in my guild there. To leave this highly vulnerable group alone like that, it was a shock" (WP5_SINUS_2)

"Then there was also the mask requirement, and a woman in labour usually can't handle that at all. One woman I cared for fainted twice during childbirth and was only allowed to take off the mask until she regained consciousness. This woman needed professional psychological care for a long time afterwards" (WP5_SINUS_3)

Additional vulnerable groups mentioned by Mannheim area HCWs as having suffered extraordinary risks and deleterious impacts during the pandemic were sex workers, addicts, and the mentally ill:

"For prostitutes, it [vaccination] is extraordinarily difficult because most of them have no identity papers and no health care. I vaccinated two who had IDs. It's really unfortunate that it was so difficult. These women are the least protected – it's bad" (WP5_SINUS_4)

"When the brothels were closed, the women stood on the street or went back to Bulgaria or Romania" (WP5_SINUS_4)

"You can't explain to an addict that they can't go out if they want to. They are free people, it's not a psychiatric ward, of course they buy alcohol outside" (WP5_SINUS_1)

"All the people with anxiety disorders and other pre-existing mental health conditions, there was a huge increase in panic attacks and depression." (WP5_SINUS_7)

"One of our [care home] residents was slightly mentally disturbed, he always wanted to get out to calm down. He freaked out when he wasn't allowed to. That's when we got a court order where we had to force him back in and give him a sedative and restrain him in bed. That was one of the worst moments I've ever experienced in care. I was totally shocked, it was not humane" (WP5_SINUS_5)

Finally, several HCWs interviewed in the Mannheim area asserted that the negative psychosocial impacts of lockdowns, fear-based risk communication, and other extreme measures could have a cascading negative impact on physical health:

"Don't keep people locked up at home, it's not good for anyone and tends to make people sick. As humans, we need a bit of activity and to be able to go outside. So I'd rather wear a mask outside everywhere than stay inside" (WP5_SINUS_1)

"We all function in such a way that fear makes us sick more easily and progressions often more severely than confidence" (WP5_SINUS_2)

By extension, the social determinants of health model holds that economic and social vulnerabilities also often aggravate health vulnerability. This tendency is also explored from a socio-ecological systems perspective in COVINFORM deliverable D6.4. In the opinion of the author, policy documents and evaluations produced by the German government and public health authorities to date do not give adequate attention to this perspective, instead reinforcing a flawed distinction between individuals and population groups at risk of negative health outcomes and those affected by non-health vulnerabilities. It is notable that HCWs working in the field intuitively reached a similar conclusion.

3.4 Greece

Public health system and main actors

In Greece and despite the economic challenges of the last decade, the health system was modernised, and became more sustainable and efficient with the implementation of a comprehensive health insurance covering the needs of all Greek residents (OECD, 2019). Greek healthcare is a system which is centralised, mixed and regulated, incorporating elements by both the public and private sector. The prime regulating entities are the social health insurance system (SHI) (private sector) and the national health service (ESY) (public sector) (Economou, Kaitelidou, Karanikolos, & Maresso, 2017). The public healthcare system provides both primary and secondary healthcare (Joint Report on healthcare and Long-Term Care Systems & Fiscal Sustainability, 2019), supported by the National Organization for the Provision of Health Services (EOPYY) which provides healthcare to ESY patients. The main leadership figure supervising the public health system is the Minister of Health and the main regulating authority is the Ministry of Health (Ministry of Health, n.d.). In relation to the private sector, there are healthcare facilities with a for profit modus operandi, while several facilities, operations are subcontracted by the public sector (Economou, Kaitelidou, Karanikolos, & Maresso, 2017). Overall, the Greek healthcare system capacity includes: 125 hospitals, 201 health centres, 1,487 regional health centres (rural areas) and 127 primary care units in urban areas.

Health crisis preparedness plans

The structure of the healthcare system did not radically change in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The National Public Health Organization (EODY), a public healthcare organisation supervised by the Ministry of Health which also has a central role in the healthcare system, closely monitored the COVID-19 pandemic and established frequent and sustainable communication with both the WHO and the

European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) (National Public Health Organization, 2021). Part of the response included the tracking of cases and contacts, while publishing daily situational reports of infection rates as well as ensured the provision of free of charge rapid tests for citizens and operated a 24/7 phone line providing information about COVID-19 to all interested parties. The Ministry of Health since the beginning of the pandemic had the primary role of communicating all regulations and rules about COVID-19, nevertheless, within the decision making process, the Prime Minister, deputy ministers, ministers, committee of infectious disease experts, the Ministry of Citizen Protection and the General Secretariat for Civil Protection also had a substantial role in the Greek response.

Crisis management implementation

COVID-19 emerged in Greece on 26 February 2020. During February and April 2,235 confirmed cases were reported in Greece, while 56% were men while 25.5% of the overall number were travellers from Italy and Israel (Demertzis, Tsiotas, & Magafas, 2020). The swift government response towards the pandemic was crucial in virus containment efforts (Gountas, Hillas, Souliotis, 2020), which was based on the pandemic response and preparedness action plan, as a foundation for the overall responses, utilising pre-existing pandemic planning policies which were laid out for cases of influenza (Ministry of Health, 2020). A wide range of protection and prevention responses and policies were launched by the Government such as social distancing, as well as a dedicated crisis management team was established (iEfimerida, 2020). The Greek government proceeded with a series of actions to address workforce shortages and procured equipment, hospital beds while hiring healthcare workers (Kousi, Mitsi, Simos, 2021), (Farsalinos, et al. 2021)., particularly in metropolitan areas, (Farsalinos, et al. 2021), whereas provided further targeted funding to enhance the healthcare system in order to establish private-public partnerships (Ministry of Health, National Public Health Action Plan 2021-2025, p. 25), (Williams, et al. 2020), (Fouda, Mahmoudi, Moy, Paolucci, 2020). In January Greece established 13 COVID-19 dedicated hospitals equipped with negative chambers (Liakos, 2020), while in February all high human density events as well as school trips abroad were cancelled (News247, 2020). In early March, optional directives on social distancing, prevention measures and personal hygiene guidelines were announced, schools and high human density facilities (shopping centres, hotels, retail shops, bars and restaurants etc) closed on a nationwide level, while a temporary suspension of flights from high risk countries such as Italy was implemented (Gazzetta, 2020). Moreover, a suspension of all religious activities and local quarantines in two villages in Western Macedonia (Kozani) were also implemented (Kathimerini, 2020). In addition, during late March, financial measures to support the economy and protect businesses and employees were announced as well as the first national lockdown on March 23, 2020 was implemented until May 4, according to which movement restrictions were at place with the exception of visiting doctors, going outside for exercise or walking pets, going to work, procuring food and medicine. These exceptions were verified via identification papers and written documents stating the time, date and reason of movement via sending a text message to the number 13033. As of mid-late May, restrictions eased and Greek residents could resume their daily activities until the rise of infections in August (News GTP, n.d.), (EODY, 2020).

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

The structure of the Greek healthcare response towards COVID-19 did not radically change during the implementation of lockdowns, particularly at the first lockdowns until the vaccination and the emergence of the Omicron variant. The Ministry of Health, the Prime Minister, the Minister of Health, the committee of infectious disease and the General Secretariat for Civil Protection continued to have

a central role in the decision making process. During mid-2021, the Greek Prime Minister conducted a reshuffling of the cabinet, which led to the change of the Minister of Health, who however continued to abide by the same modus operandi that the Greek response had adopted towards the COVID-19 pandemic (Tornos news, 2021). The collaboration between the Ministry of Health, the National Public Health Organization (NPHO), the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP), the Public Health Emergency Committee for Infectious Diseases and the National Committee for Public Health continued to have a crucial role throughout all pandemic phases (Ministry of Health, 2021). Overall, the Greek response also relied on information sharing between Greek authorities, ECDC and WHO (Economou, Kaitelidou, Konstantakopoulou, Vildiridi, 2021) allowing also the creation of a national COVID-19 registry which provided support to decision makers in the formulation of evidence-based policies and actions (National Public Health Action Plan 2021-2025, p. 26). During the first two lockdowns and prior to the vaccine rollout, a fluctuation between the strictness of measures can be observed, due to the fact that the Greek economy heavily relies on the industry of tourism and hospitality, therefore this consideration influenced restrictions particularly during the summer period. At the rollout of the vaccine, a gradual disengagement from the strict, mandatory measures can be observed, due to the fact that the scientific community would acquire in-depth knowledge about COVID-19 and how it was transmitted as well as the vaccines would form another layer of defence, particularly protecting citizens with health vulnerabilities, together with social distancing and personal health hygiene measures (such as wearing a mask) which became optional.

The Greek crisis response during the pandemic did not radically change throughout the duration of the pandemic. The structure of the response, measures and policies as well as leading figures of the response remained in most cases similar, with the exception of the changes in command, specifically the Minister of Health and Deputy Minister for Civil Protection in 2021 (Tornos news, 2021).

Upon the emergence of variants from South Africa such as the SARS-CoV-2, a steady increase of infections, in spite of lockdown measures, was observed during the second lockdown (Ta Nea, 2021). The Greek response in general can be characterised by the centralised nature of the decision making process, a rapid, organised, proactive manner (Spyros A. Papiris et al, 2020). of combating COVID-19 with the implementation of movement restriction measures, preventative measures as well as a significant reinforcement of medical personnel and equipment on a nationwide scale (Hellenic Government, 2020), (Onmed, 2020). Moreover, to support the Greek response, the Hellenic Government would also introduce measures which would entail the utilisation of private sector facilities and personnel to house COVID-19 patients as well as engage in a constant communication campaign to provide information about COVID-19 on a frequent (daily) basis in relation to measures, policies and regulations (National Public Health Organization, 2020), (Huffington Post, 2020).

The crisis response in practice

Greek healthcare experts that were interviewed suggest that there was an immediate adaptation to the new status quo which included the provision and utilisation of specialised protection equipment such as TYVEK and masks. However, they pointed out that working excessive hours and having minimum contact with the family was something exhausting. Regarding the lessons learned, the overall experience revealed the need for new walls to be built, equipped the ICU with necessary equipment which provides oxygen (invasive ventilation), monitors, and aspiration machines. Another insight by experts was that working in a small town hospital was harder in comparison to working in a big city hospital, due to the lack of staff there, nevertheless assesses that the overall management and work has been successful particularly due to the personal sacrifices of each employee. Experts also

suggested that they did not have the opportunity to talk about the impact of COVID-19 on their mental health at work with their colleagues or superior staff.

The public reaction to the crisis management

According to nationwide surveys, the general public in Greece had a high acceptance rate and awareness of the public responses, while retain a high level of trust particularly during the first pandemic phases, due to widespread fear of the COVID-19 impact and also due to the successful management of the pandemic by the Greek government (Mouchtouri, et al. 2021), (Kanellopoulou, et al. 2021), (Gavana, et al. 2022). This level of trust however gradually declined over time, particularly due to the quick pace of information distribution about COVID-19 and swift changes in guidelines and measures from the scientific community, whereas propaganda, falsified information can also be observed by political figures who urged the public to demonstrate as well as anti-vaccine popular individuals (TheToc, n.d.), (Pietromarchi, 2020), (Kanellopoulou, et al. 2021). The prolonged lockdowns are estimated to have caused emotional and economic exhaustion, frustration and fatigue which has led to the public negatively reacting towards implemented measures and policies (Kokkinidis, 2020). These cases of non-abidance to the measures were mostly observed in the forms of conducting parties during COVID-19 (In, 2021) and demonstrations (Kitsantonis, 2021), (CNN, 2021). An estimated number of 632 demonstrations have taken place as of February 2021 until late March 2021 (Protothema, 2021).

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

In Greece power hierarchies and systemic inequalities are observed which could potentially have created various types of vulnerabilities which in turn contributed to the increase the infection rates within society during the COVID-19 pandemic. Defined by the Hyogo protocol, there are three main types of vulnerabilities that were identified, which can be interrelated and applied to a wide range of the Greek population. The first type was the *health*-related vulnerability which can be interpreted as groups of people or individuals that have a higher risk rate of falling seriously ill or dying because of being exposed to COVID-19. These individuals are likely people that may have chronic illnesses and syndromes that highly contribute to their mental and physical health and may severely negatively influence their life. The second type were the *social*-related vulnerability citizens face, as they are unable to work due to covid-19 related measures (lockdown, mandatory closure of businesses), is also interrelated with the high cost of cancer treatments and medicines, a shortage of cancer drugs, a significant drop in diagnoses. The third type to be observed is the *communication*-related vulnerability, due to the overexposure to frequent COVID-19 related news, that resulted in an increased rate of depression. Despite the significantly low but likely steadily increasing rate of non-abiding citizens, a key finding referred to an inability of the participants that developed depression to adhere to the restrictive and containment rules (isolation) of the COVID-19 lockdown (Petros Skapinakis et al, 2020).

Regarding vulnerable groups, the Greek Government's enlisted a holistic approach which ensured that all citizens that were considered to be affected by health/physical, social (and cultural), communication vulnerabilities would be accommodated in the best way possible, in spite of the apparent healthcare system weaknesses due to the decade-long austerity (iefimerida, 2020). In accordance with the national plan for vaccination against COVID-19, the Ministry of Health under the then Minister Vasilis Kikilias, had prioritised the vaccination of healthcare and medical personnel, particularly those that are combating COVID-19 in specialised Emergency Healthcare Facilities, School teachers (elementary, primary, high school), elderly citizens based on their age. Also 65 mobile vaccination units were utilised for citizens that may not be able to commute, such as elderly, inmates and other citizens facing chronic

diseases (National Public Health Organization, 2020). Regarding refugees and migrants, they were vaccinated by medical experts on site in the 48 temporary accommodation facilities. Despite the economic hardship, shouldering the migrant crisis and shortages in medical equipment, facilities, vaccines and sporadic cases of non-adherence to the pandemic movement restriction measures, Greece has managed to handle the pandemic, without stigmatising any specific group of people that fall into a vulnerability group category (Carassava, 2021). Greece's holistic approach to the pandemic and early prevention measures have contributed to saving lives.

The Greek responses towards vulnerable individuals are not observed to have created new vulnerabilities despite the communication related vulnerability, according to which residents have increasingly demonstrated acts of non-adherence to COVID-19 measures due to the immense psychological impact the daily inflow of negative information (infection rate and COVID-19 related deaths) had on their psychological state, in combination with the prolonged lockdowns and social isolation. Nevertheless, an EU wide rise in domestic violence can be observed. Similarly, it is an undeniable fact that forms of domestic violence and abuse have significantly been increased in Greece as the pandemic outbreak and throughout the pandemic, while some sources suggest the rates have quadrupled (Chatzisyneonidis and Kioskli, 2023), (Chioni-Chotouman, 2020), (Kitsantoni, 2022), (Spiliopoulou and Anagnostopoulou, 2023).

3.5 Italy

Public health system and main actors

As mentioned in D5.1, Italy has a “*Servizio Sanitario Nazionale*” (SSN) [National Health Plan, NHS], which provides universal coverage largely free of charge according to the 32° article of the Italian Constitution. The SSN is decentralised and is based on three levels: State, region and local boards. The State legislates on the principles and defines the budgets; the regions adapt them to local contexts and manage healthcare delivery through local boards. At a state level, the Ministry of Health defines the health system's main goals, determines the core performance standards and guidelines, establishes work contracts, and allocates national funds to the regions according to law 23 December 1978 n°833. The Ministry of Health is organised in three independent departments: Department of Public Health and Innovation, Department of Planning and Organization of the SSN and Department of Veterinary Care, Food Safety and Collegial Organs for Health Protection (Ferre et al., 2014). The Ministry of Health is supported by several specialised government agencies, such as The National Institute of Health (ISS), The National Agency for Regional Health Services (AGENAS), National Center for Disease Prevention and Control (CCM), National Institute for Scientific Research (IRCS) and National Authority for Pharmaceutical Regulation (AIFA). The most important technical and consultative agency to the Ministry of Health is the National Health Council (CSS). It consists of 50 members and a president, and it brings together representatives of the national government agencies listed above as well as scientists, physicians and other recognized experts.

The regions are responsible for the functioning of the health services within their areas of jurisdiction and organising and delivering healthcare (Ferre et al., 2014). At a local level, geographically based Aziende Sanitarie Locali (ASL) [Local Health Authorities], working closely under the regions' jurisdiction, deliver primary care, secondary and specialist care, directly or through public hospitals accredited private providers according to law 23 December 1978 n° 833. Each ASL territory is further divided into

Districts, the institutional level that directly controls the provision of public health and primary care services to approximately 60 000 inhabitants (Ferre et al., 2014). Preventive medicine and public health services are delivered by the Department of Prevention while a network of GPs provides family medicine services according to law 8 November 2020 n°189. GPs work for the regional health system and coordinate with the activities of the Districts.

Health crisis preparedness plans

As mentioned in D4.7 and D5.5, since the end of 2003, when the outbreaks of avian influenza by virus has become endemic in birds and the virus has caused infections in humans as well, the risk of an influenza pandemic has been more concrete and persistent. For this reason, the WHO recommended all countries to develop a Pandemic Plan and to constantly update it following agreed lines. The “Piano nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale” [National influenza pandemic preparedness and response plan, 2006] was drawn up according to the 2005 WHO guidelines, updated and it replaced the previous Italian Multiphase Plan for and Influenza Pandemic, published in 2002.

Crisis management implementation

With the Ministerial Circular “New Coronavirus Pneumonia (2019-nCov) China” of 22 January 2020 were officially declared the first cases COVID-19 in Italy. On February 2020, the “Piano Nazionale in risposta a un’eventuale emergenza pandemica da COVID-19” [National Health Plan in response to a possible COVID-19 pandemic emergency] established epidemiological surveillance of COVID-19 cases in Italy, on the basis of the case definitions prepared by the WHO and the technical specifications provided by the ECDC from UE/EEA countries and the UK.

On the 31st of January 2020, Italy declared the State of Emergency for six months (later prolonged with decree-law 7 October 2020 n°125 and decree-law 14 January 2021 n°2). From January 2020 on a total of 1034 acts (the complete list is available here:

<https://www.openpolis.it/coronavirus-lelenco-completo-degli-atti/>) have been issued to counter the spread of coronavirus in Italy, for an average of more than 27 per month. The first months of 2020 were the most intense from the point of view of regulatory production: in February 67 Covid acts were published, in March 103, in April 65. In 2022, the total number of published acts was 176. In 2023, 12 acts were issued (Openpolis, 2021).

As mentioned in D4.1, to deal with the epidemic, the Government chaired by Giuseppe Conte adopted a shorter administrative, not legislative, procedure: the issuance of Decrees of the President of the Council of Ministers (D.p.c.m.). The Civil Protection Department was asked to lead a command-and-control governance structure to coordinate interventions for the State of Emergency's duration supervised by the Prime Minister's Office. A Scientific Technical Committee (CTS) was established to consult, support and coordinate the activities for overcoming the epidemiological emergency due to the spread of Coronavirus.

The Government appointed a regional coordinator in each of the 20 Italian regions to implement the decisions and the decree of both the Civil Protection Department and the Ministry of Health. Even if the Italian health system is decentralised and regions have administrative autonomy, the institutive law of the SSN determines that the Government can obtain full decisional powers during an epidemic or a pandemic.

The circular of 29 February 2020 n°2619 of the Ministry of Health dictated the Guidelines for assistance for critically ill patients affected by Covid-19, underlining the urgency for the Regions to prepare an emergency plan to guarantee suitable levels of treatment through an adequate number of intensive care beds, identifying for this purpose one or more structures to be dedicated to the exclusive management of patients affected by Covid-19, and respecting some conditions expressly provided for.

As mentioned in D5.1, the Italian government adopted the triple Ts strategy: testing, tracing and treatment in order to prevent the spread of the virus. The lockdowns were accompanied by the imposition of certain obligations that were constant over time, such as the use of surgical mask outside one's home; the spacing of two metres between people wherever they pass or stop; limits to the presence of more people at a time, based on the relationship between capacity and the obligation to spacing at least two metres, in a public place, or of one person at a time or only by appointment.

The Ministry of Health and the CTS identified specific guidelines and standards that the regions were expected to respect. However, there have been differences in the way regions implemented the Ministry of Health and CTS recommendations (Pecoraro, Luzi & Clemente, 2021; Meschi et al., 2020; Mugnai & Bilato, 2020; Romagnani et al., 2020). These differences were due to the incidence of the epidemic cluster, organisation of the integrated home assistance and primary care network, and the number of beds in ICU and resources (Pecoraro, Luzi & Clemente, 2021; Berardi et al., 2020). In the most affected regions, the Government issued the immediate strengthening of the intensive care hospital wards (Pecoraro, Luzi & Clemente, 2020).

Through the National Emergency Fund, the so called Cure Italy and Liquidity decrees promoted the purchase of devices and equipment specifically aiming at treating Covid-19 patients, such as assisted ventilation systems in intensive care units, and ordered the requisition of health facilities and movable and immovable properties, including hotels.

The circular of the Ministry of Health of 1st March 2020 required that, in the shortest possible time, an interregional cooperation model coordinated at national level had to be activated, with the involvement of public and private accredited structures. The plan envisaged, at the regional level, an increase of 50 per cent in intensive care beds and 100 per cent in pulmonology, with a redistribution of staff (doctors and nurses), to be concentrated in the intensive and sub-intensive care wards, thanks to a rapid and qualifying training course for respiratory support.

To address the phase of coexistence with the virus, the so-called Relaunch Decree (May 2020), provided for structural strengthening of the hospital network through the adoption of specific reorganisation plans. The law-decree Relaunch envisaged a structural allocation on the national territory of at least 3500 intensive care beds, going from 5179 beds pre-emergency to 8679 with an increase of 70%; restructuring of emergency rooms, with separation of care paths and identification of distinct areas of stays for patients suspected of COVID-19 or potentially contagious, awaiting diagnosis; implementation of means of transport dedicated to secondary transfers for Covid-19 patients.

The epidemic hit the ASLs hard. Both the GPs and the long-term care facilities, private and public, were unprepared (Castelli et al., 2021; Kurotschka et al., 2021; Modenese e Gobba, 2020; Lombardo et al., 2020; de Girolamo et al., 2020). GPs were required to help prevent and control activities and manage at-home patients with suspected and confirmed Covid-19 infections, working with the hospital and the ASL public health services network (Torri et al., 2020).

During the first wave of Covid-19, GPs experienced a shortage of disposable of individual protection, and the procedures and training often came late (Martin-Delgado et al., 2020). Instead, during the second wave, GPs were entrusted to the diagnosis of Covid-19.

From 10 March 2020, the regions established, at an existing continuity of care facility, a Special Continuity of Care Unit (USCA) for every 50,000 inhabitants for the home management of patients affected by COVID-19 that do not require hospitalisation.

The long-term care facilities paid the highest price during the first wave of Covid-19 epidemic in Italy (Lombardo et al., 2020). This was due to a shortage of both devices and healthcare providers (Armocida, Formenti, Ussai, Palestra & Missoni, 2020). On the 24th March of 2020, the Ministry of Health updated guidelines for prevention and control in these institutions.

The Government determined the strengthening and reorganisation of the primary care network and hospital network by increasing the number of hours of the agreed outpatient specialist care and emergency room. Until the end of the emergency period, the regions committed to establishing special continuity of care units for the home management of patients affected by mild Covid-19.

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

As mentioned in D5.1.3, at the beginning of the second wave of pandemic (October 2020) the Ministry of Health was committed to publishing, on its institutional website, on a weekly basis, the results of the monitoring of the health risk connected to the evolution of the epidemiological situation relating to the spread of the Covid-19 virus that provided the regional impact of the pandemic, thus classifying each region according to the epidemiological risk. Subsequently, the DPCM of the 14th of January 2021 has partially modified the classification criteria of the risk areas, establishing specific measures according to the weekly incidence of contagion cases per 100,000 inhabitants. These criteria were definitively regulated in February 2021, when the vaccine campaign was already moving forward the healthcare personnel to those most at risk. The criteria supplemented the legislative discipline of the region's classification criteria in relation to the progress of vaccination campaigns and the related levels of epidemiological risk.

Beyond the “Piano Nazionale in risposta a un’eventuale emergenza pandemica da COVID-19” [National Health Plan in response to a possible COVID-19 pandemic emergency] established in 2020, other two documents have been upset and have replaced the previous influenza pandemic plans: “Prevenzione e risposta a COVID-19: evoluzione della strategia e pianificazione nella fase di transizione per il periodo autunno-invernale” [Prevention and response to COVID-19: evolving strategy and planning in the transition phase for the autumn-winter period] and “Piano strategico-operativo nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale (PanFlu) 2021-2023” [National Strategic-Operational Plan for Pandemic Influenza Preparedness and Response (PanFlu) 2021-2023]. The first one refers to the second pandemic phase, while the last is valid from the end of the state of emergency.

As mentioned in D5.5, the PanFlu (2021) points out specific actions for each of the four pandemic phases determined by the WHO (2018): 1. In the interpandemic phase, planning activities in the event of an influenza pandemic; 2. In the alert phase, defining roles and responsibilities of different actors at the national and regional levels for the implementation of preparedness measures; 3. In the pandemic phase, providing tools for harmonised regional planning to define roles and responsibilities of the different actors involved and for the implementation of preparedness measures; 4. In the transition

phase, developing a cycle of training, monitoring and continuous updating of the plan to facilitate its implementation and monitor the efficiency of the interventions undertaken. For each of these four phases, the PanFlu (2021) establishes a list of specific actions to be taken in the different areas: governance; epidemiological and virological surveillance; infection prevention and control; procurement of PPE, medicines, and supplies of essential medications; education and training. The PanFlu (2021) includes strategies to assess pandemic mitigation and manage the current phase.

In Italy, the two main sources of information about the COVID-19 pandemic are the Civil Protection Department (Protezione Civile) and the Italian National Institute of Health (Istituto Superiore di Sanità). They provide different data since the Civil Protection Department collects information on the total number of positive tests, deaths, hospitalizations, and intensive care admissions in all the Italian provinces while Italian National Institute of Health requests Regions to provide individual-level details as demographic data, clinical conditions, and comorbidities. Civil Protection Department aggregated data are faster and easier while Italian National Institute of Health data allow more detailed and accurate analysis. Data monitoring should lead decisionmakers to concrete decisions: in this frame, much importance is given to the communication strategy. The communication of containment or re-opening measures was extremely heterogeneous across the country due to the high variability of the epidemiological curve and the different political views and this led to conflicting ideas over the time [Bosa et al, 2021].

The crisis response in practice

The respondents identified both drawbacks and best practices:

RSAs (residential care facilities for the elderly) resulted in the main drawback of the management of the pandemic (especially in the first phase). In fact, the issue of RSAs gives an idea of how unprepared these facilities were: “some collapsed, while others were able to adapt but, in general, we had a concrete perception of the poor quality of care in these facilities”. (Public Health_01 Italy). The same was highlighted by another expert who stressed that “the residential care facilities were often the site of Covid-19 outbreaks”. The Stakeholder hinted that the primary care network needs to be remodelled in Italy. (Public Health_02 Italy).

The experts reported some lessons learned from the organisational point of view for the health system. As we explained earlier in this report and in D5.1, the SSN in Italy is organised with a division of responsibilities between state and regions. According to one of the experts, functional cooperation between different hospital facilities is a fundamental aspect to be promoted and fostered in the future: “if the network had not been created it (i.e., the management of the pandemic) would have been a disaster” (Public Health_01 Italy). Another expert stressed the important role played by the region during different stages of the pandemic. “[...] there is always this double vision. Those who say “we need to centralise” but to centralise, the centre must be very strong, and no one can deal with this [...]. We have strengthened ourselves (The Ministry of Health), for example...But Italy is a country that is difficult to govern centrally. At the same time, however, there are regions that make leaps forward and so the centre has to chase the regions. It happens a bit like that, that's the mechanism. But the regions have had a strong role from an organisational point of view, when the commissioner (The extraordinary commissioner taking care of vaccination) says “let's do the hubs” rather than as it was in the first phase. But then the regions are the ones that apply.” (Public Health_2 Italy)

Among future priorities, the experts identified issues related to data collection and monitoring. According to one of the “Despite Italy collecting both aggregated and individual data on Covid-19, we still lack common methods to collect and compare data at the European level. The future of Covid-19 data monitoring appears to focus on the symptomatic cases and the hospitalisation rates rather than asymptomatic and RT index” (Public Health_2 Italy).

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

As mentioned in D5.5, the PNEP (2002) identified as vulnerable in an influenza pandemic people aged over 65 years old, people with chronic diseases or diabetes or HIV positives, pregnant women, and children above 14 years old. Instead, the NIPPRP (2006) stratified the population in six categories and determined an order of priority for their safeguard. The six categories, in order of priority, are: 1) healthcare providers; 2) security and emergency services personnel; 3) essential workers; 4) people at high risk of severe or fatal complications due to influenza; 5) children; 6) healthy adults. The PanFlu (2021) defined as vulnerable children, pregnant women, the elderly, people with chronic or oncologic diseases and people with disabilities. Moreover, the PanFlu (2021) stated that there are several categories of people that can be considered fragile and listed non-exhaustively and without implying an order of priority the sequent categories: the elderly, particularly those who are housed in nursing homes or long-term residences; pregnant women; people with rare diseases; people with psychiatric illnesses; people with severe comorbidities or immunodeficiencies; people with disabilities; the homeless or those living in particularly fragile social conditions; people in detention; migrants and asylum seekers.

As mentioned in D5.1.8, although the pandemic repercussions on physical and mental health spared no segment of the population, the pandemic hit the older population. In Italy, the mean age of patients dying for COVID-19 infection was 81 years (ISS, 2021). The pandemic worsened the inequalities, isolation, loneliness and ageism discrimination. Those who were already isolated and excluded before the pandemic remained on the margins; many others became isolated and felt lonely because of the containment measures adopted. Fear and sense of loneliness were fuelled by the excessive number of deaths recorded in nursing homes. The Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) led a survey on mortality in nursing home which reported an average of 9.1% of all nursing homes’ residents died in Italy, with a peak of 14% in Lombardy, between 1st February and 14th April, of which about 37.4% officially due to COVID-19 (Istituto Superiore di Sanità, 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic imposed a significant burden on healthcare workers (HCWs). HCWs worked in close contact with Covid-19 positive patients and were exposed to a higher risk of infections than the general population (Boffetta et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2020).

Hospital overcrowding and PPE shortage were the main risk factors for Covid-19 infection among HCWs during the first wave (Anelli et al., 2020). Most of the infections of HCWs happened in hospitals (94,2%) (National Institute for Insurance against Accidents at Work, 2021) and the increase in the number of contagious diseases did not spare an increase in deaths. So, HCWs were vulnerable to many adverse mental health consequences, such as depression, anxiety and insomnia (Pappa et al., 2020). Several surveys showed HCWs with pre-existing psychological problems had an increased risk of psychopathological consequences (Lasalvia et al., 2021); burn-out was very frequent among Italian nurses and intensive care units; and, HCWs suffered from somatization, depression and anxiety and perceived the need for psychological support. Lastly, HCWs who lost a family member reported higher distress levels than those who did not (Conti et al., 2020).

However, if in the first wave of the Covid-19 pandemic, Italian HCWs were often compared by newspapers to heroes or soldiers at the front (Quotidiana Sanità, 2020) and Italians were grateful and moved by the efforts of the HCWs (Il Messaggero, 2020; La Stampa, 2020), during the second wave, the public perception shifted. HCWs were often blamed for any inefficiencies in delivering healthcare services and sometimes even physically or verbally attacked (Internazionale, 2020; Nurse24, 2020). In September 2020, the Government approved a law to prevent violence against HCWs.

Literature has shown that the distribution of COVID-19-related and all-cause mortality in migrants and natives was not substantially different from those who were well-integrated and had access to healthcare resources and services. While, the marginalised migrants such as refugees, asylum seekers and undocumented migrants (usually underrepresented in mortality analysis) were likely to face a higher risk of contracting infectious diseases, including COVID-19, and experiencing poorer outcomes due to poor living conditions, difficulties at adopting restrictive measures, scarcity of protective equipment, limited access to testing procedures and treatments.

The negative impact of the COVID-19 health emergency has been particularly evident for people living in residential institutions, such as long-stay residential care homes (LSRCHs) and prisons. To monitor the situation and adopt potential strategies aiming at strengthening essential plans and principles for healthcare-associated infection (HCAI) control and prevention, on 24 March 2020, the ISS - in cooperation with Italy's national authority for the rights of prisoners and people deprived of their liberty (GNPL) - launched a survey on COVID-19 infection in LSRCHs. The survey collected responses from 1,356 nursing homes. Among the most difficult aspects related to the management of the health response during the first phase of the emergency the respondents reported: lack of personal protective equipment (77.2%), lack of information received about the procedures to be carried out to contain the infection (20.9%), lack or scarcity of medicines, lack of health personnel (33.8%), difficulties in transferring residents with COVID-19 to hospital facilities (12.5%), difficulty in isolating residents with COVID-19 (26.2%), impossibility to perform Covid-19 tests (52.1%).

3.6 Portugal

Public health system and main actors

The DGS (Directorate-General of Health), Portugal's national public health agency, oversees the promotion and safeguarding of public health, as well as disease prevention and management. It is an independent agency that is described as the *National Health Authority*. DGS has played a significant role in the control of the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal by offering direction and suggestions on precautions, testing, treatment, and vaccine. The DGS supported decision-making and public health initiatives and oversaw the monitoring and surveillance of the epidemic. The National Health Service (SNS), which offers free and open access to healthcare services, is the main provider of healthcare in Portugal's public health system. It is divided into primary care facilities, hospitals, and specialty clinics.

Health crisis preparedness plans

The Portuguese government has a crisis communication framework in place, which comprises a national emergency plan and a communication strategy. While DGS supervises the communication of health-related information to the public and healthcare rules, the National Civil Protection Authority

(ANPC) oversees, coordinates and communicates emergency responses. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the DGS worked closely with other government departments, particularly the Ministry of Health, to organise the national response to the pandemic. We conducted a thorough and lengthy investigation but were unable to uncover any earlier COVID-19 crisis-related government communication plans or initiatives. The Portuguese government had documentations in place before and during the COVID-19 pandemic to cope with pandemics and other crisis circumstances; for example, the National Plan for Pandemic Influenza (DGS, 2007) and the National Emergency Plan. However, the pandemic highlighted gaps in these plans, including the need for more resources, coordination among different sectors, and flexibility in adapting to new situations (Borges et al., 2021).

Crisis management implementation

On March 18, the government proclaimed a state of emergency, giving them exclusive authority to enforce curfews, prohibit travel, and shut down non-essential companies (Governo de Portugal, 2020). The National Contingency Plan for SARS-CoV-2 Infection served as the primary document that guided the DGS and the Ministry of Health's crisis management (DGS, 2020). Measures including illness surveillance, testing, tracking, healthcare response, and communication initiatives were part of the National Contingency Plan (DGS, 2020). The government also formed a task force known as the Operational Task Force for COVID-19, and together with the DGS, the government held public and daily press conferences. Information was made available online and a telephone line was activated for screening.

Before the pandemic, the National Health System demonstrated a lower capacity to respond to systemic risk than the average of the other OECD countries in parameters such as the number of doctors, nurses, and consultations per thousand inhabitants. However, in the beginning of the pandemic, Portugal was in the lead regarding testing per thousand inhabitants (10th among OECD countries), having adopted a policy of testing open to the public (available to all, including asymptomatic) (Monteiro et al., 2022). In terms of restrictive measures, Portugal was one of the ten OECD countries with higher indexes of sanitary strictness (closure of workplaces, schools, travel bans, etc.). However, the lack of personal protective equipment, testing supplies, and medical personnel were a few of the difficulties felt in the public health system (DGS, 2020). As it will be discussed later, Portugal was quite successful in its vaccination efforts, and that success has allowed to lower the sanitary risk stemming from the relative lack of resources in health (compared to other OECD countries) that was felt especially at the beginning of the pandemic (Monteiro et al., 2022).

Portugal's ageing population presented problems in terms of increasing viral susceptibility and healthcare demands (Nordic Welfare Centre, 2020). Due to this demographic element, the healthcare system was put under additional strain to safeguard this vulnerable population. There was also limited capacity for testing and contact tracing, which made it challenging to properly detect and control the transmission of the virus (Público, 2020). In terms of public behaviour, it was difficult to get people to comply with preventative measures. Several population segments showed resistance to or noncompliance with the procedures at certain points in time (Público, 2020).

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

- COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown:

In March 2020, a state of emergency was proclaimed that put Portugal on lockdown. After 45 days in lockdown, starting from May and over the summer, Portugal is no longer under a state of emergency and measures are relaxed. In Autumn 2020 cases rise again to a new maximum and from October, tighter measures are taken to stop the spread. In November, a new state of emergency is proclaimed. Restrictions are made tighter during the winter. To be more efficient in vaccination procedures, by November 2020, the government nominates a task force. The task force for the elaboration of the "Vaccination Plan against COVID-19 in Portugal", initially managed by Francisco Ramos, aims to ensure the coherence and execution of the plan and coordinate the work already done, among all the entities involved in the success of this operation (SNS, 2021a). In December 2020, the vaccination plan was presented, and the priority groups are people over 50 years old with associated pathologies, residents and workers in nursing homes, and health and essential services professionals. By the end of December, vaccines start being administered. By January 2021, Portugal became the country in the world with the highest number of new cases per million inhabitants and big central hospitals announce they are overstrained, working beyond their capacity. In February 2021, the numbers of new deaths and infections are starting to drop. The pressure on hospitals is also beginning to decrease, with fewer hospital admissions and fewer people in intensive care. Francisco Ramos – the initial manager of the task force – is replaced by Vice Admiral Henrique Gouveia e Melo. This task force ended up being very successful and gained a lot of popular support. As vaccination became more widely available, Portugal gradually lifted restrictions, removing the state of emergency in May 2021. In June 2021, Gouveia e Melo announced the creation of an "open house" so that people over 70 (and after that, gradually, younger people) who have been left out of the process can be vaccinated without an appointment. By July, more than half of the population is fully vaccinated. As of September 2021, Portugal had administered over 12 million vaccine doses and fully vaccinated over 6 million people (Our World in Data, 2021).

During this timeframe, the main changes in the resources in the public health system were the reorganisation of hospitals, triage, number of ICU beds, medical staff redirected to COVID-19 units, government website sharing information about the pandemic to control the pandemic, communications by the prime minister after meeting with experts, and the development of the STAYAWAY COVID app to identify possible exposure to the virus.

- Omicron up until September 2022:

The emergence of the Omicron variant in November 2021 led to a resurgence of COVID-19 cases. The government and health authorities responded by reintroducing some measures, such as mask mandates and capacity restrictions. By the end of December 2021 Portugal registered the highest number of new infections, but this is not reflected in the number of hospitalisations and deaths. In February 2022, DGS announced that the biggest surge in cases has passed, and measures are once again relaxed. Portugal's vaccination campaign and experience with the pandemic allowed for a more targeted response to the Omicron variant. As of September 2022, Portugal had fully vaccinated over 85% of its population, and the country had a relatively low number of daily cases (DN, 2021). Throughout the pandemic, the country had Marta Temido as Minister of Health, and Graça Freitas as director of the DGS. In August 2022, Marta Temido left their position and was replaced by Manuel Pizarro (DN, 2022). Also, Graça Freitas left their position for normal retirement.

The crisis response in practice

The response initially focused on controlling the spread of the virus through preventative measures, but as vaccination became more available, the focus shifted to managing the impact of the virus on healthcare and the economy. In fact, this shift in crisis response seemed to be possible mainly because of the COVID-19 vaccination campaign. After the implementation of the task force by November 2020, the vaccination plan became effective. The vaccination campaign is considered, by many, one of the most successful aspects concerning the pandemic response.

“From a personal point of view, it provides protection and tranquillity. In clinical terms, the numbers speak for themselves, with a much lower probability of serious illness and unnecessary hospitalisation, freeing up resources for other clinical situations.” (HCW4)

“In the later phase with Gouveia e Melo things went very well and I think that in terms of communication it couldn't have gone much better, I think it was quite adequate too (...) the implementation of vaccination on a large scale in Portugal was an example of success.” (HCW2)

Additionally, one significant change was the introduction of the digital COVID-19 certificate, which allowed individuals to prove their vaccination status, negative test results, or recovery from COVID-19 (European Commission, 2021). The shift towards a more localised approach to crisis management was another change, with measures and restrictions targeted to areas with higher incidence rates (Observador, 2022). The integration of the National Civil Protection Authority within the Ministry of Internal Administration in September 2021 was a change in the allocation of responsibilities for crisis management, seen as a move to strengthen the government's response to crises (Government of Portugal, 2021). Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors also influenced crisis response. The country's decentralised healthcare system allowed for greater flexibility in decision-making at the local level (Clemente et al., 2021). Communication and coordination were identified as key factors in effective crisis response, with the need to incorporate the perspectives and needs of marginalised and vulnerable populations highlighted (Santos et al., 2021). This coordination did not always happen as efficiently as necessary. In fact, the collaboration between different actors is characterised by an uncoordinated and misaligned communication process with diffuse boundaries regarding the scientific opinion and political opinion which in some situations creates opposite action vectors.

“(...) It was important for people to have access to data, and suddenly the National Health Service stops feeding the website (...) we ask what is going on, and there is no answer (...) so there is a lot of lack of coordination in terms of communication” (PHPDM1)

Based on expert interviews conducted with healthcare workers and a public health decision maker, several aspects were highlighted. The age group seems to have been the main criterion for shaping public health responses. Still, the expert believes that the design of public health measures was guided by inconsistency of perspectives between the scientific community and policy makers, the scientific knowledge has not been sufficiently considered as a foundation for the design of structured measures to respond to the public needs on the pandemic context and these measures were adapted only to some groups of the society, thus giving rise to the emergence of inequalities. It was mentioned that the community inputs were not taken into consideration. Additionally, the expert mentioned that the collaboration between different actors was characterised by an uncoordinated and misaligned

communication, with the political agenda overlapping with the technical/scientific considerations. After the publication of the measures, their implementation was successful at a local level (e.g., use of face masks), but the same cannot be well verified in most distant/interior regions.

In terms of negative impacts on day-to-day life of HCWs, some experts mentioned an increase in workload, consequently associated with less time to rest, less income, and a more stressful/anxiety-inducing work environment. On the other hand, experts from covid-free hospitals or certain specialties that had less consultations during the pandemic experienced decreases in workload in some of their usual functions. In fact, we notice that there is a big difference between the experience of HCWs who worked directly with COVID-19 cases and the experience of those who did not. The experts also highlighted a very accentuated negative impact on patients' ability to access the health services they needed for non-COVID related care; in fact, sectors were changed to respond to COVID-19 cases without compensation to non-COVID patients. Therefore, the polarisation of resources and associated practical barriers resulted in a lack of public healthcare.

“Access to non-COVID-related care was clearly left, for example, our gynaecology block became the COVID block so almost all scheduled gynaecology surgeries ceased to exist (...) There was a great deficit in access to healthcare not related to COVID.” (HCW2)

Negative impacts concerning HCWs' mental health were also referred to. Despite the supposed availability of mental health support (intended by the measures created), most experts refer to a lack of support at the workplace and/or mention receiving only informal support (e.g., keeping in contact with friends). Prejudice and shame were pointed as elements of resistance in seeking mental health support among health professionals. In terms of positive impacts, HCWs mentioned only a few like the emergence of new relationships of mutual and group support.

“There was an opportunity, but it is not a topic that is actually very easy for health professionals, it seems that there is always some degree of prejudice in relation to mental health and health professionals usually do not like to admit to their peers that they may have levels of burnout or anxiety (...) people suffer a lot inside.” (HCW2)

“(...) We managed to assemble a family (...) we managed to establish a bond that remains until today (...) it has also caused a collective that until that moment was not known (...)”. (HCW1)

Regarding successes, it was mentioned that vaccination brought positive outcomes by providing a high level of protection against the virus and mitigating some of its impacts (even though the campaign did not always had great results); the vaccination brought more security at all levels, and it also represented a definitive contribution to facilitate the interactions doctor-patient. Related to this aspect, one of the participants mentioned that teleconsultation was the most effective strategy in the pandemic period.

The public reaction to the crisis management

The public's reaction to the crisis management and changes during the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal varied throughout the course of the pandemic. During the early stages of the pandemic, the Portuguese government was praised for its swift response to the crisis, implementing measures such as lockdowns, mask mandates, and social distancing guidelines. In May 2020, 72% of Portuguese

respondents expressed satisfaction with the government's response to the pandemic, higher than the EU average of 62% (Eurobarometer, 2020). However, as the pandemic continued and restrictions on daily life persisted, frustration and fatigue among the public grew. In November 2020, a protest against the COVID-19 measures drew thousands of people to the streets of Lisbon, with participants expressing their belief that the government was exaggerating the threat (Reuters, 2020). Additionally, the pandemic has had significant economic impacts in Portugal, particularly in industries such as tourism and hospitality. Unemployment rates increased from 6.5% in Q4 2019 to 7.9% in Q4 2020 (Eurostat, 2021), and there have been reports of businesses struggling to stay afloat (Portugal Resident, 2021). In terms of social outcomes, the pandemic has also highlighted inequalities. Low-income and marginalised communities have been disproportionately impacted by the pandemic, with higher rates of infection and greater economic insecurity (ECDC, 2020).

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

In the first months of the pandemic, the government launched a campaign to promote awareness of the risks of COVID-19 among vulnerable groups and to encourage adherence to public health guidelines. This campaign included targeted messaging and information dissemination (WHO, 2020). On the other hand, the expansion of telemedicine services for individuals with chronic health conditions was one of the measures implemented by the public health system (ECDC, 2020). People with chronic conditions were monitored, or at least screened remotely, mostly by telephone, had access to chronic prescriptions by automatic renewal and access was ensured by dispensing medicines usually dispensed by hospital pharmacies in community pharmacies (CNS, 2020). To support the response of HCWs, the “Linha de Apoio ao Médico” (Support Line for Doctors) was activated for validation of suspected cases and a new digital platform (Trace COVID-19) was created for registration of information about the cases, contact tracing, integration of the work done by different teams (Public Health, Family Health, Hospital Care) in the clinical monitoring of each case (CNS, 2020).

Regarding mental health, there was a reorganisation in the departments of mental health and psychiatry, more specifically in the psychiatry services and psychiatry services for children and adolescents, with the elaboration of plans of contingency, norms, and, later on, the articulation with other intervention entities and support entities for children and young people, to expedite communication between the various services in the signalling of urgent cases and vigilance of the most vulnerable groups (elderly, children, isolated individuals and individuals with mental health problems). This response allowed for the psychiatry services and teams to keep running without being “invaded” by other specialties, keeping the assistance to all with severe mental illness. In fact, the number of psychiatry consultations increased from 2019 to 2020 and 2021. In-person consultations never ceased to exist for the more severe cases and teleconsultation and telephone support lines were adopted only for a few months for the less severe cases (returning to in-person as soon as possible) (CNS, 2022).

The government also implemented measures to protect the elderly, such as setting up specific care homes for COVID-19 positive patients and providing support for home care (Reuters, 2020; World Health Organization, 2020). The importance of protecting healthcare workers was addressed by providing personal protective equipment and offering mental health support to those on the front lines (European Commission, 2020; SIC Notícias, 2020). Multiple telephone lines were created at the level of mental health services in hospitals, with the involvement of multidisciplinary teams, for psychological support to health professionals and patients (CNS, 2022). The government also provided support for immigrants and refugees, including access to healthcare, education, and social welfare

benefits (Migration Policy Institute, 2020; *Expresso*, 2021). New vulnerable groups, like low-income workers, were also acknowledged during the pandemic (*The Guardian*, 2020; *Público*, 2020).

During the vaccination rollout and variants after January 2021, not much changed from what had been addressed so far. In terms of vaccination, vulnerable groups were clearly defined as priority groups. These priority groups included: health professionals; armed forces, security and critical services professionals; professionals and residents/elderly in Long Term Care Facilities and similar institutions; and professionals and patients from the National Network for Integrated Continued Care. After these groups, the priority groups that followed were people over 50 with at least one of the mentioned pathologies associated with higher risk and people over 80 (SNS, 2021c).

Besides the efforts already mentioned, we could not identify any other specific measures adopted to support vulnerable groups by the public health system or related to health. There were other forms of support provided by the government, and especially from independent entities or community organisations, but nothing more concerning the public health system and its acknowledgment of vulnerable groups. As expected, there have been concerns about the effectiveness and adequacy of the support measures. Overall, the Portuguese government demonstrated a willingness to acknowledge vulnerabilities during the pandemic, but there has been criticism from the experts regarding the lack of a tailored risk communication and the reactive way of designing programs for the vulnerable. At the same time, at the level of the public health system, the non-COVID services were heavily compromised, leading to several negative impacts and also raising discontent.

Expert interviews - About Vulnerability: Specific vulnerability was highlighted due to disparities in healthcare access and due to a bad distribution of resources, compromising non-COVID patients. Experts consider that the responses to the pandemic have not sufficiently considered the needs of some vulnerable groups. One of the experts mentioned that there is always room for improvement, but that it is – and would always be – difficult to find a balance between protecting vulnerable groups from infection and mitigating the impacts of isolation. However, one positive aspect mentioned was that some vulnerable groups had the benefit of being vaccinated first and more quickly than the rest of the population. Regarding forms of vulnerability, the experts identified and distinguished between medical vulnerability (e.g., vulnerability to infection) and social/socio-economic vulnerability. Concerning self-perceived vulnerability, while one HCW considered everyone to be equally vulnerable, most of the interviewed experts reported a higher level of self-perceived vulnerability due to their occupation and, consequently, a higher exposure and proximal contact with COVID patients and people in general (aligned, at times, with a lack of protective equipment and resources).

Domestic violence was one of the concerns during the pandemic, and civil society organisations launched campaigns to raise awareness and provide support for victims. The economic impact of the pandemic has also affected low-income families and people in precarious jobs, leading to food insecurity and difficulties in paying for basic needs such as rent and utilities. The pandemic has also had an educational impact, particularly for children from low-income families and those with special needs. Host schools were established to receive children and young people unable to take online classes at home and measures were implemented to support remote learning and provide technological equipment. Still, the learning gap created with the pandemic was insufficiently dealt with. Furthermore, there was a negligence of the non-COVID services with groups with other pathologies that need continued consultation and treatment, therefore creating new vulnerabilities. In general, despite being made with the best intentions (e.g., to protect the population), some of the

measures created new vulnerabilities, or only mitigated existing vulnerabilities partially, leaving others – especially the ones related to specific vulnerable groups – to be dealt with.

“Someone who has a more precarious job, these people cannot be doing tests every day (...) if they do tests, then they stay for 15 days, and who finds money for their children to eat? (...) For those who do not have a stable employment situation, they cannot lose their morning of work (...) maybe they are not called the next day. It's obvious that inequalities remain, then if we think in terms of migrant communities, from the lack of understanding of the messages (...) Even these precarious jobs are all out of protection” (PHPDM1).

3.7 Spain

Public health system and main actors

After the first outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, the Spanish government implemented measures to contain the spread of the virus, activated the health system to its maximum capacity, established a legal framework to support the new measures, and introduced financial and economic exceptions and measures. The Ministry of Health was made responsible for managing all aspects of the pandemic, including vaccine purchase and the definition of guidelines and measures. The government also led the design of policies and actions over those of the Autonomous Communities, even overriding them.

Out of this situation, four months after the initial lockdown in March 2020, the Spanish government created the *Plan de respuesta temprana en un escenario de control de la pandemia por COVID-19* (Early Response plan for the transmission increase on a controlled scenario of Covid 19 pandemic) (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020a). This plan has not been updated or reviewed since its release and remains current to this day. In this document, the Spanish government refers to the Covid-19 pandemic as a seasonal flu and states that the situation is under control and heading towards the ‘new normal’, which implies that Covid was an endemic illness and could not be eradicated. The primary concern was to prevent people from being infected with both seasonal flu and Covid-19 at the same time and to avoid swamping hospitals. The key response during that time was to increase flu vaccination.

Crisis management implementation

The initial pandemic response was managed under the National Influenza Response Plan, which was not designed for a pandemic with similar features. This led to logistical and organisational challenges due to a limited legal and operational framework. As the pandemic's scale became apparent, there was a need to develop a tailored legal framework and streamline administrative procedures for rapid mobilisation of resources. This included hiring more professionals, expanding inventory of protective equipment and medicines. The absence of a pandemic-specific plan had a detrimental impact on the timely, coordinated, and effective response of professionals and public administrations, occasionally overwhelming health and social services.

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

The Spanish response to the health crisis caused by COVID-19 did not have a prior preparedness plan. During the months of greatest impact of the pandemic, the health crisis was managed within the framework of a plan designed for a pandemic with different characteristics, the National Influenza Response Plan from 2005 (Ministry of Health, 2005). It wasn't until July 2020 that the Early Response

Plan in a scenario of COVID-19 pandemic control was presented, a plan that has not been updated or reviewed to this day (Ministry of Health, 2020a). Other documents worth mentioning chronologically from the publication of the early response plan are:

On October 22, 2020, a document was presented specifying coordinated response actions for the control of COVID-19 transmission, which includes the technical development of the indicators included in the Early Response Plan and establishes the framework for a proportional response to the different levels of alert defined after a risk assessment process based on epidemiological and public health capacity and assistance indicators (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020b).

On December 2, 2020, the first COVID-19 vaccination strategy was launched, which will have eleven updates, the last of which was on February 8, 2022 (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020c).

On October 2021, the Ministry of Health proposed an evaluation of the performance of the national health system, establishing the necessary guidelines and questions to conduct an adequate evaluation of the pandemic in different health system environments, with the aim of identifying areas for improvement and lines of action to face the new challenges that lie ahead for the health system in the preparation and response to new health crises (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2021a).

On June 3, 2022, the surveillance and control strategy against COVID-19 after the acute phase of the pandemic was launched (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2022a), admitting the change in the epidemiology of COVID-19 and advocating for a transition towards a different strategy that monitors and directs actions towards people and areas of greater vulnerability.

The current situation of COVID-19 in Spain

The latest D5.5 report has updated information on the health situation of COVID-19 until June 2022. Since then, the COVID situation has been stable, and two events are worth mentioning: 1) On September 26, 2022, the vaccination campaign for the second booster dose began (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2022b). 2) On February 7, 2023, the council of ministers approved the elimination of the mandatory use of masks in public transportation, remaining mandatory in healthcare and socio-sanitary centres, as well as in pharmacies (BOE, 2023). Currently, in May 2023, the debate remains open on whether masks should continue to be mandatory in healthcare, socio-sanitary centres, and pharmacies, where they are still mandatory (El País, 2023).

The changes in the crisis response

The COVID-19 pandemic hit early and hard, causing significant damage both in terms of public health and the economy. Spain has a series of characteristics, such as an ageing population, high levels of social interaction, and the labour market structure (economic dependence on tourism and the catering sector, the importance of the informal economy) that contributed to worsening the crisis. The high constant flow of people both within the country and from abroad was fundamental to the rapid spread of the virus in the initial phase. The age structure of the population also disadvantaged Spain, exacerbated by intergenerational cohabitation in households. Additionally, the physical proximity in social interactions contributed to the spread of the contagion, and the collapse of the tourism industry during the pandemic further exacerbated economic difficulties (Navarro and Velasco, 2022).

At the beginning of the health crisis in 2020, coordination between the different levels of government in Spain was an additional challenge. The pandemic proved to be a complex intergovernmental problem worldwide, requiring high collaboration between governments and testing governance

systems. In a decentralised country like Spain, with jurisdictional conflicts and territorial divisions, vertical coordination between the different levels of government was critical in crisis management. This fact is one of the most highlighted aspects among experts interviewed (both decision-makers and healthcare workers), to know clearly who was responsible for decision making and to create mechanisms that guarantee adequate accountability.

This unprecedented situation led to four phases in government management: from February to the end of 2020 (Navarro and Velasco, 2022). Starting with a decentralised strategy during the first two weeks, followed by total centralization of power in the hands of the central government during the next three months, a third phase where the autonomous communities participated again in governance processes, and finally, during the management of the second wave of contagion and the second state of emergency, a softer centralization was applied with less restrictive measures and again, more decision-making power in the autonomous communities.

This is where the concept of co-governance arises, which was essential to address the additional challenges facing the Spanish political system due to the lack of effective mechanisms for vertical coordination when the pandemic broke out. Although some coordination mechanisms already existed, such as the Conference of Presidents or the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System, they had to be reformed to act more effectively. The system went through a constant learning process to find ways to overcome the crisis and establish more collaborative multilevel structures, although it faced territorial tensions and traditional blame games of the Spanish multilevel system. The pandemic also demonstrated the great adaptability of the decentralisation system, which was able to adapt to the different phases of the health crisis, but also showed that the system can suspend well-established subnational competencies, which has implications for Spain's "quasi-federal" decentralisation model (Erkoreka and Hernando-Pérez, 2022).

On the other hand, Royo (2020) argues that there are three dimensions in which Spain fell far short: first, in terms of efficiency, as the lack of predictability in the institutional and political environment undermined the response to the pandemic; second, in terms of transparency, as the lack of available and reliable data and the lack of information provided to the general public deeply undermined trust in the government; and finally, in terms of participation, as the government rarely encouraged public participation in decision-making and failed to engage the opposition in a timely and constructive manner.

On a positive note, this experience helped in negotiating and building a dialogue between political decision-makers with different interests and the scientific community, resulting in evidence-based health measures. The coordination with European and international bodies such as European Medicines Agency and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control further strengthened the technical-scientific cooperation. A comprehensive evaluation of the government's response to the COVID-19 crisis remains to be done. One of the main shortcomings is the lack of independent audits to assess the measures taken and identify critical points that need correction. A thorough evaluation is crucial to determine the results and impacts of the measures taken and create a more robust framework for future pandemics.

Regarding the strategy for vaccination, the Spanish health system's previous experience with vaccination campaigns has been a great advantage in achieving the COVID-19 immunisation goals. The vaccination strategy has been reviewed and updated based on scientific evidence, and adjustments have been made through dialogue and agreements between decision-makers and their expert

committees. This, along with following EU and EMA guidelines, has been crucial in the success of vaccination campaigns.

Limitations have been observed in terms of testing and screening strategy. Since only those who developed symptoms were tested, asymptomatic individuals were hard to track. Moreover, differences between testing and tracing criteria across Autonomous Communities hindered data comparability. The lack of tracers has negatively impacted screening efforts and transmission control.

The pandemic has highlighted the need to strengthen primary care and invest in infrastructure and human resources. The 2008 crisis weakened the National Health System, and the pandemic has emphasised the importance of a robust public health system and a comprehensive information system to improve decision-making. Strengthening the epidemiological surveillance and monitoring system should be a priority to generate early warnings and effective follow-up.

Finally, the crisis management has highlighted the importance of promoting health security by increasing investment in R&D&I in the health sector, particularly in developing vaccines and medicines in Spain. This investment would mitigate vulnerability and external dependence and guarantee a national strategic reserve of health supplies in the event of pandemics or human catastrophes.

The response to this point is based exclusively on the interviews conducted for WP5, both with decision-makers (DM) and HCW. The information gathered through the expert interviews should not be generalised, however, when analysing the five interviews (2 DM and 3 HCW) we find common patterns that show us which points of the debate are central and relevant to the whole.

“The assessment, interpretation of information, data analysis, recommendation proposals and decision making were carried out at an impressive speed”, as stated in WP5_2_DM’s interview. “To achieve this, hierarchies were eliminated, and a unified team was created. In this team, all levels of management, from politicians to deputy directors, area chiefs and technicians, had equal weight and sat at the same table. Thanks to this structure, decisions were made directly and quickly, based largely on technical-scientific evidence”.

This approach increased levels of accountability, pressure on the unit and on the quality of information. When asked whether the measures implemented had the desired effects, this same expert declares that, although they were defined in detail, “sometimes the measures were broader than what made sense from a transmission control point of view, but that was what allowed them to be implemented”.

It was mentioned that decision-makers felt pressured to take measures if other countries were taking them, even if it did not make sense for their specific situation. This fact weighed heavily in the decision-making process, leading technicians to apply policies and practices even if they felt that some measures were not necessary.

Meanwhile, another decision-maker (WP5_1_DM) is of the opinion that “*the autonomous communities have faced the pandemic alone*”, implying that the government wanted the autonomous communities to take action when things were going badly and the government to take credit when things were going well, and this has resulted in a bad relationship with the Ministry of Health (the Madrid government during the pandemic has been of the opposite political party as the central government). Furthermore, cooperation between political institutions has been stated to be poor, with too much politicisation and lack of coordination between the central government and the autonomous communities. Also, that the information transmitted to the press has been insufficient, which has caused confusion among the population. This opinion of the second decision-maker shows the

continuous quarrel between the central government and the Community of Madrid during the pandemic.

One of the most negative aspects of the pandemic was, in fact, the excessive politicisation of the health crisis, which according to various studies led to a change in the transcendental, social and interpersonal beliefs of Spaniards, producing an increase in polarisation (Bernacer et al., 2021). Thus, it is curious to observe the different points of view depending on the position in which one finds oneself, for example, WP5_1_DM highlights as something positive or extraordinary that the health professionals were the ones who made the necessary organisational changes in the centres to cope with the pandemic, that is, that there was a bottom-up transformation; this opinion is opposed to that given by the HCWs. The HCWs interviewed for WP5 highlight the lack of leadership from above, pointing out that each centre has done what it could, but they do not understand how it is possible that in the middle of the pandemic there were empty beds, that there was no transfer policy between autonomous communities, that resources were not passed between them, and so on. Another problem pointed out by one of the HCWs is that the “politicians did not take difficult decisions to avoid court indictments, leaving all this burden of responsibility to the physicians at the front line” (WP5_2_HCW). In short, for HCWs the situation seems to have been more difficult than for decision-makers, who have had to face the crisis first hand, while experiencing a sense of abandonment by the institutions, a lack of guidance and coordination.

The public reaction to the crisis management

Culture, defined as norms, values and beliefs, can influence social behaviours such as the response of authorities and citizens during the COVID-19 pandemic in Spain (Bruna et al., 2020). On the one hand, they influence the decisions of policymakers and, on the other hand, they condition the willingness of citizens to follow confinement, hygiene and physical distancing measures.

Spain has a low level of interpersonal trust, but places a high importance on the values of conformity and obedience, possibly as a mechanism to reduce uncertainty stemming from a lack of trust. It follows that coercive measures adopted in Spain reflect these predominant values and may be more effective than in other more cooperative contexts. Moreover, low citizen trust and the need to foster compliance suggest that policies should focus on improving credibility and education (Bruna et al., 2020).

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

To see the vulnerabilities of the Spanish public health system, we have to take into consideration the points on which the *early response plan* focuses, where, without explicitly pointing out the vulnerabilities of the system, it does so indirectly in point 3 of the text, where it mentions the pillars of early response (capacities in the field of public health and private care, capacities for the implementation of prevention and collective protection measures...) throughout the successive paragraphs we see how the text points out the points to be strengthened in the system (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020a).

It is possible that this question could be better answered in the future, as an *evaluation of the performance of the Spanish national health system in the face of the covid-19 pandemic* (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2021a) is being carried out, which in principle should answer those issues that are the subject of the question posed.

With regard to HCWs, based on the action procedures for occupational risk prevention services against exposure to SARS-CoV-2, the following table shows the vulnerability or not of these groups depending on the tasks they carry out (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020d).

Risk exposure Low risk exposure Low probability of exp

Risk exposure	Low risk exposure	Low probability of exposure
<p>Healthcare and non-healthcare workers caring for a suspected or confirmed case of COVID-19.</p> <p>Healthcare transport technicians, if there is direct contact with a transferred suspected or confirmed COVID-19 case.</p> <p>Situations where close contact at work with a suspected or confirmed COVID-19 case cannot be avoided.</p>	<p>Healthcare workers whose work does not involve close contact with a suspected or confirmed case of COVID-19, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Companions for transportation. - Orderlies, orderlies, cleaners. <p>Laboratory staff responsible for virological diagnostic tests.</p> <p>Non-health-care workers who have contact with possibly contaminated medical equipment, fomites or waste.</p> <p>Home help for asymptomatic contacts.</p>	<p>Workers without direct contact with the public, or at a distance of more than 2 metres, or with collective protection measures that prevent contact, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administrative staff. - Health transport technicians with a collective barrier, without direct contact with the patient. - Public transport drivers with a collective barrier. - Security personnel.
Requirements		
<p>Depending on the specific exposure risk assessment of each case: components of biological protection PPE and, under certain circumstances, aerosol and splash protection.</p>	<p>Depending on the specific risk assessment of each case: components of biological protection PPE.</p>	<p>Not necessary to use PPE.</p> <p>In certain situations (lack of cooperation of a symptomatic person):-respiratory protection,- protective gloves.</p>

Table 1. Risk scenarios for exposure to SARS-CoV-2 in the work environment **Source:** Ministry of Health

Furthermore, we see that they are recognised as a vulnerable group as they are included in the first phase of vaccination (Gobierno de España, 2022).

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

The social groups most affected by the pandemic have been children, the elderly, women, people with functional diversity, people with intellectual disabilities, immigrants in an irregular administrative situation, people with unshared family responsibilities, people deprived of their liberty or addicted to substances, and people who are chronically ill or without a regular income (Morcillo Martínez, 2021). We can see how, from the very beginning, vulnerable groups were already taken into account (Presno Linera, 2020), as in the RD 463/2020, of 14 March, which declared a state of alarm for the management of the health crisis situation caused by COVID-19 establishes in Article 4 that any protection measures carried out must necessarily pay attention to vulnerable groups.

Chronology of the response to the needs of vulnerable groups

On 18 March 2020, the technical document of recommendations for action in the face of the crisis by covid-19, for managers of social services for homeless care (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020e) and home-based care (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020f) is launched.

On 27 March 2020, the technical document of recommendations for action by social services in the face of the COVID-19 crisis in segregated settlements and highly vulnerable neighbourhoods is published (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020g).

On 31 March 2020, the technical document of recommendations for action by the public system for the protection of children and adolescents in the face of the COVID-19 crisis (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020h) is made public.

Between 10 June 2020 and 6 September 2022, a series of measures are taken in relation to penitentiary institutions (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020i & Ministerio de Sanidad, 2022c).

On 29 October 2020, a document is launched that ties in very well with this point, the document health equity and covid-19, an analysis and proposals to tackle epidemiological vulnerability related to social inequities, which defines social vulnerability, the "social determinants impacting on epidemiological vulnerability to covid-19 (employment, clustered housing, precarious economic conditions, disadvantaged residential areas, digital gap...) and a series of proposals to address these situations (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2020j).

From the beginning of the pandemic until 2 August 2021, the ministry is carrying out a series of reports called "COVID-19 in different environments and groups of people" where it analyses and updates how COVID-19 can affect different groups of people (the elderly, people with different illnesses, pregnant women, smokers, people with obesity, children and adolescents, people with mental illnesses, and the effect of COVID-19 on different groups of people), and how the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 acts in different environments (residential centres for the elderly, work environments, health centres, educational centres and socially vulnerable population), in which the measures to be taken were updated, although the points on which the report is based have not altered over time (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2021b).

In addition, a series of actions are being implemented by the public administration and social entities in Spain to deal with the consequences of this crisis (Morcillo Martínez, 2021):

Measures to strengthen social services in emergency situations. The Spanish government has established a social fund to support projects and labour contracts for enhancing social services. These services include home-based telecare, assistance for the homeless, and virus prevention in residential centres. The central government and Autonomous Communities recognized the importance of considering social services as essential during the pandemic. Various measures have been taken, such as providing psychological support for social service workers, expediting funding mechanisms for municipalities, hiring new professionals, and improving coordination between community and specialised services. Additionally, relevant technical documents and recommendations have been issued by multiple ministries and professional bodies.

Measures to prevent the transmission of the virus in social and healthcare facilities. Residential homes for institutionalised individuals implemented several measures. These included categorising residents based on their physical and cognitive status, disinfecting facilities, providing psychosocial support

services for families, establishing a telephone service for additional support, and facilitating secure video-call communications with families. Other actions taken were hiring more staff, transferring inspection responsibilities to Health Departments, opening dedicated institutions for non-hospitalized elderly COVID-19 patients, and enforcing a complete ban on visits by relatives. Furthermore, Order SND/265/2020 of 19 March outlined specific measures for homes for the elderly and social-health centres in response to the COVID-19 crisis.

Financial resources have been allocated to ensure the basic right to food during the pandemic. This is essential to address child and adolescent poverty. There is a need to analyse how cash benefits can help to overcome these difficulties and to improve their management so that they reach those in need more efficiently. The way in which the pandemic has been tackled in Spain has highlighted the importance of investing in improving the management of cash benefits.

Measures to improve home care during confinement. During confinement, the care of people with dependency or disability in their homes was affected for various reasons, such as the closure of day centres and the difficulty for carers to move around. To address this situation, a number of measures were implemented, such as the reinforcement of telecare, the delivery of food at home, the anticipation of dependency benefit payments and the improvement of home care services. While these initiatives have been effective, interventions are still needed to address the consequences of prolonged isolation of older people during the pandemic. Confinement was necessary to prevent the spread of the virus, but its prolonged duration can put people's physical and mental health at risk.

Measures to care for the homeless. During the pandemic, homeless people have found themselves in a particularly vulnerable situation, as many of the prevention measures (social distancing, hygiene, isolation) are not feasible for those without a home. To address this problem, various measures have been implemented to enable this group to be confined safely and in good conditions. These include the provision of emergency accommodation in schools, shelters, municipal housing and other community facilities.

Measures to tackle the problem of gender-based violence and to prevent and care for women victims of violence. The situation of confinement and prolonged cohabitation with aggressors have increased the risk of gender violence. For this reason, various measures have been implemented, such as public awareness campaigns, reinforcement of telephone and psychological care, as well as the publication of guides and materials to raise awareness and provide guidance to women victims. In addition, resources such as safe accommodation have been made available and care and protection for the children of victims of gender violence has been promoted.

3.8 Sweden

Public health system and main actors

The Swedish healthcare system is highly decentralised, involving all three levels of government (national, regional, local) and with expertise allocated to large autonomous agencies, regions and municipalities. Based on legal provisions (harmonised legislation and guidelines) and under the supervision of the Government through the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs and other government agencies, the county councils or regions and the municipalities are responsible for providing and funding a wide range of health-related services.

The Government gives general policy instructions to the national government agencies and political direction is issued through the Government's budget allocation, legislation, directives and managerial appointments. Apart from the healthcare Act, the regions and municipalities are ruled by the Swedish Local Government Act. The Government works closely with the National Board for Health and Welfare (NBHW) and the Public Health Agency (PHA). At the regional level, 12 county councils and 9 regional bodies are responsible for financing and delivering health services to citizens. At the local level, 290 municipalities are responsible for care of the elderly and the disabled.

National agencies in the healthcare sector have no responsibility or control over the regions delivering healthcare; their only means of guiding the region is to provide information and to maintain informal networks (Pierre, 2020; Statskontoret, 2020). Overall, the healthcare system is highly dependent on coordination and management. The decentralisation has led to regional differences in terms of cost-sharing, type of treatment, access to new medicines, available care, and mortality.

ECONOMICAL RESOURCES: The Swedish healthcare system is financed through taxes and fees (out-of-pocket payments). The level of taxes to be allocated to the health sector is decided by the elected parliaments on the three levels: National Government for the general taxation, the county councils or regions decide the county taxation, and the municipalities are responsible for local taxation. The Parliament, the central Government, the county councils and the municipalities set the public budget for healthcare, on each level respectively. The funds to be allocated to each sector/type of care are determined by the counties/regions and the municipalities, given their respective responsibilities.

MEDICAL RESOURCES: *Regionally organised services* include primary, specialist, outpatient and hospital care, health promotion, disease prevention and rehabilitation. The county level responsibility of healthcare brings on differences in the way the various types of care are organised. Overall, general practitioners (GPs) in public health centres provide primary care, while outpatient specialist care is provided in outpatient departments in public hospitals. Most hospitals are local with limited specialisation, and some regional, offering a wider range of specialties. Seven of these hospitals are highly specialised university hospitals. Healthcare provision has traditionally been public. However, private provision, notably in terms of private primary care providers with whom the councils or regions establish contracts, has been encouraged during the last decades. Private companies own some hospitals, even if they are financed by public funds.

Far below the average in the EU, is the number of intensive care beds. In 2015, the Swedish average was 226 per 100 000 inhabitants compared to the EU average of 402.

The *municipalities* are responsible for elderly care, care for people with physical and mental disabilities, support and service to people who have been treated and discharged from hospital care, for school healthcare, and for long term care (LTC) (ibid). The primary LTC service is mainly home care, comprising help with daily activities and personal care. Also other services such as home nursing care, personal safety alarms and transportation services are available. The responsibility of medical care and rehabilitation for elderly in ordinary homes is shared between municipalities and regions. This places high demands on the coordination of care between them.

Health crisis preparedness plans

In 2005, the NBHW was commissioned by the Government to produce a national pandemic plan that included plans for national interventions and provided a basis for regional planning. It was revised in 2009, and later in 2012 after the swine flu, and again in 2015 after the Ebola outbreak. Since 2015, the

PHA coordinates pandemic preparedness at national level in Sweden and provides support for planning at regional and local levels. The pandemic plan was revised again in 2019. The current plan consists of three volumes:

- Folkhälsomyndigheten, Pandemiberedskap. Hur vi förbereder oss – ett kunskapsunderlag, 2019. [Pandemic preparedness. How we prepare – a knowledge-base]
- Folkhälsomyndigheten, Pandemiberedskap. Hur vi kommunicerar – ett kunskapsunderlag, 2019. [Pandemic preparedness. How we communicate – a knowledge-base]
- Folkhälsomyndigheten, Pandemiberedskap. Tillgång till och användning av läkemedel – en vägledning, 2019. [Pandemic preparedness. Access to and use of pharmaceuticals – guidelines]

The overall structure of the Swedish crisis management system is that a crisis should be handled by public authorities according to their respective areas of responsibility, following the three basic principles of responsibility, equality, and proximity. The Government's tasks in crisis management involve primarily strategic issues, and the responsibility for command and coordination of operational work lies with the relevant authorities and agencies. The PHA is responsible for coordinating preparedness against serious health threats, including a pandemic and its consequences. The agency is also designated to be the national contact point for the WHO and the ECDC. The Swedish Civil Contingency Agency's (SCCA) main tasks are to develop and support coordination of society's emergency preparedness. Support must also be provided to national authorities, regions, municipalities and industry in their emergency preparedness.

Crisis preparedness at the regional level is partly administered and falls under the responsibility of 21 national *County Administrative Boards*. A County Administrative Board is responsible for its geographical area as well as for state activities within its county. A County Administrative Board should aim to reduce vulnerability in society, ensure that risk and preparedness considerations are included in community planning and develop capacity to handle peacetime crisis. Before, during and after a crisis, the County Administrative Board should promote coordination and a common approach of the measures that need to be taken.

Sweden's 21 *regions* are responsible, among other things, for healthcare and infection control. The regions' responsibility for emergency preparedness also includes disaster medical preparedness (as well as responsibility for pandemic preparedness). Each region has an infection control physician who develops a pandemic plan and liaises with those responsible for preparedness in the region. The regulations and general advice on emergency medical preparedness from the NBHW state that a region must plan its healthcare to maintain emergency medical preparedness. The planning must be based on the region's risk and vulnerability analysis. Since the regions operate within the counties' geographical areas, they are expected to cooperate with both the county administrative boards and the municipalities in their analysis work.

Most Swedish *hospitals* had a pandemic plan prior to the COVID-19 outbreak, but the scope and focus varied widely. In most hospitals, the pandemic plan scenario was based on influenza. In some hospitals, the pandemic plan was part of the disaster plan, which was more focused on natural disasters and accidents, and in other hospitals there were more detailed plans for infections such as Ebola. No plan was suited to such high volumes or to the handling of the COVID-19 pandemic. The hospitals generally experienced a very early and rapid escalation in the number of COVID patients.

The *municipalities* are responsible for several activities at the local level, including elderly care. Within their geographical area, they must promote cooperation and coordination in planning and preparation in the case of extraordinary events in peacetime.

Crisis management implementation

Sweden reported the first case of COVID-19 infection at the end of January 2020, when a woman returning from China tested positive. One month later 12 cases were registered, and no casualties. The PHA encouraged travellers who had been abroad to get tested to track the infection. The risk of a widespread epidemic in Sweden was considered as low.

The situation changed dramatically during the first two weeks in March. On the same day that the WHO declared the disease a pandemic (March 11th), the first person died from COVID-19 in Sweden. The PHA then assessed COVID-19 to be community spread. Focus was then directed on containing the spread of the virus to avoid overloading hospitals with patients, and a “flattening the curve”-approach was implemented as the main strategy. The virus was still not considered a mortal threat to people not belonging to high-risk groups (elderly, those with underlying illnesses). To use recommendations rather than legal restrictions and lockdown, was considered a more effective and sustainable way to manage the pandemic. No mandatory restrictions were implemented. In March 2020, the government and the PHA urged the public to avoid unnecessary visits to hospitals and nursing homes, and to refrain from non-essential travels abroad and all non-essential travels from outside Europe were stopped. Also, distance learning for all secondary schools, colleges and universities was recommended, and people over 70 years old were advised to minimise non-essential social contacts. However, primary schools, restaurants, shops, and factories remained open.

Barriers to implementation of what was planned

Several barriers to implementation of pre-planned strategies were pointed out in later evaluations and reports:

- Unclear or decentralised responsibility for infection control.
- Limited testing capacity.
- High levels of staff turnover within elderly care, limited training, and limited knowledge of Swedish language among the staff that aggravated the situation (SOU, 2020:80; IVO, 2021).
- Lack of medical supplies (facemasks, protective equipment) due to a just-in-time delivery system and previous out-phasing of stocking equipment.
- Lack of intensive care beds.
- Lack of overall coordination of healthcare between different regions, between regions and municipalities, and between different municipalities. In short, a too decentralised healthcare structure.

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

April 2020 became the deadliest month in Sweden (2.913 deaths). The first wave was over as the vacation period (July) approached. The PHA and other authorities urged citizens to uphold social distancing, handwashing, and home office if possible. During the first months of the fall 2020, things were gradually getting back to normal even if distant working and teaching at universities still was the

“new normal”. Gatherings for more than 50 persons were not allowed, and sports events were conducted without an audience. Amusement parks and other public venues were kept closed. In September, less than 50 persons died from COVID-19, and the Government and government agencies worked on a plan for reopening society.

Then, signs of cluster outbreaks were detected in the city of Uppsala in October and by the end of the month the second wave was confirmed. The numbers of infected persons rose from 141 in October to 1,263 in November. New and stronger measures were imposed. Public gatherings were limited to 8 persons and authorities urged citizens only to socialise with those sharing the same household. Infection rates reached a new record in December (more than 205,000 cases) and more than 2,608 individuals died with an ongoing COVID-19 infection. The number of hospitalizations also reached a new record.

A new pandemic law was implemented in January 2021. It allowed for public gatherings to be dissolved, and gyms, restaurants and malls to be closed if restrictions were not followed. Only then, the PHA recommended face masks in public transport during rush hours. The recommendation expired six months later (July 2021). Face masks were never mandatory in Sweden during the pandemic, and complete lockdowns were never implemented.

When reports about mutations of the virus appeared Sweden closed the borders to the UK, Denmark and Norway in an attempt to stop the British mutation from spreading in the country. These measures were in vain. The British mutation caused the curve of infections to rise again in March 2021. The third wave had arrived but death tolls continued to decrease. Vaccination of elderly people explains these opposing trends.

Vaccinations started on 27 December. In the first phase, people in particular need of protection were vaccinated. In the second phase, which started in February 2021, healthcare workers and people over 70 years of age were also included. By summer 2021, the majority of older age groups were vaccinated. Several municipalities introduced vaccination requirements for new staff in health and social care by the end of 2021.

2.) Omicron up until September 2022

TheOMICRON-version of the virus started to spread in Sweden during the first weeks of January 2022. In early February, 3 223 new cases of COVID-19 were registered in the Stockholm region and by the beginning of March this figure had doubled to 6 336 cases.

From May 2022 to 1 December 2022, the number of registered deaths in Sweden had grown by around 2,400 people without a direct wave of disease being registered. A fifth wave of COVID-19 then hit Sweden between December 2022 and January 2023, causing 2,500 new deaths.

Despite the level of transmission, there were fewer cases of severe infection due to high vaccination coverage. Fewer people needed intensive care and fewer deaths compared to previous waves.

In February 2023, 86% of Swedes older than 17 years had received at least two vaccinations against COVID-19. Restrictions on crowds and restaurant visits were lifted on 9 February 2022. The ban on the entry of non-citizens was lifted on 1 April 2022. The national ban on visits to elderly care facilities ended on 1 October 2020. The temporary corona law expired on 31 March 2022.

The crisis response in practice

The initial strategy of the PHA was to allow a controlled spread of infection to achieve herd immunity. It was estimated that a sufficient level of herd immunity would be reached before vaccination was possible. The calculation turned out to be inaccurate. All regions in Sweden changed their strategy and cancelled the tracing of infection in mid-March 2020 on the advice of the PHA.

During March 2020, intensive care resources were concentrated in specific cities. From mid-February to April, the number of planned surgeries decreased by 63% to save protective equipment. Early in the pandemic, many regions began to significantly expand the number of intensive care beds. By the end of May 2020, there was generally no shortage of intensive care beds in Sweden. The readiness to move patients between regions was strengthened with helicopters and ambulances from the armed forces

As the pandemic proceeded, regions rapidly reorganised their health systems to increase capacity where it was most needed. The flexibility of regional healthcare was a prerequisite for this reorganisation. At the same time, the transformation came at a high price in the form of deferred care and exhausted staff. The consequences were particularly severe for municipalities and regions, which entered the crisis with an already heavily burdened organisation. In addition to restructuring, the regions had to build up logistics for broad-based vaccination and large-scale sampling. The build-up has revealed a number of strengths and weaknesses in government governance. In several important processes, late and unclear decisions on the division of roles between the state and municipalities/regions led to unnecessary delays at critical stages.

Reflections on pandemic management in terms of public health responses

Here we refer primarily to the summary of six interviews already submitted to the project on request. A summary follows below. All interviews were conducted with healthcare workers and managers in the City of Gothenburg and the Region of Västra Götaland.

BARRIERS

Overall, the coronavirus pandemic revealed major shortcomings in the preparedness of pharmaceutical supply, medical and protective equipment for healthcare workers. The market's just-in-time production could not cope with a global pandemic.

At the beginning of the pandemic, all the IPs working in elderly care report strong concerns about becoming infected and passing on the infection to their own family members. These concerns diminished after the implementation of vaccinations, both by staff and patients. Mental stress was also caused by negative publicity in news media and especially social media claiming staff within elderly care passed on the infection to the care takers, and that staff was not sufficiently trained to take care of the elderly. Staff were also exposed to direct threats on social media or from relatives to care takers.

IPs also experienced an increased workload and stress at the beginning of the pandemic. This was partly due to the spread of infection among care recipients, partly due to a lack of protective equipment, and partly due to time-consuming new routines in the use of protective equipment.

IPs explain that also care recipients have felt substantial fear, sadness, anxiousness and loneliness during the pandemic. The increased workload, and limited time with each care recipient, has caused stress for both staff and the elderly. The IP emphasises that the social distancing has been especially difficult for many immigrant care recipients that come from a culture of multi-generational living.

Several IPs report coordination problems, mainly between different levels of the care chain but in some cases also between different functions within the same level. Overall, the lack of interfaces in the formal organisation has been overcome by spontaneous initiatives and the use of informal structures.

GOOD PRACTICES

Several IPs report a stronger cohesion in teams and a greater understanding and knowledge of each other's tasks. One IP claims that staff developed a deeper care and respect for each other. A sense of belonging and working as a whole team, and a feeling of being needed and carrying out important work is the greatest take-away, and also an area for development in general for future work.

There was a local Covid support team established within elderly home care services during summer of 2020 consisting of extra staff that only handled COVID positive patients. This was found helpful as they assisted with e.g., testing and relieved work-load.

Vaccination had a positive impact on the healthcare worker's working environment

LESSONS LEARNED

One IP argues that increased vaccination was a pivotal factor in changing the work environment for the better; the staff, the IP included, as well as the care recipients who then perceive themselves as less vulnerable and scared.

The IP further emphasises the importance of the aforementioned COVID team in assisting the routine work.

Another IP mentioned the importance of working towards a better understanding of working conditions and tasks between different units in the regional and local healthcare chain.

The public reaction to the crisis management

Quarantine and self-isolation: These measures were never mandatory in Sweden, only recommendations. However large parts of the population seem to voluntarily have reduced social contacts. According to a representative survey from 2021: 79 % avoided travelling with public transports, 84 % refrained from visiting pubs and restaurants, 89 % refrained from travelling during vacations, 80 % refrained from seeing friends, 40 % worked/studied from home.

There is a correlation between level of income and vaccination, i.e. the higher the income, the higher the proportion who have been vaccinated. There is a correlation between income level and vaccination coverage regardless of age and country of birth. The greatest difference between vaccination coverage and income groups is among persons born in countries outside Europe, the least difference is among persons born in Sweden.

Vaccination coverage also differs by educational level, The higher education, the higher vaccination rates.

Trust in government authorities and healthcare providers: There was a rally effect regarding trust in government and government institutions during the first month of the pandemic in 2020 and the support for the PHA increased between March and April 2020. This support later declined as did the support for the Swedish strategy to handle the pandemic. In contrast, the trust in government was

higher 18 months into the pandemic than before the outbreak. Trust in healthcare providers increased significantly between February and April 2020 and remained stable for the following 12 months.

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

Vulnerable groups were identified at the beginning of the pandemic based on the following conditions:

Age: Persons 70 years and older were directly identified as a vulnerable group.

Health conditions: Persons suffering from obesity, heart conditions, respiratory problems, diabetes, cancer, and pregnant women.

Vulnerable groups that were identified after a while based on the following conditions:

Socio-Economic: People living in overcrowded households, with limited opportunities to work from home, dependent on public transports, with exposed professions, e.g. taxi drivers, cashiers. To a large extent these conditions applied for the majority of migrants living in Sweden.

healthcare workers: Already before the pandemic there was a shortage of trained healthcare professionals in Sweden. The problem increased dramatically during the pandemic due to growing sick absence among healthcare staff. Vaccination coverage (two doses) among hospital staff was 94 %. Among nursing staff in residential care homes it was slightly lower.

The number of sick hours among nurses, midwives, biomedical analysts and radiographers increased by 28% between 2019 and 2020. In 2021, sick hours decreased slightly but was still almost 15% higher than in 2019. There are no official statistics on how many healthcare workers that were affected by post-COVID or died from COVID-19.

How the pandemic and the heavy workload affected healthcare workers psychologically is unclear. Sweden has not carried out any coordinated screening or support programmes for the staff.

Elderly - information targeted at older people was provided from the outbreak of the pandemic. The main message was to isolate themselves from social contacts. Home care workers were required to use protective equipment in all contacts with elderly care recipients.

Migrants – information was available in more than 20 different languages, and in migrant dense suburbs so called “vaccination interpreters” were hired by the local communities/municipalities to inform migrant residents with poor Swedish language skills about the possibilities and benefits of vaccination. The “vaccination interpreters” were recruited among residents in migrant dense areas.

healthcare workers, especially in elderly care. Already March 2020, it was recognised that healthcare providers were suffering from lack of adequate protective equipment. Also, there was a lack of training and language skills among staff in elderly care. As well as employment conditions (hourly contracts) that made employees go to work even if they felt sick.

Sweden never implemented total lockdown. Instead, arguments were forwarded from the PHA to avoid total isolation of persons and closing of workplaces to avoid psychological and economical constraints on people and society. Those who were forced to work or study from home (university and college/upper secondary school students) testified to psychological strain from homework and isolation. Study performance was said to deteriorate among these groups.

On the other hand, teachers and healthcare professionals objected to not closing pre-schools and primary schools, mentioning a greater risk of becoming infected themselves. The latter group of professionals already considered themselves particularly vulnerable.

For people 70 years and older, there is a lot of evidence that those who were already socially, economically and health-wise vulnerable suffered more from mental problems during the pandemic. The lack of social contacts was significant. Digital exclusion, such as not being able to participate in digital activities, became more pronounced when people could not meet in person. This applied not least to certain groups of foreign-born residents.

In its audit report of 17 May 2022, the Swedish National Audit Office wrote, among other things, that "the state's work to ensure access to personal protective equipment during the coronavirus pandemic [...] was not carried out effectively. The deficiencies in the regions' and municipalities' supply preparedness existed before the pandemic and had been pointed out a number of times /.../ the government and the responsible authorities should have [previously] done more to address these deficiencies." Auditor General Helena Lindberg said that "in times of crisis, how the responsible authorities handle their responsibilities and roles is tested. The authorities focused on their other core tasks rather than on coordinating their actions for effective crisis management". The hesitation of the County Administrative Boards was unwarranted and contributed to unnecessary delays in the state's crisis management." [ibid].

3.9 England

Public health system and main actors

For citizens and residents of the United Kingdom (UK), the UK provides a universal healthcare system through the National Health Service (NHS). The healthcare system is mainly funded via taxation, national insurance, and patient charges. In the UK, there is; (1) 135 Clinical Commissioning Groups (CCGs), (2) 1,300 Primary Care Networks established in June 2019, (3) 77 NHS Trusts/150 NHS Foundation Trusts, (4) 151 Local Authorities who are responsible for public health services for children up to 19 years old and other services, and (5) 7 regional teams. Prior to COVID-19, Public Health England (PHE), a Government executive agency, supported health authorities in the UK. Established in 2013, PHE became accountable mainly to the Secretary of State for Health and took on responsibilities from a range of other organisations (ibid). PHE was responsible for: (1) assisting the public to safeguard and improve their health, (2) safeguarding the nation's health and preparing for public health emergencies, (3) distributing information and knowledge with local authorities and the NHS, and (4) carrying out research and gathering data.

Health crisis preparedness plans

A number of pandemic plans existed before the COVID-19 pandemic. They are as follows:

1. UK Influenza Contingency Plan (2005)
2. National Framework for responding to an influenza pandemic (2007)
3. UK Influenza Pandemic Preparedness Strategy (2011)

England had previously engaged in pandemic exercises to evaluate the UK's preparedness and response to a flu pandemic. The exercises focusing on a flu pandemic include Cygnet and Cygnus (2016) and Pica (2018). These plans were never published and were not disclosed to parliament.

Crisis management implementation

The UK was slow to introduce public health measures compared to other EU countries. At the beginning of 2020, the UK healthcare system was going through a decade of underfunding (ibid). During this time, the NHS was facing heightening demand, as well as shortages of bed capacity. Such struggles were intensified by unaddressed workforce problems, "especially in areas of high socioeconomic disadvantage" (ibid). These issues meant that the NHS stepped into the COVID-19 pandemic in a more strenuous position compared to other health systems in similar countries (ibid).

In terms of how the government/people in charge/authorities responsible for crisis management reacted to the COVID-19 pandemic, the nursing home scandals that occurred during the initial stages of the pandemic are worth raising. According to a March 2023 BBC publication, former Health Secretary Matt Hancock ignored March 2020 advice from Chief Medical Officer Chris Whitty stating that everyone entering care homes should be tested. Hancock initially accepted the advice but later on changed his mind and resorted to testing of people being moved to care homes from hospitals. Despite the relaxed reaction during the initial stages of the pandemic (see former Prime Minister Boris Johnson's first televised March 2020 speech to the UK nation), relevant public health measures were put in place to minimise COVID-19 infection. Examples of measures include: (1) Switching from face-to-face interactions to telephone/video calls, (2) PPE wearing becoming a standard practice by April 2020, (3) Most of England setting up dedicated 'primary care COVID-19 hubs,' and (4) Implementation of COVID-19 home visiting services.

Regarding documents that were followed during this timeframe, and especially when the pandemic first broke out, a NHS Confederation publication revealed that the UK did not possess the necessary pandemic planning or resilience abilities for COVID-19. According to a British Medical Association report, suitable planning exercises for COVID-19-type viruses had little influence on the broader pandemic preparedness policy, and recommendations were not followed (ibid).

From a public health perspective, COVID-19 responsibility included the work of former Health Secretary Matt Hancock. Barriers that emerged in terms of implementation of what was planned:

1. **NHS Contact Tracing App:** Initially, England's planned contact tracing app was centralised. By having a centralised system, the app witnessed a number of issues. With the centralised app, insufficient transparency, especially the limited data about the first Isle of Wight trial, resulted in suspicion and distrust. Referring back to D5.5, the results of the trial were that the app only acknowledged 4% of Apple phones and 75% of Google Android devices. After careful consideration, England moved to a decentralised system (ibid).
2. **NHS Test and Trace (NHSTT):** Performance issues involving contact tracing, provision of testing and adherence to isolation guidance.
3. **Vaccination:** The COVID-19 vaccination witnessed a number of issues such as delays in vaccinating specific groups of society. This includes the aim of vaccinating the majority of 12-

to 15- year-olds by late October 2021. The School Age Immunisation Services were blamed for the slow rollout. Other issues concerned wastage of vaccines (ibid).

Crisis management changes over time and the drivers of change

With regard to changes to the public health system, the afore-mentioned PHE became the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) on 1 October 2021. At the time of reporting, it was announced that UKHSA would function as a fundamental part of the public health system and the national security infrastructure to combat COVID-19 and future threats locally, nationally, and globally.”

In terms of changes to response, the initial course of action was the adoption of ‘herd immunity’. England followed a herd immunity-type approach when responding to the COVID-19 pandemic. Following simulations carried out by the Imperial College COVID-19 response team, however, the UK eventually introduced social distancing measures. The simulations carried out demonstrated how severely hospitals would be overwhelmed (ibid).

The crisis response in practice

With regard to structural change/change of responsibilities, it is worth noting that Matt Hancock stepped down as the Health Secretary on 27 June 2021.¹⁹ The decision to resign was due to breaching social distancing guidance (ibid). In terms of the occurrence of multiple crises, two events are worth shedding light on. The first event concerns Brexit. At the time of reporting, a 2020 briefing by Nuffield Trust stressed that poor funding for public health and social care contributed towards restrictions in the UK’s capability to address COVID-19 during the first wave. Because of Brexit, leaving the single market would have meant “slower growth, making addressing these more difficult.” The second event concerns the War in Ukraine. Regarding positive developments in the UK, the UK became the first country in the world to authorise the administration of Pfizer/BioNTech’s COVID-19 vaccine. In terms of solutions that made measures obsolete, people in the UK were given more freedoms once they were vaccinated. For example, because of the vaccine rollout in the UK, the Government was able to mitigate restrictions in England through the first half of 2021.²² With a focus on issues concerning data collection, January 2022 reporting by the Office for National Statistics on the number of COVID-19 deaths in England and Wales had been criticised and labelled as both “factually incorrect and highly misleading.” According to author James Tucker, circa 9 out of 10 deaths involving COVID-19 have been linked to COVID-19. Tucker, at the time of reporting, explained the correct number of deaths would have been around 140,000 (ibid).

TRI have conducted interviews with two PHDMs. In an attempt to finalise the recruitment of the desired target audience, TRI approached relevant interviewees from February-March 2023. Unfortunately, TRI were not successful with the second round of interview invitations, due to lack of responses from contacts. The following data presented below will therefore only concern the two interview findings we have.

With regard to the interview conducted with the Director of Public Health, successes observed include strengthened collaboration with relevant bodies. This includes collaboration with health services, education and schools, local volunteers, and the media. Commenting on all the different collaborations the Director’s organisation engaged in, the interviewee said:

“the organisation strengthened relationships, built trust, and put a strong emphasis on transparency”.

A second interview with an Assistant Director of Public Health pointed out issues relating to protecting the most vulnerable during the pandemic. According to the interviewee, the national government did not do this well. Priorities were shifted elsewhere, and specific vulnerable groups were left out in terms of support. As stated by the interviewee, *“In the beginning, nationally there was a huge emphasis on hospital treatment systems but not enough focus on residence in care homes or what has to be done to our children that cannot go to school, not all people have a laptop or can use an internet hotspot. I cannot speak for the national government, but I am in the position to say that if we knew at that time what we know now we could have done better.”*

Regarding lessons learnt provided by the Assistant Director of Public Health, the following information is relevant. Focusing on public trust, the interviewee explained that the public were underestimated within the context of COVID-19. Furthermore, the interviewee stressed that trust would have been heightened during the pandemic had information being disclosed been honest and genuine. In their own words, the interviewee commented:

“Don’t underestimate the public. The public can learn, we all have learned, but let’s recognise that the public are mainly growing adults and responsible people. So don’t make promises that you cannot keep. The public will trust you and be more tolerant if you say you don’t know the things that you really don’t know but repeating that you know something that you don’t know makes people picking up other kind of messages.”

With regard to lessons learnt by the Director of Health, the interviewee commented that at a government level, it was difficult to assist vulnerable people. In their own words, the interviewee said:

“Other than shielding people, the national government tried to manage things centrally, but along the time it realised it was better to provide money at the government level. This has been a lesson learnt from the UK government, certainly for England where there is too much population to be managed”.

The public reaction to the crisis management

One example of public reactions to COVID-19 crisis management concerns the topic of pandemic preparedness. Looking back at D5.5, on October 2020, a doctor named Moosa Qureshi, who organised a campaign for transparency into NHS preparedness for a pandemic said: *“Disgracefully, the Government covered up Exercise Alice – a coronavirus exercise which predicted the importance of isolating patients, contact tracing, PPE provision, trained personnel and adequate NHS beds.”*

Another example of public reactions to crisis management concerns the outbreak of COVID-19 protests. With a focus on protests that erupted in 2021, people became critical of the government’s response to the pandemic. The eruption of protests came during a time when people started to worry about the risk of new waves of infections.

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

In the beginning of the pandemic, a number of vulnerabilities were acknowledged and addressed by the public health system. In one COVINFORM interview with a Public Health Director, the interviewee explained that the first vulnerable group pre-COVID-19 concerns individuals who were receiving social care and healthcare support. In their own words, the interviewee said: *“the organisation had to think*

about how to provide them with support (e.g., with food and medicines). The Public Health Director added that other groups recognised as vulnerable were groups vulnerable to high risk of mortality from COVID-19 (obese, ethnic groups, ethnic communities). As mentioned by the Public Health Director, this *“required engagement with communities, also to avoid stigmatisation and stereotypes.”* As expected, vulnerabilities did change over time. During the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and first lockdown up until mass vaccination roll-out, new vulnerable groups identified and accounted for during this time frame include: (1) Vulnerable in UK: 70+, <70 with health conditions, and pregnant women, (2) 2.2 million told to shield at home for 12 weeks from March 2020, (3) Identified through health records and COVID-19 risk assessments, (4) Care home workers, whom were considered twice as likely to die, and (5) Ethnic minority groups, whom were considered to have COVID-19 and severe outcomes.

As stated in the interview with the Public Health Director, another group considered to be vulnerable were people vulnerable due to restrictions in everyday life because of isolation and the collapse of social networks. Indeed, this includes people with mental health issues and the so-called *“just-about-coping people.”* Simply put, these people refer to those who are just about able to pay their bills and lost their job or went on furlough during the pandemic.

With a focus on vulnerabilities identified during vaccination rollout and the emergence of new COVID-19-related variants, particular attention was paid to vaccinating those most vulnerable to the virus. As mentioned in a December 2022 press release, the NHS began encouraging the most vulnerable people to COVID-19 to get vaccinated for winter (ibid). People considered to be vulnerable by the Joint Committee on Vaccination and Immunisation (JCVI) and encouraged to get the booster were pregnant women, people who have a learning disability or serious mental illness, or another condition which makes them eligible, such as blood cancer, diabetes, epilepsy and asthma, among additional chronic conditions stated in the Green Book (ibid).

During the early stages of the pandemic, support to vulnerable groups was given by the Community Champions Scheme. Particular support was given to communities at greater risk of COVID-19, including disabled people, BAME communities and the elderly, faith groups and hard-to-reach communities. Also known as the health champions, the scheme made sure that community members who were volunteering would help address health inequalities, *“both in the context of short-term emergency response and longer-term health promotion and prevention.”* Support to vulnerable groups mainly came in the form of recognising barriers to obtaining information and providing adjusted support for local people. At the time, support looked like phone calls for people who were excluded digitally, focused helplines, and linking to GP surgeries (ibid). As of 25 January 2021, funding was aimed at areas with plans to reach groups such as older people, disabled people, and people from ethnic minority backgrounds who, at the time of writing, were more likely to suffer long-term impacts and poor outcomes from COVID-19. The 60 councils developed their own plan to strengthen communications with such groups including helplines, school programmes, workplace engagement, phoning those in at-risk groups as well as training sessions to assist people provide information and advice. Those working in public health also assisted with communications by reducing costs for services, providing telemedicine services, and accessing vaccines without needing to show citizenship.

A few examples of how public health measures affected vulnerable groups/created new vulnerabilities include: (1) Guidance to stay indoors has contributed towards heightened loneliness and isolation. The clinically extremely vulnerable (CEV) in particular have been said to have witnessed heightened health anxiety due to their higher chances of infection and serious illness, (2) CEV groups were also impacted by orders to shield. Not being able to work contributed towards heightened stress because of reduced

earnings, (3) Lockdowns contributed towards the escalation of domestic abuse. New vulnerabilities that followed included barriers to accessing support, including “cancelled” services and missed opportunities to intervene during interactions in lockdown with frontline workers, heightened feelings of fear, isolation, and loss of control, especially during the early stages of the pandemic from the combination of abuse and pandemic-related changes to daily life, and (4) Loneliness from lockdowns which limited social contact. Those identified to be vulnerable from loneliness included the youth and those already experiencing mental health symptoms (ibid).

3.10 Wales

Public health system, main actors and health crisis preparedness plans

The basic model of the Welsh healthcare system can be characterised as the so-called Beveridge or national healthcare model, based on universal healthcare coverage for all citizens provided by the Government (Kulesher & Forrestal, 2014). This national healthcare model is funded through taxation with a small proportion raised through national insurance contributions, and the Government has ownership of most of the delivery of health services (ibid.). Since the devolution of Wales in 1999, the country is responsible for healthcare provision and the National Health Service (NHS Wales) takes responsibility for health services to the population through seven Local Health Boards supported by three specialist NHS trusts (Longley et al., 2012). Healthcare is therefore primarily provided through the publicly funded NHS Wales for all in Wales, although the private sector also provides healthcare (Yar et al., 2006). Public Health Wales is the national public health agency in Wales and is one of the public bodies that forms part of the Welsh NHS. One of its roles is to protect the public from infection and to provide advice on epidemiology (the incidence and prevalence of disease). Although operationally independent of the Welsh Government, it acts at the Welsh Government’s direction.

The Welsh pre-pandemic preparedness strategy is aligned to the overarching UK-wide strategy. The main Welsh document that resembles a pandemic response plan or strategy is the *Wales Framework for Managing Infectious Disease Emergencies 2005*. It “sets out national arrangements for managing major infectious disease emergencies, including national coordination, operational responsibilities of NHS organisations and the role of partner agencies” (Welsh Government 2007). Wales also has a more pandemic-specific response plan; the *2007 Pandemic Influenza Guidance Planning* was established before the 2009 influenza pandemic. For emergencies in general, Wales has the *Pan-Wales Response Plan*, that entails the “command, control and coordination urgent response structure for national emergencies and includes activation levels and multi-agency responsibilities” (Welsh Government, 2021).

Crisis management implementation, and its changes over time

In planning for the COVID-19 pandemic, Wales was initially aligned with the UK-wide pandemic response and officials took seat in the COBR (Cabinet Office Briefing Rooms) meetings and was updated by the UK-wide Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE). SAGE is led by the UK government chief scientific adviser (GCSA), Sir Patrick Vallance, and the chief medical officer (CMO), Chris Whitty. SAGE is an ad hoc committee that brings together government scientists and officials with external experts. On March 18, 2020, Wales initiated its own health protection regulations. In Wales, the Coronavirus Restrictions were approved by the Welsh Parliament on March 25th, giving Wales the power to manage the pandemic independently of the other British nations. Documents followed by

the decision makers and authorities entailed assessment of the efficacy of the pandemic measures in place and need for adjustment. These were daily, weekly, and demand-based briefing and advice documents (Welsh Government, no date a) and impact assessment documents (Welsh Government, no date b). The collections that were not internal are mostly (still) available on the Welsh Government website. Later on in the pandemic, these documents were published with a lower frequency.

In addition to the UK-wide SAGE group, Wales created a Technical Advisory Cell (TAC) and a Technical Advisory Group (TAG) to support SAGE in advising the Welsh Government and Public Health Wales. TAG – SAGE experts, alongside the Chief Scientific Adviser for Health (Rob Orford), Chief Medical Advisor (Frank Atherton) and Chief Nursing Officer (Jean White followed-up by Sue Tranka) met three times a week to discuss the progress of the pandemic. TAG-SAGE experts inform the ministers, which in turn present changes to the regulations to the Welsh Cabinet for consideration. The Cabinet makes the final decision which is communicated to the ministers.

The Technical Advisory Cell had multiple sub-devised Cells – in particular the ‘Guidance Cell’, ‘Telephone Cell’, and ‘Enclosed Settings Cell’ – that consisted of people who had been working in different parts of Public Health Wales. One interviewee who worked as a senior public health practitioner at Public Health Wales during the pandemic explained that she used to work in health protection (e.g. smoking cessation). She worked for the ‘Guidance Cell’, in which, like her colleagues, she used her network and communication skills to advise organisations, such as care homes and community groups, about pandemic advice from the Welsh Government and how it applied to their situation in practice. She describes the public health response procedures having changed from beginning of the pandemic until January 2022:

“That information [from the Welsh Government] would reach us was never at the pace at which it was televised or announced. So, you know, as it progressed, obviously, we're now in a place, which is very different to the first wave, where there is more tactical input, there's more scientific input from the bodies. And that that process is very, it's very clear now. Whereas in those early, you know, months, quarter, it was very much, you know, they've announced something, what does this mean? What is our public health response going to be to this? Because we are only an advisor and organisation. We don't create any clinical advice that's on behalf of the NHS or Welsh Government.”

The collaborative process between the Welsh Government and its scientific committees and leaders with Public Health Wales and other health institutions seemed to have improved strongly. During the early pandemic days, the interviewee mentioned that she and her colleagues needed to check the website WalesOnline for news from the Welsh Government that they hadn't received before it was televised. A BBC journalist interviewed for WP7 corroborated this by saying that Welsh government staff would give them information just a couple of hours before the press conferences at the start of the pandemic. Given the confusion with pandemic measures being published with speed as the highest priority, a lesson learned seems to have been the recognition that cross-organisational agreement on the measures is more important than the speed of the announcements of public health measures.

In preparedness strategies in Wales, vaccination had not been considered in particularly thorough ways because they anticipated an Influenza pandemic. As Influenza vaccines are relatively easily adaptable, vaccines were considered to be more easily and more widely available in the preparedness plans than the COVID19 vaccines ended up being. Vaccination in the preparedness plans was thus not considered a special or particularly important pandemic measure. Since its inception in Winter 2020,

the development of the vaccination strategy incorporated ideas around equity, given that it was particularly concerned with ‘protecting the vulnerable’ in society. The decision maker who as a public health expert has been in charge of the vaccination plan explained how the programme started:

“I went fully over to the vaccination program in July (2020). And then we basically got together and established a program board with all of the health boards on it. And with a stakeholder group with many of the third sector partners on it, representing groups that would be interested in the vaccinations. And also a kind of the lens of the third sector for homelessness, asylum seekers and refugees, people whose mother tongue was not English, people who had a learning disability, or any disability. So it was a very broad ranging stakeholder group. And it was mainly so we'd have the board meeting for the planning over the summer, and then we'd have a stakeholder group to tell them what we're planning, we would do tabletop exercises with some of the different scenarios depending on what vaccine we thought might come through first, the logistics around that we'd have a number of subgroups underneath.”

This interviewee and another vaccine strategist interviewed for COVINFORM explained that when the first dose of the vaccines had been administered to the wider population, it became more clear what social groups had been less inclined to become vaccinated. Building on this new knowledge, the vaccine equity programme expanded its reach into newly identified ‘vulnerable’ social groups by adjusting the intensity of their efforts to address those groups. The lesson learned was to consider a changing dimension of vulnerability during the pandemic and be prepared for an increase in the categories and varieties of vulnerable groups. As such, new social groups were identified as vulnerable. In response to this widening of vulnerable groups, further kinds of health protection and types of vaccination were considered.

Vulnerabilities over time of the pandemic crisis

Vulnerability was a concept that was apparently used in particularly different ways depending on the line of work of the interviewee. Their understanding of the concept reflects in the pandemic management decisions. Medical staff and public health officials who worked on applied decision-making processes tended to consider vulnerability in a more strictly clinical way in the context of the pandemic with age and pre-existing conditions being of highest concern (UK Government 2020). The interviewee who was most senior of all interviewees; the Chief Nursing Officer for Wales (since August 2020) placed vulnerability at the heart of the pandemic response in Wales in the policy development concerning COVID-19:

“We think of people and then we think pathways don't really think oh, yeah, the cardiovascular groups, and then diabetic people. And we don't really stratify people in other groups. But I think in the pandemic, we started to stratify people for vulnerability, what were their social vulnerabilities? What were their mental health vulnerabilities? What were the physical vulnerabilities? And, and the policy started to be developed in that manner, which was the first time I've seen that sort of emergence of thinking, which is quite a maturation in a system, which I think what I assumed was mature in the sort of national scale thinking before, this was a different type of idea. And what it showed us in the population is that those with social deprivation, those that have the social determinants, that impact with social terms are not as positive and will impact health, people have far

more vulnerabilities and those vulnerabilities are not one, they will come in a mass. So if you're living in social deprivation, you know, your education abilities, or will be impacted your ability to have good social relationships and a stable home is impacted."

Her account suggests a strong social aspect in developing pandemic measures to address social difference and mitigate social impact of COVID-19. However, the interview with a senior health practitioner suggests that this social aspect and the attention to mental health, social deprivation, and education abilities amongst other social determinants of health had been more or less lost in the implementation of pandemic health policies. The senior health practitioner stated that the actual term 'vulnerability' was not part of their everyday vocabulary in deciding where to intensify testing efforts.

"Purely because when the vaccines did start to come out we found there is a bit more hesitation. (...) it wouldn't be a word that we've use 'vulnerability'; it's all about the data and where the cases are. So then might be certain areas at time that would have been more at risk. So again, it's that language, I think 'being more at risk to COVID' that had to have additional measures. So for example, at the time, Llanelli town was a hotspot in terms of the amount of cases that were coming through there. So it was a very much – that was a high risk area. So we had to target more of the workforce in terms of sending testing the mobile testing unit out there. So yeah, again, you know, in terms of the concept of vulnerability in a health protection world – it would just be, the language would be about risks in relation to COVID and the setting."

Similar to how vulnerability was considered in the broader pandemic measure development (see D4.7), also in public health spheres vulnerability seemed to have been a concept with which pandemic policy could be social policy in nature as well. However, in the implementation and operationalization the concept seemed to have diminished in its capacity to guide the pandemic response more holistically. Instead, it gave way to more measurable concepts such as 'risk', which affirm public health science interpretations of vulnerability as weakness and lack through the application of higher risk scores for higher levels of vulnerability. One lesson that can be learned from the employment of 'vulnerability' in policy entails the necessity of having expertise in the social dimensions of illness, health, and living in a society. In particular at lower operational levels such expertise is key to hold onto social sensitivities in the pandemic response; not just at the higher policy level. Addressing the capacity of vulnerability to include many aspects of life in pandemic times that are difficult to measure, there is clearly a need for accepting qualitative criteria of measuring impact of the pandemic in addition to quantitative ones.

4 Summary

In this deliverable, we reviewed several aspects of the COVID-19 impact on the healthcare system. In each of the ten case study countries, we emphasised on the healthcare system preparedness plans, the implementation of the response to the pandemic and the changes in the response over time, the challenges in the response, the public reaction to the implementation, and issues regarding the vulnerable groups in the different countries. Similarities were identified as well as unique characteristics in each of the countries.

Comparative definitions and operationalization of health vulnerabilities, including pre-existing conditions and comorbidities, mental health vulnerabilities, and social precarity

The impacts of COVID-19 on health vulnerabilities have been recognised and addressed in all of the case study countries. Across these countries, vulnerable groups have been identified based on age, pre-existing conditions, and immunocompromised status. The elderly, individuals with chronic illnesses, and those with weakened immune systems have consistently been recognised as higher-risk groups. Mental health vulnerabilities have also been acknowledged, with increased rates of depression, anxiety, and stress observed among various populations. Social precarity, encompassing factors such as poverty and inequality, has been recognised as exacerbating health vulnerabilities.

Besides these similarities, each country also has unique aspects in defining and operationalising health vulnerabilities. These variations highlight the diverse strategies employed to address health vulnerabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In Belgium, for example, there is a comprehensive recognition of both medically vulnerable and socially vulnerable groups. Medical vulnerability includes the elderly, individuals with chronic conditions, and those with decreased immunity or cancer. Social vulnerability encompasses occupational vulnerability, material and social deprivation, vulnerable families with children, and homelessness. Social vulnerability gained increased attention as the pandemic progressed.

Germany expanded its definition of health vulnerabilities over time, initially focusing on factors that increased the risk of severe COVID-19 progression, such as older age and pre-existing medical conditions. The definition later expanded to include front-line workers, individuals in precarious living or working situations, and those in critical infrastructure.

In Italy, the identification of health vulnerabilities involved recognising various groups at higher risk, including people with disabilities, psychiatric illnesses, rare diseases, and those living in fragile social conditions. Refugees and undocumented migrants faced higher risks due to poor living conditions and limited access to healthcare resources. The mental health vulnerabilities of healthcare workers and vulnerable individuals were acknowledged, exacerbating existing inequalities and impacting mental well-being.

Spain identified vulnerable groups such as children, the elderly, women, people with disabilities, immigrants in irregular administrative situations, and individuals with chronic illnesses or without regular income. Measures were implemented to support these groups, including strengthening social services and providing assistance to the homeless. The effectiveness of these measures is under evaluation.

Social and cultural factors have played a significant role in shaping public health responses to the COVID-19 pandemic across the case study countries. In several countries, initial public reactions to government measures showed support and perceived solidarity among the population. However, over time, satisfaction with measures decreased, and there was a rising perception of excessive measures and frustration among segments of the population. Trust in public institutions, such as parliament or government, varied and sometimes declined, influenced by factors such as party political preferences, educational background, and changes in communication.

Social and cultural factors influencing public health responses

The influence of social and cultural factors on public health responses is evident in the varying levels of public acceptance, compliance, and adherence to measures. Factors such as socioeconomic status, living conditions, access to resources, and cultural norms shape individuals' ability and willingness to comply with guidelines. Trust in public health authorities and the government, clear and consistent communication from trusted sources, and community solidarity also emerged as important factors in shaping public behaviour.

While there are similarities in their experiences, few countries also have unique aspects in how social and cultural factors have influenced their responses. Belgium faced criticism for initial policy responses that were seen as excluding vulnerable groups and relying heavily on digital platforms, thereby exacerbating disparities in access to resources. Germany witnessed a rise in the "lateral thinker" movement characterised by scepticism towards governmental measures, while the majority of healthcare workers displayed critical acceptance rather than outright rejection.

Italy experienced diverse responses across regions due to the decentralised nature of its health system, with variations in implementing national recommendations and decision-making. Public perception of healthcare workers shifted over time, initially praising them as heroes but facing blame and criticism during the second wave. Spain faced challenges related to low interpersonal trust, excessive politicisation, lack of coordination, and insufficient transparency and public participation.

Sweden's strategy of allowing controlled spread reflected cultural norms of conformity and emphasised recommendations rather than mandatory restrictions. The UK and Wales emphasised the role of social determinants of health, including social deprivation and stable housing, in developing pandemic measures and addressing the impact on vulnerable groups.

In Portugal, cultural practices, social norms, and public trust in health authorities shaped the population's response to the pandemic. Community solidarity, grassroots initiatives, and support systems played a significant role in addressing vulnerable individuals' needs. Greece experienced a decline in public trust influenced by the rapid dissemination of information, changes in guidelines, and misinformation from political figures and anti-vaccine individuals.

Institutional, legal, and data collection factors influencing public health responses

Across the case study countries various institutional, legal, and data collection factors have influenced public health responses to the COVID-19 pandemic. In many countries, the institutional framework includes government bodies responsible for public health, such as ministries of health or national health agencies, which have played a central role in coordinating and implementing pandemic responses. Legal frameworks and emergency measures were enacted to support public health measures, such as the declaration of a state of emergency or the implementation of specific acts or plans.

Data collection and surveillance systems were vital for monitoring the epidemiological situation and informing decision-making. Efforts were made to collect data on COVID-19 cases, hospitalisations, deaths, and other relevant indicators. Data analysis and modelling supported the assessment of the pandemic's evolution and guided the implementation of control measures.

While there are similarities in their experiences, each country also has unique aspects in how these factors have shaped their responses. Austria faced challenges due to an outdated epidemic act, which lacked definitions and regulations for handling infectious diseases. Belgium's complex government structure, with responsibilities shared between the federal level and regional entities, led to challenges in crisis management and coordination. Data collection, transparency, and ownership raised concerns, as pressure to release detailed figures had to be balanced with responsible interpretation.

Germany relied on existing legal foundations and enacted several acts to grant extraordinary powers to control the pandemic. The evaluation of legal foundations and measures provided critiques and

recommendations for future pandemic planning, emphasising the need to consider social determinants explicitly. Greece highlighted the central role of various institutions and authorities, such as the Ministry of Health, the National Public Health Organization, and the General Secretariat for Civil Protection, in decision-making and crisis management.

Italy's institutional response involved issuing decrees and circulars, with the Civil Protection Department and the Ministry of Health leading the coordination efforts. Portugal's response involved the Directorate-General of Health coordinating and implementing public health measures. Legal frameworks, emergency measures, and data collection systems were established to support the response, with data analysis and modelling informing decision-making.

Spain faced challenges in crisis management due to a limited legal and operational framework at the beginning of the pandemic. Efforts were made to develop tailored legal frameworks, streamline administrative procedures, and enhance coordination between different levels of government. Sweden's decentralised healthcare system posed challenges in coordinating responses between different regions and levels of government.

In the UK, the National Health Service played a central role in coordinating healthcare services, and government agencies provided guidance and regulations. Wales took a proactive role in managing the pandemic, with the Welsh government, scientific committees, and health institutions collaborating in decision-making. Data collection and analysis were important for assessing the efficacy of measures and informing responses.

Public health communication and epidemiological outcomes

Throughout the case study countries, public health communication has played a crucial role in managing the COVID-19 pandemic. Efforts have been made to disseminate accurate information, promote preventive measures, and address public concerns. Epidemiological outcomes have been influenced by the effectiveness of public health communication, adherence to preventive measures, and the implementation of containment strategies.

Across these countries, public health communication focused on raising awareness about COVID-19, promoting preventive measures such as mask usage and social distancing, and providing guidance to the population. Communication campaigns were implemented through various channels, including traditional media, websites, social media platforms, and community networks. Clear and timely communication played a vital role in educating the public, fostering behaviour change, and reducing the transmission of the virus.

While there are similarities in their experiences, each country also has unique aspects in their communication strategies and resulting epidemiological outcomes. Austria faced challenges in communication about vaccination, particularly regarding mandatory vaccination, with discrepancies between federal levels and institutions. Belgium emphasised tailored communication strategies for different audiences but faced criticism for the slow implementation of lockdown measures and initial neglect of specific groups' needs. Challenges remained in reaching non-native speakers and ensuring accurate interpretation of data.

Germany experienced a decline in public trust over time, along with fluctuations in mask-wearing compliance. Greece implemented frequent information campaigns, situational reports, and free rapid testing, along with social distancing measures and the suspension of high-density events and religious activities. In Italy, communication strategies varied across regions, contributing to public confusion and scepticism. Inconsistent messaging and differing regional implementation of guidelines resulted in variations in epidemiological outcomes.

Portugal's communication efforts involved collaboration between the government and the Directorate-General of Health, focusing on raising awareness, providing guidance, and disseminating information through various channels. Spain faced challenges due to a lack of predictability in the

institutional and political environment, resulting in decreased trust in the government. However, collaboration with the scientific community and international bodies improved evidence-based health measures.

Sweden's communication emphasised recommendations rather than mandatory restrictions, but concerns arose regarding the clarity and consistency of communication. In the UK, public health messaging evolved throughout the pandemic, adapting to changing conditions. Wales prioritised public health communication, providing regular updates and guidelines to inform and educate the public. Epidemiological outcomes were monitored closely to assess the effectiveness of interventions.

Impacts of COVID-19 on health care workers

The COVID-19 pandemic has had significant impacts on healthcare workers worldwide, and in the case study countries. Despite variations in healthcare systems and responses, several common themes emerge across these countries.

Healthcare workers in all the case study countries faced increased workloads, longer working hours, and heightened risks of exposure to the virus. They experienced physical and emotional stress, shortages of personal protective equipment, and challenges in managing the demands of COVID-19 patients. Burnout, mental health issues, and financial problems were prevalent among healthcare workers, highlighting the strain they faced during the pandemic. Delays in necessary operations and treatment were observed due to overloaded medical systems.

Belgium acknowledged healthcare workers as a vulnerable group and prioritised them for vaccination, recognizing their specific risks and challenges. Efforts were made to improve working conditions and provide incentives, although issues such as fatigue, illness, and delayed treatment persisted. In Greece, healthcare workers worked in high-risk environments and faced a higher risk of infection compared to the general population. The shortage of PPE and insufficient training during the early stages of the pandemic resulted in increased infections, severe cases, and deaths among healthcare workers. Additionally, the perception of healthcare workers shifted over time, from initial praise and gratitude to blame and criticism during the second wave.

In Spain, healthcare workers expressed a sense of abandonment, lack of guidance, and coordination issues with institutions. They shouldered the responsibility of making difficult decisions while politicians seemed to avoid accountability.

Despite these unique aspects, the similarities across countries reveal the shared experiences of healthcare workers worldwide. The increased workloads, risks of infection, mental health strain, and challenges in accessing necessary resources were common across the countries, reflecting the global impact of the pandemic on healthcare workers.

Overall, the impacts of COVID-19 on healthcare workers have been profound, and addressing their needs and concerns is crucial for their well-being and the effective management of the crisis.

References

4.2 Austria

- Baltaci, H. (2020). COVID-19 and migrants in Austria. Migration Policy Centre Blog. <https://blogs.eui.eu/migrationpolicycentre/covid-19-and-migrants-in-austria/>
- Holz Müller, I. (2021, September 30). *Faktencheck: Weniger Psychotherapieplätze als von Krankenkasse angekündigt*. <https://www.profil.at/faktiv/faktencheck-weniger-psychotherapieplaetze-als-von-krankenkasse-angekuendigt/401754048>
- Kittel, B., Kritzinger, S., Boomgaarden, H., Prainsack, B., Eberl, J.-M., Kalleitner, F., Lebernegg, N., Partheymüller, J., Plescia, C., Schiestl, D. W. and Schlogl, L. (2020). The Austrian Corona Panel Project: Monitoring individual and societal dynamics amidst the COVID-19 crisis. *European Political Science*, 1–14.
- Krejca, F., Partheymüller, J. & Kritzinher, S. (2022). Vertrauen in der Corona-Krise: Ein Update. Austrian Corona Panel Project, Blog 152. Available at <https://viecer.univie.ac.at/corona-blog/corona-blog-beitraege/blog-152-vertrauen-in-der-corona-krise-ein-update/>
- Kurzthaler, I., Kemmler, G., Holzner, B., & Hofer, A. (2021). Physician’s Burnout and the COVID-19 Pandemic—A Nationwide Cross-Sectional Study in Austria. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 12, 784131. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.784131>
- Leiblfinger, M., Prieler, V., Schwiter, K., Steiner, J., Benazha, A., & Lutz, H. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 Policy Responses on Live-In Care Workers in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland. *Journal of Long Term Care*, 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.31389/jltc.51>
- Leichsenring, K., Schmidt, A. E., & Staflinger, H. (2021). *Fractures in the Austrian Model of Long-Term Care: What are the Lessons from the First Wave of the COVID-19 Pandemic?* (Nr. 2021). 2021, Article 2021. <https://doi.org/10.31389/jltc.54>
- Lenger, M., Maget, A., Dalkner, N., Lang, J. N., Fellendorf, F. T., Ratzenhofer, M., Schönthaler, E., Fleischmann, E., Birner, A., Bengesser, S. A., Queissner, R., Platzer, M., Tmava-Berisha, A., Trojak, R. M., & Reininghaus, E. Z. (2023). Feeling Informed and Safe Are Important Factors in the Psychosomatic Health of Frontline Workers in the Health Sector during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Austria. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(2), 1533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20021533>
- OTS. (2021, Dezember). *Hilferuf aus Herzchirurgie und Intensivmedizin: Dringende Herzoperationen müssen verschoben werden*. OTS.at. https://www.ots.at/presseaussendung/OTS_20211202_OTS0011/hilferuf-aus-herzchirurgie-und-intensivmedizin-dringende-herzoperationen-muessen-verschoben-werden
- Partheymüller J., Plescia C., Kritzinger S. (2020). Solidarity and trust in times of corona: Austria in a comparative perspective. *Austrian Journal of Political Science* 49(2), 1–11.
- Pfabigan, J., Wosko, P., Pichler, B., Reitinger, E., & Pleschberger, S. (2022). Under reconstruction: The impact of COVID-19 policies on the lives and support networks of older people living alone. *International Journal of Care and Caring*, 6(1–2), 211–228. <https://doi.org/10.1332/239788221X16308602886127>
- Pollak, M., Kowarz, N. & Partheymüller, J. (2020). Chronologie zur Corona-Krise in Österreich - Teil 1: Vorgeschichte, der Weg in den Lockdown, die akute Phase und wirtschaftliche Folgen. Austrian Corona Panel Project, Blog 51. Available at <https://viecer.univie.ac.at/corona-blog/corona-blog-beitraege/blog51/>

- Pollak, M., Kowarz, N. & Partheymüller, J. (2021). Chronologie zur Corona-Krise in Österreich - Teil 5: Dritte Welle, regionale Lockdowns und Impffortschritt. Austrian Corona Panel Project, Blog 112. Available at <https://viecer.univie.ac.at/corona-blog/corona-blog-beitraege/blog112/>
- Reuter-Oppermann, M., Müller-Polyzou, R., Wirtz, H., & Georgiadis, A. (2020). Influence of the pandemic dissemination of COVID-19 on radiotherapy practice: A flash survey in Germany, Austria and Switzerland. *PLOS ONE*, 15(5), e0233330. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233330>
- Schmidt, A. E., Leichsenring, K., Staflinger, H., Litwin, C., & Bauer, A. (2020). *The impact of COVID-19 on users and providers of Long-Term Care services in Austria*. International Long-Term Care Policy Network. [LTCcovid.org](https://ltccovid.org)
- Siebenhofer, A., Huter, S., Avian, A., Mergenthal, K., Schaffler-Schaden, D., Spary-Kainz, U., Bachler, H., & Flamm, M. (2021). COVI-Prim survey: Challenges for Austrian and German general practitioners during initial phase of COVID-19. *PLOS ONE*, 16(6), e0251736. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0251736>
- Simon, J., Helter, T. M., White, R. G., Van Der Boor, C., & Łaszewska, A. (2021). Impacts of the Covid-19 lockdown and relevant vulnerabilities on capability well-being, mental health and social support: An Austrian survey study. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 314. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10351-5>
- Statistik Austria - Gesundheit (2021). Gesundheitsausgaben nach Leistungserbringern und Finanzierungsträgern. Statistik Austria. https://www.statistik.at/web_de/statistiken/menschen_und_gesellschaft/gesundheit/gesundheit_sausgaben/index.html
- Stolz, E., Mayerl, H., & Freidl, W. (2020). *The impact of COVID-19 restriction measures on loneliness among older adults in Austria* [Preprint]. Public and Global Health. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.09.08.20190397>
- The Social Employers (2022). The impact of COVID-19 on social services employers in Europe: A report from the Federation of European Social Employers. The Social Employers. <https://socialemmployers.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/The-Social-Employers-COVID19-report.pdf>
- Tsibulak I, Reiser E, Bogner G, *et al* (2020) Decrease in gynecological cancer diagnoses during the COVID-19 pandemic: an Austrian perspective *International Journal of Gynecologic Cancer* **30**:1667-1671.

4.3 Belgium

- Andries, S. (2020, December 23). *Zorgpersoneel krijgt premie en loonsverhoging*. De Standaard. https://www.standaard.be/cnt/dmf20201222_97963757
- Belgisch Raadgevend Comité voor Bio-ethiek. 2009. *Advies Nr. 48 van 30 Maart 2009 Betreffende Het Belgisch Operationeel Plan Influenzapandemie*. https://www.health.belgium.be/sites/default/files/uploads/fields/fpshealth_theme_file/advies_4_8_pandemie.pdf (June 3, 2022).
- Desson, Zachary, Emmi Weller, Peter McMeekin, and Mehdi Ammi. 2020. "An Analysis of the Policy Responses to the COVID-19 Pandemic in France, Belgium, and Canada." *Health Policy and Technology* 9(4): 430–46.
- De Kamer. 2021. *Bijzondere commissie belast met het onderzoek naar de aanpak van de COVID-19-epidemie door België*. Belgische Kamer van Volksvertegenwoordigers. <https://www.dekamer.be/flwb/pdf/55/1394/55K1394002.pdf>.

- ECDC. 2022. *Evaluation of the SARS-CoV-2 Testing Policy in Belgium from June to December 2021*. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. Technical report. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/covid-19-evaluation-SARS-CoV-2-testing-policy-Belgium-Feb-2022.pdf>.
- European Commission. (2019). *Joint Report on Health Care and Long-Term Care Systems and Fiscal Sustainability – Belgium Country Document 2019 Update* (Institutional Paper No. 105). Economic and financial affairs, Economic policy commission. https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/joint-report-health-care-and-long-term-care-systems-and-fiscal-sustainability-country-documents-2019-update_en
- Facon, P. (2020). *Strategie en prioriteiten met het oog op de versterking van het Belgische testbeleid door versterking van de testcapaciteit en de inclusie van nieuwe testtechnieken*. Regeringscommissariaat Corona. https://www.zorg-en-gezondheid.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/Testbeleid%20en%20antigeen_201105_NL.pdf
- FPS Social Security. (2020, August 12). *Monitoring van de sociale impact van de COVID-19-crisis in België*. Federale Overheidsdienst - Sociale Zekerheid. <https://socialsecurity.belgium.be/nl/sociaal-beleid-mee-vorm-geven/sociale-impact-covid-19>
- Gerkens, S., & Merkur, S. (2010). Belgium: Health system review. *Health Systems in Transition*, 12(5), 1–266, xxv.
- Hanover Comms. (2020, September 1). *Spotlight on the Belgian Healthcare System*. Hanover Communications. <https://www.hanovercomms.com/blog/spotlight-on-the-belgian-healthcare-system/>
- Kulesher, R. R., & Forrestal, E. E. (2014). International models of health systems financing. *Journal of Hospital Administration*, 3(4), 127. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jha.v3n4p127>
- Le Bacq, T. (2020, September 9). *Van het applaus worden de helden van de zorg niet rijk, van hun salaris ook niet: “We hopen dat dit ommekeer is.”* Nieuwsblad.be. https://www.nieuwsblad.be/cnt/dmf20200908_96431599
- OECD. (2019). *Belgium: Country Health Profile 2019*. <https://www.oecd.org/health/belgium-country-health-profile-2019-3bcb6b04-en.htm>
- Sciensano. 2021. *Thematisch Verslag: Vaccinatiegraad En Epidemiologische Impact van de COVID-19 Vaccinatiecampagne in België*. Brussels, Belgium. <https://covid-19.sciensano.be/nl/covid-19-epidemiologische-situatie>.
- VAZG. (2020). *Charter “Hoe veilig de draad opnemen als oudere in onze samenleving.”* Vlaams Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid / Agency for Care and Health Flanders. <https://www.zorg-en-gezondheid.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/Charter%20Hoe%20veilig%20de%20draad%20terug%20opnemen%20als%20oudere%20in%20onze%20samenleving.pdf>
- Task Force Kwetsbare Groepen. (2020a). *Communicatie kwetsbare groepen*. FPS Societal Integration / POD Maatschappelijke Integratie. <https://www.mi-is.be/nl/tools-ocmw/fiches-kwetsbare-groepen-eerste-golf>
- Task Force Vaccinatie. 2022. *Prioritaire Inenting van Personen Met Een Verhoogd Risico Tijdens de COVID-19 Pandemie in 2021 in België*. Regeringscommissariaat Corona. https://gcm.rmnet.be/clients/rmnet/content/medias/pdf/rapport_wg_strat_vax_nl_final.pdf
- UHasselt. (2020). *Corona in Limburg: Ervaringen uit de zorg- en welzijnssector*. Universiteit Hasselt. <https://www.uhasselt.be/corona-in-limburg>
- De Standaard. (2020, October 23). *‘Zonder nieuwe maatregelen, belanden we in een catastrofe.’* De Standaard. https://www.standaard.be/cnt/dmf20201022_97664042

Vandijck, D., & Annemans, L. (2009). Belgian Healthcare: Overview of the Health System and Financing. *ICU Management & Practice*, 9(4). <https://healthmanagement.org/c/icu/issuearticle/belgian-healthcare-overview-of-the-health-system-and-financing>

VAZG. (2020a). Charter “Hoe veilig de draad opnemen als oudere in onze samenleving.” Vlaams Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid / Agency for Care and Health Flanders. <https://www.zorg-en-gezondheid.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/Charter%20Hoe%20veilig%20de%20draad%20terug%20opnemen%20als%20oudere%20in%20onze%20samenleving.pdf>

4.4 Germany

BMG (2022, June 30). *Evaluation der Rechtsgrundlagen und Maßnahmen der Pandemiepolitik. Bericht des Sachverständigenausschusses nach §5 Abs. 9 IFSG.* https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/fileadmin/Dateien/3_Downloads/S/Sachverstaendigenausschuss/220630_Evaluationsbericht_IFSG_NEU.pdf.

Busse, Reinhard & Blümel, Miriam (2014): Germany: Health System Review. In: European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies. Health Systems in Transition. Vol.16. No.2. HiT Germany (who.int), Germany | Commonwealth Fund. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/255932/HiT-Germany.pdf.

Commission Services & Economic Policy Committee (2019). Germany: Health Care & Long-Term Care Systems. An excerpt from: European Commission (2019). Joint Report on Health Care and Long-Term Care Systems and Fiscal Sustainability. [joint-report_de_en.pdf](https://ec.europa.eu/economic_policy_committee/joint-report_de_en.pdf) (europa.eu).

OECD, World Health Organization (WHO) (2019): State of Health in the EU: Germany. Country Health Profile 2019. [36e21650-en.pdf](https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/health/state-of-health-in-the-eu-germany) (oecd-ilibrary.org).

RKI (2020a). SARS-CoV-2 Steckbrief zur Coronavirus-Krankheit-2019 (COVID-19) [Stand: 06.03.2020]. No longer available online.

RKI (2020b). *Vorbereitungen auf Maßnahmen in Deutschland Version 1.0: Ergänzung zum Nationalen Pandemieplan – COVID-19 – neuartige Coronaviruserkrankung.* Robert Koch Institut. https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/InfAZ/N/Neuartiges_Coronavirus/Ergaenzung_Pandemieplan_Covid.html

RKI. (2021). *Beschluss der STIKO zur 1. Aktualisierung der COVID-19-Impfempfehlung: Epidemiologisches Bulletin* (No. 2/2021). Robert Koch Institut. https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Infekt/EpidBull/Archiv/2021/02/Art_01.html

Universität Erfurt, Bernhard-Nocht-Institut für Tropenmedizin, Robert Koch Institut, Bundeszentrale für gesundheitliche Aufklärung, and Leibniz-Institut für Psychologie und Science Media Center. (2022, May 31). COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring COSMO Explorer. <https://projekte.uni-erfurt.de/cosmo2020/web/explorer/>

4.5 Greece

- OECD, European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies (2019). Greece: Country Health Profile 2019. State of Health in the EU. Paris, OECD/Brussels, European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, available at: <https://www.oecd.org/greece/greece-country-health-profile-2019-d87da56a-en.htm> [accessed May 30 2022].
- Economou C, Kaitelidou D, Karanikolos M, Maresso A. Greece: Health System Review. *Health Syst Transit*. 2017 Sep;19(5):1-166. PMID: 29972131. Available at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29972131/>.
- Demertzis K, Tsiotas D, Magafas L. Modeling and Forecasting the COVID-19 Temporal Spread in Greece: An Exploratory Approach based on Complex Network Defined Splines. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020 Jun 30;17(13):4693. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17134693. PMID: 32629791; PMCID: PMC7370089. Available at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32629791/>.
- Gountas, I., Hillas, G. and Souliotis, K. (2020), Act early, save lives: managing COVID-19 in Greece. *Public health*, 187, 136–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2020.08.016>.
- Greece, Ministry of Health, Ministerial Decision, “Establishment and essential parameters of the operation of the National COVID-19 Patient Registry [...]”, No 2649, O.G B’ 1390/14-4-2020, Art. 2, available in Greek at <https://www.enomothesia.gr/kat-yegeia/astheneies/upourgike-apophase-2649-2020-phek-1390b-14-4-2020.html>.
- Ministry of Health, National Public Health Organization (2020 January 28), Novel Coronavirus Sars-Cov-2 pandemic preparedness and response Action Plan, [Press Release] <https://www.moh.gov.gr/articles/ministry/grafeio-typoy/press-releases/6648> [accessed May 30 2022].
- iEferida. (March 23, 2020). Reuters-Coronavirus: Greece's reaction is faster compared to other European countries. Available at <https://www.iefimerida.gr/kosmos/reuters-koronoios-pio-grigori-i-antidراسi-tis-elladas-apo-alles-hores>.
- Kousi, T., Mitsi, L.C. and Simos, J. (2021), The Early Stage of COVID-19 Outbreak in Greece: A Review of the National Response and the Socioeconomic Impact, *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(1), 322. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18010322>.
- Farsalinos, K., Poulas, K., Kouretas, D., et al. (2021), Improved strategies to counter the COVID-19 pandemic: Lockdowns vs. primary and community healthcare, *Toxicology Reports*, 8, 1-9 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2020.12.001>.
- Ministry of Health (2021) National Public Health Action Plan 2021-2025, Section 3.2 COVID-19 Pandemic Response, p.p. 25-27, available at: <https://www.moh.gov.gr/articles/health/domes-kai-drases-gia-thn-yegeia/ethnika-sxedia-drashs/8776-ethniko-sxedio-drashs-gia-th-dhmosia-yegeia-2021-2025>.
- Fouda, A., Mahmoudi, N., Moy, N. and Paolucci, F. (2020) The COVID-19 pandemic in Greece, Iceland, New Zealand, and Singapore: Health policies and lessons learned, *Health Policy and Technology*, 9(4), 510–524 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.08.015>.
- Williams, G.A., B. Maier, C., Scarpetti, G., Giulio de Belvis, A., Fattore, G., Morsella, A., Pastorino, G., Poscia, A., Ricciardi, W and Silenzi, A. (2020), What strategies are countries using to expand health workforce surge capacity during the COVID-19 pandemic?. Available at <https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/publications/i/9999-12-31-eurohealth-health-systems-responses-to-covid-19-26-21>.
- Liakos Yiannis. (January 28, 2020). Corona virus: These are the reference hospitals for possible cases in Greece. *CNN*. Available at <https://www.cnn.gr/ellada/story/205559/koronaivos-ayta-einai-tanosokomeia-anaforas-gia-pithana-kroysmata-stin-ellada>.

- News 247. (February 28, 2020). Corona virus: Suspension of all educational trips abroad. Available at <https://www.news247.gr/koinonia/koronoios-anastoli-olon-ton-ekpaideytikon-ekdromon-sto-exoteriko.7592950.html>.
- Gazzetta. (March 14, 2020). Corona virus: Ban on flights to Italy from Greece. Available at <https://www.gazzetta.gr/plus/koinwnia/article/1456135/koronoios-apagoreysi-ptiseon-pros-italia-apo-ellada>.
- Kathimerini. (March 16, 2020). All religious functions are suspended by government decision. Available at <https://www.kathimerini.gr/politics/1069449/anastellontai-oles-oi-thriskeytikis-leitoyrgies-me-apofasi-tis-kyvernisis/>.
- Tornos News. (August 31, 2021). Greek PM Mitsotakis reshuffles his cabinet again replacing three ministers. Available at <https://www.tornosnews.gr/en/greek-news/politics/45262-greek-pm-mitsotakis-reshuffles-his-cabinet-again-replacing-three-ministers.html>.
- Economou C, Kaitelidou D., Konstantakopoulou O., Vildiridi L.V., The Health System Response Monitor (HSRM). (2021, February 28). *Workforce*. Retrieved March 3, 2021 from <https://www.covid19healthsystem.org/countries/greece/livinghit.aspx?Section=2.2%20Workforce&Type=Section>.
- Ta Nea. (January 26, 2021). Mutation: They are looking for when the new strain of the coronavirus came to Greece. Available at <https://www.tanea.gr/2021/01/26/world/metallaksi-psaxnoun-pote-irthe-stin-ellada-to-neo-stelexos-tou-koronaion/>.
- Papiris SA, Bouros D, Markopoulou K, et al. (2020, December 17). *Early COVID-19 Lockdown in Greece and IPF: A beneficial “impact” beyond any expectation*. *European Respiratory Journal*, vol 57 issue 2, Available at: <https://erj.ersjournals.com/content/erj/early/2020/11/19/13993003.03111-2020.full.pdf>.
- Hellenic Government. (2020, February 25). Legislative Content Act, 42 / A / 25.02.2020, Urgent measures to prevent and limit the spread of coronavirus. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://sfee.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/PNPfek42a25022020.pdf>.
- Hellenic Government (2020 January 5), Operation of COVID-19 Vaccination Session Management System and Web-platform, [News Bulletin] <https://covid19.gov.gr/leitourgia-tou-systimatos-kaitis-platformas-diacheirisis-synedrion-emvoliasmou-kata-tou-koronaion-sars-cov2> [accessed May 30 2022].
- Hellenic Government (2020 April 21) Establishment of 500 Mobile Health Units for home nursing care services, sampling of biological material and immediate rapid test execution of throughout the country [News bulletin] available at: <https://covid19.gov.gr/idikes-kinites-monades-ygias-komy-nosilefton-gia-tin-ypostirixi-ton-domon-tis-protovathmias-frontidas-ygias-pfy-tou-e-s-y> [accessed May 30 2022].
- Onmed.gr. (2020, February 27). *First case of coronavirus in Greece - The course of health of the 38-year-old in Thessaloniki*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://www.onmed.gr/yygeia-eidhseis/story/382180/proto-kroysma-koronaion-stin-ellada-38xroni-gynaika-sti-thessaloniki>.
- National Public Health Organization (EODY) (2020, March 23). *COVID-19 in Greece*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://eody.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/covid-gr-daily-report-20200323.pdf>.
- National Public Health Organization (EODY). (2020, February 3). *Instructions concerning preventative measures against COVID-19 infection dissemination in school units and institutions that offer educational services*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://eody.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/odigies-prolipsis-stis-scholikes-monades.pdf>.

- Ministry of Health, National Public Health Organization (2020 January 28), Novel Coronavirus Sars-Cov-2 pandemic preparedness and response Action Plan, [Press Release] <https://www.moh.gov.gr/articles/ministry/grafeio-typoy/press-releases/6648> [accessed May 30 2022].
- National Public Health Organization (EODY). (2020, February 3). *Instructions concerning preventative measures against COVID-19 infection dissemination in school units and institutions that offer educational services*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://eody.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/odigies-prolipsis-stis-scholikes-monades.pdf>.
- National Public Health Organization/NPHO (n.d.) Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), available at: <https://eody.gov.gr/en/covid-19> [accessed May 30 2022].
- National Public Health Organization/NPHO (n.d.) Emergency Operation Center, Office for Risk Assessment and Response to Public Health Threats, available at: <https://eody.gov.gr/ektakta-peristatika-dimosias-ygeias-k-epich> [accessed May 30 2022].
- National Public Health Organization/NPHO (n.d.), International Health Regulations, <https://eody.gov.gr/diethnis-ygeionomikos-kanonismos>.
- Huffington Post. (2020, February 2020). *19 questions and answers from EODY for coronavirus COVID-19*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from https://www.huffingtonpost.gr/entry/19-eroteseis-kai-apanteseis-apo-ton-eode-via-ton-koronoio-covid-19-gr-5e566227c5b6fc7a9e383fe2?utm_hp_ref=gr-koronoios.
- Huffington Post. (2020, February 26). *Thessaloniki: The first case of COVID-19 in Greece*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from https://www.huffingtonpost.gr/entry/thessalonike-to-proto-kroesma-koronaioe-sten-ellada-gr-5e565153c5b649ec433096bd?utm_hp_ref=gr-koronaiois.
- Huffington Post. (2020, March 11). *Infographic: The map and history of coronavirus cases in Greece*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://www.huffingtonpost.gr/entry/infographic-o-chartes-kai-to-istoriko-ton-kroesmaton-koronoioe-sten-ellada-gr-5e68f655c5b68d61645e4f42>.
- Huffington Post. (2020, February 26). *The surgical mask supply in Thessaloniki run out in a few days*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from https://www.huffingtonpost.gr/entry/exantlethekan-mesa-se-liya-24ora-oi-cheiroeryikes-maskes-ste-thessalonike-gr-5e565b40c5b6fc7a9e3831b0?utm_hp_ref=gr-koinonia.
- Mouchtouri, V.A., Agathagelidou, E., Kofonikolas, K., et al. (2020), Nationwide Survey in Greece about Knowledge, Risk Perceptions, and Preventive Behaviors for COVID-19 during the General Lockdown in April 2020. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(23), 8854 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph1723885>.
- Kanellopoulou, A., Koskeridis, F., Markozannes, G. et al.(2021), Awareness, knowledge and trust in the Greek authorities towards COVID-19 pandemic: results from the Epirus Health Study cohort, *BMC Public Health*, 21, 1125 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11193-x>.
- Gavana, M., Papageorgiou, D.I., Haidich, A.B., Kokkali, S., Talimtzi, P., Paganas, A., Andreou, M., Yakimova-Polyzou, V., Symintiridou, D. and Smyrnakis, E. (2022), Perceived risk and pandemic response awareness in low-capacity public primary health care in Greece, *Rural and Remote Health*, 22, 6985 <https://doi.org/10.22605/RRH6985>.
- TheToc. (n.d.) Phaedon Vovolis: Who is the denialist cardiologist who organized the gathering of anti-vaccinationists. Available at <https://www.thetoc.gr/koinwnia/article/faidon-bobolis-poi-os-einai-o-arnitis-kardiologos-pou-organose-ti-sugkentrosi-ton-antiemboliaston/>.
- Virginia Pietromarchi. (November 16, 2020). Protesters to defy gov't ban on Athens Polytechnic uprising march. *Al Jazeera*. Available at <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/11/16/greek-protests-coronavirus>.

- Kokkinidis, T. (2020, December 6), Why Greece was less effective in dealing with Covid's second wave, Greek Reporter <https://greekreporter.com/2020/12/06/why-greece-was-less-effective-in-dealing-with-covids-second-wave> [accessed 30 May 2022].
- Kitsantonis, N. (2021, March 3). *Protests and Vandalism Follow Hit Man's Hunger Strike*. New York Times. Retrieved March 24, 2021 from <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/03/03/world/hunger-strike-protests-greece.html>.
- Niki Katsiantonis. (January 23, 2022). In Greece, a String of Killings Pushes Domestic Abuse Into the Spotlight. *New York Times*. Available at <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/01/23/world/greece-domestic-violence-abuse.html>.
- CNN. (2021, March 17). *Coronavirus: The spread of Covid 19 in Greece with numbers (17/03)*. Retrieved March 24, 2021 from <https://www.cnn.gr/ellada/video/258581/koronoios-h-exaplosi-tis-covid-19-stin-ellada-me-arithmoys-17-03>.
- Protothema. (March 19, 2021). ND: 632 marches since the beginning of February - SYRIZA still calls for demonstrations. Available at <https://www.protothema.gr/politics/article/1106188/nd-632-poreies-apo-tis-arhes-fevrouariou-o-suriza-exakolouthei-na-kalei-se-diadiloseis/>.
- Skapinakis P, Bellos S, Oikonomou A, Dimitriadis G, Gkikas P, Perdikari E, Mavreas V. Depression and Its Relationship with Coping Strategies and Illness Perceptions during the COVID-19 Lockdown in Greece: A Cross-Sectional Survey of the Population. *Depress Res Treat*. 2020 Aug 26;2020:3158954. doi: 10.1155/2020/3158954. PMID: 32908697; PMCID: PMC7450302. Available at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32908697/>.
- Iefimerida. (2020, March 31). *Coronavirus: Municipalities in Athens take care of Greek Roma – Disinfections, supply of food and medicine*. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://www.iefimerida.gr/ellada/koronoios-merimna-dimon-gia-roma>.
- Carassava A. (2021, March 7). *Greece Sidelines Thousands of Asylum-Seekers in National Inoculation Drive*. VOA News. Retrieved March 3, 2021, from <https://www.voanews.com/covid-19-pandemic/greece-sidelines-thousands-asylum-seekers-national-inoculation-drive>.
- Stavros Chatzisyneonidis, Kitty Kioskli, An observational study of domestic violence in Greece during COVID-19 through police records: The profile of heinous crimes between nuclear and extended family relationships, *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, Volume 17, 2023, paad004, <https://doi.org/10.1093/police/paad004>.
- Chara Chioni-Chotouman. (November 30, 2020). Violence against women and lockdowns in Greece: available data and the situation during the second lockdown. European Law and Gender Action, University of Pisa, Department of Law. Available at <https://elan.jus.unipi.it/blog/violence-against-women-and-lockdowns-in-greece-available-data-and-the-situation-during-the-second-lockdown/>.
- Maria Spiliopoulou and Valentini Anagnostopoulou. (November 25, 2020). Roundup: Reports of domestic violence in Greece spike during COVID-19 lockdown. *Xinhua*. Available at http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2020-11/25/c_139540825.htm.
- Greek Travel Pages News (GTP). (n.d.) Covid-19 Government Measures. Available at <https://news.gtp.gr/monitoring-covid-19-impact-travel-industry/covid-19-government-measures/page/23/>.
- European Commission. (June 7, 2019). Joint Report on Health Care and Long-Term Care Systems and Fiscal Sustainability – Country Documents 2019 Update. Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs. Institutional Paper 105. Available at https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/joint-report-health-care-and-long-term-care-systems-and-fiscal-sustainability-country-documents-2019_en.

Demertzis K, Tsiotas D, Magafas L. Modeling and Forecasting the COVID-19 Temporal Spread in Greece: An Exploratory Approach based on Complex Network Defined Splines. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020 Jun 30;17(13):4693. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17134693. PMID: 32629791; PMCID: PMC7370089. Available at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32629791/>.

National Public Health Organization (EODY). (August 31, 2020). Daily report of epidemiological surveillance of infection by the novel coronavirus (COVID-19). Available at <https://eody.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/covid-gr-daily-report-20200831.pdf>

4.6 Italy

Armocida B., Formenti B., Ussai S., Palestra F., Missoni E., *The Italian health system and the COVID-19 challenge*, (2020). *The Lancet – Public Health* [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(20\)30074-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(20)30074-8)

Anelli, F., Leoni, G., Monaco, R., Nume, C., Rossi, R. C., Marinoni, G., Spata, G., De Giorgi, D., Peccarisi, L., Miani, A., Burgio, E., Gentile, I., Colao, A., Triassi, M., & Piscitelli, P. (2020). *Italian doctors call for protecting healthcare workers and boosting community surveillance during covid-19 outbreak*. *BMJ* (Clinical research ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1254>

Berardi, C., Antonini, M., Genie, M. G., Cotugno, G., Lanteri, A., Melia, A., Paolucci, F. (2020). *The COVID-19 pandemic in Italy: Policy and technology impact on health and non-health outcomes*. *Health policy and technology*, pp. 454–487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.08.019>

Boffetta, P., Violante, F., Durando, P., et al. (2021). *Determinants of SARS-CoV-2 infection in Italian healthcare workers: a multicenter study*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-85215-4>

Bosa, I., Castelli, A., Castelli, M., Ciani, O., Compagni, A., Galizzi, M., Garofano, M., Ghislandi, S., Giannoni, M., Marini, G., Vainieri, *Response to COVID-19: Was Italy (un)prepared?* (2021). *Health Economics, Policy and Law*, pp. 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1744133121000141>

Conti, F., Di Tanna, G. L., Zanus, G., & Grossi, U. (2020). *Impact of COVID-19 Outbreak on Healthcare Workers in Italy: Results from a National E-Survey*. *Journal of community health*, pp. 675–683. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10900-020-00845-5>

De Girolamo G., Cerveri G., Clerici M. et al (2020) *Mental Health in the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Emergency—The Italian Response*. *JAMA Psychiatry*. doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2020.1276

Ferre, F., de Belvis, A. G., Valerio, L., Longhi, S., Lazzari, A., Fattore, G., Ricciardi, W., & Maresso, A. (2014). *Italy: health system review*. *Health systems in transition*, pp. 1–168. PMID

Kurotschka, P. K., Serafini, A., Demontis, M., Serafini, A., Mereu, A., Moro, M. F., Carta, M. G., Ghiretto, L. (2021). *General Practitioners; Experiences During the First Phase of the COVID-19 Pandemic in Italy: A Critical Incident Technique Study*. *Frontiers in public health*.

Lombardo, F. L., Salvi, E., Lacorte, E., Piscopo, P., Mayer, F., Ancidoni, A., Remoli, G., Bellomo, G., Losito, G.; Ancona, F., Canevelli, M., Onder, G., Vanacore, N.; Italian National Institute of Health Nursing Home Study Group (2020). *Adverse Events in Italian Nursing Homes During the COVID-19 Epidemic: A National Survey*. *Frontiers in psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.578465>

Lasalvia, A., Amaddeo, F., Porru, S., Carta, A., Tardivo, S., Bovo, C., Ruggeri, M., & Bonetto, C. (2021). *Levels of burn-out among healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic and their*

associated factors: a cross-sectional study in a tertiary hospital of a highly burdened area of north-east Italy. BMJ open. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020->

Lasalvia, A., Bonetto, C., Porru, S., Carta, A., Tardivo, S., Bovo, C., Ruggeri, M., & Amaddeo, F. (2020). *Psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers in a highly burdened area of north-east Italy.* *Epidemiology and psychiatric sciences.* <https://doi.org/10.1017/S2045796020001158>

Martin-Delgado, J., Viteri, E., Mula, A., Serpa, P., Pacheco, G., Prada, D., Campos de Andrade Lourenção, D., Campos Pavan Baptista, P., Ramirez, G.; Mira, J. J. (2020). *Availability of personal protective equipment and diagnostic and treatment facilities for healthcare workers involved in COVID-19 care: A cross-sectional study in Brazil, Colombia, and Ecuador.* *PloSone.* <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0242185>

Modenese A., Gobba F.(2020). *Increased Risk of COVID-19-Related Deaths among General Practitioners in Italy.* MDPI – Healthcare. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare8020155>

Mugnai, G.; Bilato, C. (2020). *Covid-19 in Italy: Lesson from the Veneto Region.* *European journal of internal medicine*, pp. 161–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2020.05.039>

Nguyen, L. H., Drew, D. A., Joshi, A. D., Guo, C. G., Ma, W., Mehta, R. S., Sikavi, D. R., Lo, C. H., Kwon, S., Song, M., Mucci, L. A., Stampfer, M. J., Willett, W. C., Eliassen, A. H., Hart, J. E., Chavarro, J. E., Rich-Edwards, J. W., Davies, R., Capdevila, J., Lee, K. A., ... Chan, A. T. (2020). *Risk of COVID-19 among frontline healthcare workers and the general community: a prospective cohort study.* *medRxiv.* <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.29.20084111>

Pappa S, Ntella V, Giannakas T, Giannakoulis VG, Papoutsis E and Katsaounou P (2020) *Prevalence of depression, anxiety, and insomnia among healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic review and meta-analysis.* *Brain Behavior and Immunity*, pp. 901–907.

Pecoraro F., Clemente F., Luzi D. (2020). *The efficiency in the ordinary hospital bed management in Italy: An in-depth analysis of intensive care unit in the areas affected by COVID-19 before the outbreak* *Plos one Journal* <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239249>

Romagnani P., Gnone G., Guzzi F., Negrini S., Guastalla A., Annunziato F., Romagnani S. & De Palma R. (2020) *The COVID-19 infection: lessons from the Italian experience.* *Journal of Public Health Policy*

Torri, E., Sbrogiò, L. G., Rosa, E. D., Cinquetti, S., Francia, F., & Ferro, A. (2020). *Italian Public Health Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic: Case Report from the Field, Insights and Challenges for the Department of Prevention.* *International journal of environmental research and public health*, pp. 36-66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17103666>

Epicentro website:

<https://www.epicentro.iss.it/en/coronavirus/sars-cov-2-gender-differences-importance-sex-disaggregated-data>

Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 patients dying in Italy Report based on available data on March 1st, 2021

https://www.epicentro.iss.it/en/coronavirus/bollettino/Report-COVID-2019_1_march_2021.pdf

4.7 Portugal

- Antena Livre (2022, Fevereiro 26). Cronologia: Covid-19/Dois anos: Principais acontecimentos da pandemia em Portugal [Cronologia: Covid-19/Dois anos: Principais acontecimentos da pandemia em Portugal \(antenalivre.pt\)](https://antenalivre.pt)
- Borges, A., Gomes, M., & Ribeiro, M. T. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal: Lessons learned and future implications for health and social policies. *Health Policy*, 125(6), 714-719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2021.03.015>
- Clemente, A., Alves, C., & Chinita, M. J. (2021). COVID-19 in Portugal: Public health versus economic imperatives. *Health Policy and Technology*, 10(4), 490-493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2021.06.010>
- Conselho Nacional de Saúde (2020, Outubro). PORTUGAL E A RESPOSTA À COVID-19: A POSIÇÃO DO CONSELHO NACIONAL DE SAÚDE E O CONTRIBUTO DAS ENTIDADES QUE O CONSTITUEM. <https://www.cns.min-saude.pt/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Reflexao-do-CNS-quanto-a-resposta-a-pandemia-por-COVID-19.pdf>
- Conselho Nacional de Saúde (2022) A pandemia de COVID-19: Desafios para a saúde dos Portugueses. Lisboa: CNS, 2022 [Relatorio-CNS2022_web.pdf \(min-saude.pt\)](https://www.cns.min-saude.pt/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Relatorio-CNS2022_web.pdf)
- Directorate-General of Health. (2020). National Contingency Plan for SARS-CoV-2 Infection. Retrieved from <https://covid19.min-saude.pt/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Plano-de-Conting%C3%Aancia-Nacional-Novo-Coronav%C3%ADrus-COVID-19.pdf>
- DN. (2021, September 22). Portugal já atingiu a meta de 85% da população vacinada. DN. <https://www.dn.pt/sociedade/portugal-ja-atingiu-a-meta-de-85-da-populacao-vacinada-14202410.html>
- DN (2022, September 9). Manuel Pizarro substitui Marta Temido como ministro da Saúde. <https://www.dnoticias.pt/2022/9/9/327296-manuel-pizarro-substitui-marta-temido-como-ministro-da-saude/>
- Eurobarometer. (2020). Standard Eurobarometer 93: Public Opinion in the European Union. <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2337>
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. (2020). COVID-19 in Portugal. [https://covid19-country-overviews.ecdc.europa.eu/#4 Portugal](https://covid19-country-overviews.ecdc.europa.eu/#4_Portugal)
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. (2021). COVID-19 situation update for the EU/EEA and the UK. Retrieved from <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/cases-2019-ncov-eueea>
- European Commission. (2021). COVID-19 digital certificate. https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/coronavirus-response/safe-covid-19-vaccines-europeans/covid-19-digital-certificate_en
- Eurostat. (2021). Unemployment statistics. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Unemployment_statistics#Unemployment_rate_by_sex_and_age_-_annual_data
- Financial Times. (2021). Portugal's tourism-dependent economy struggles amid pandemic. Retrieved from <https://www.ft.com/content/2a86796e-6e0d-4a4b-92c5-9dd46c18917a>
- Governo de Portugal. (2020). Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 10-A/2020, de 13 de março. Diário da República, 2.ª série. <http://www.dre.pt/7gua4/1194610/1194646/1194686/1194706/1194726/1194736/1194766/11>

- SNS (2021a, February 5). Task Force. <https://www.sns.gov.pt/vacinacaocovid19/task-force/>
- SNS (2021b, January 28). Balanço do primeiro mês. https://www.sns.gov.pt/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Balanco_primeiroMes.pdf
- SNS (2021c, May 17). Grupos Prioritários. <https://www.sns.gov.pt/vacinacaocovid19/grupos-prioritarios/>
- The Portugal News. (2020). Hospitals at breaking point as COVID-19 cases continue to rise. Retrieved from <https://www.theportugalnews.com/news/2020-10-27/hospitals-at-breaking-point-as-covid-19-cases-continue-to-rise/56420>

4.8 Spain

- BOE. (2023) *Real Decreto 65/2023, de 7 de febrero, por el que se modifica la obligatoriedad del uso de mascarillas durante la situación de crisis ocasionada por la COVID-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2023/02/07/65/con>
- Fernando Bruna, Matilde Massó & Isabel Neira. (2020) *Does culture matter during a pandemic? An approach to the Spanish crisis of the COVID-19*, Revista Española de Sociología 2020, DOI: 10.22325/fes/res.2020.48.
- Carmen Navarro & Francisco Velasco. (2022) *From centralization to new ways of multi-level coordination: Spain's intergovernmental response to the COVID-19 pandemic*, Local Government Studies, 48:2, 191-210, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254511>
- El País. (2023) *Mascarillas en farmacias y centros sanitarios: ¿ha llegado el momento de levantar la última restricción de la pandemia?*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: <https://elpais.com/sociedad/2023-04-20/mascarillas-en-farmacias-y-centros-sanitarios-ha-llegado-el-momento-de-levantar-ultima-restriccion-de-la-pandemia.html>
- Gobierno de España (2022). *¿Cuándo me vacuno?*. Retrieved 28th April 2023, from: <https://www.vacunacovid.gob.es/preguntas-y-respuestas/cuando-me-vacuno>
- Juana María Morcillo Martínez. (2021) *Exclusión social, pandemia y políticas sociales en España: un análisis desde el Trabajo Social*, Trabajo Social 24 (1): 169-191, DOI: 10.15446/ts.v24n1.94719
- Javier Bernacer, Javier García-Manglano & Eduardo Camina. (2021) *Polarization of beliefs as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic: The case of Spain*, PLoS ONE 16(7), DOI: 10.1080/03003930.2022.2042683.
- Miguel Ángel Presno Linera. (2020) *Estado de Alarma por Coronavirus y Protección Jurídica de los Grupos Vulnerables*, RDP, Brasília, Volume 17, n. 94, 15-34
- Mikel Erkoreka & Josu Hernando-Pérez. (2022) *Decentralization: A hándicap in fighting the COVID-19 pandemic? The response of the regional governments in Spain*, Public Admin Dev. 2022; 1-12, DOI: 10.1002/pad.1988

Ministerio de Sanidad (2005). *National Influenza Preparedness and Response Plan*. Retrieved 28th April 2023, from: <https://www.sanidad.gob.es/ca/profesionales/saludPublica/docs/PlanGripeIngles.pdf>.

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020a) *Plan de respuesta temprana en un escenario de control de la pandemia por covid-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/COVID19_Plan_de_respuesta_temprana_escenario_control.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020b) *Coordinated response actions to control the transmission of COVID-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Actuaciones_respuesta_COVID-19_ENG.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020c) *Estrategia de vacunación frente a COVID-19 en España*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/prevPromocion/vacunaciones/covid19/Actualizaciones_Estrategia_Vacunacion/docs/COVID-19_EstrategiaVacunacion.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020d) *Procedimiento de actuación para los servicios de prevención de riesgos laborales frente a la exposición al SARS-CoV-2*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: <https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/PrevencionRRL COVID-19.pdf>

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020e) *Documento técnico de recomendaciones de actuación ante la crisis por COVID-19, para los gestores de servicios sociales de atención a personas sin hogar*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Recomendaciones_GESTORES_servicios_Ps_SIN_HOGAR_y_COVID-19.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020f) *Documento técnico de recomendaciones de actuación desde los servicios sociales de atención domiciliaria ante la crisis por COVID-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Recomendaciones_GESTORES_SAD_COVID-19_Ver_2.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020g) *Documento técnico de recomendaciones de actuación de los servicios sociales ante la crisis por COVID-19, en asentamientos segregados y barrios altamente vulnerables*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Recomendaciones_actuacion_COVID_asentamientos_y_barrios_vulnerables_27_3_2020.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020h) *Documento técnico de recomendaciones de actuación desde el sistema público de protección a la infancia y a la adolescencia ante la crisis por COVID-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: [https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Recomendaciones_PROTECCION_INFANCIA_31-3-2020_\(final\).pdf](https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Recomendaciones_PROTECCION_INFANCIA_31-3-2020_(final).pdf)

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020i) *Medidas de desescalada en centros penitenciarios en relación al COVID-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/COVID19_Desescalada_en_centros_penitenciarios.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2020j) *Health equity and covid-19, an analysis and proposals to tackle epidemiological vulnerability related to social inequities*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/HEALTH_EQUITY_AND_COVID-19.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2021a) *Evaluación del desempeño del sistema nacional de salud español frente a la pandemia COVID-19*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Evaluacion_Desempeno_SNS_Espanol_COVID-19.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2021b) *COVID-19 en distintos entornos y grupos de personas*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Evaluacion_Desempeno_SNS_Espanol_COVID-19.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2022a) *Estrategia de vigilancia y control frente a COVID-19 tras la fase aguda de la pandemia*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Nueva_estrategia_vigilancia_y_control.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2022b) *Comienza la campaña de vacunación de la segunda dosis de refuerzo para seguir protegiendo a la ciudadanía*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Nueva_estrategia_vigilancia_y_control.pdf

Ministerio de Sanidad. (2022c) *Actualización de la adaptación de las medidas de la estrategia de detección precoz, vigilancia y control de COVID-19 tras la fase aguda de la pandemia para los centros penitenciarios dependientes de la secretaría general de instituciones penitenciarias*. Retrieved 28rd April 2023, from: https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/Nueva_estrategia_vigilancia_y_control.pdf https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/documentos/COVID-19_Adaptacion_Estrategia_Vigilancia_Centros_Penitenciarios.pdf

Sebastián Royo. (2020) *Responding to COVID-19: The Case of Spain*, Eur Policy Anal. 2020; 6: 180-190, DOI: 10.1002/epa2.1099

4.9 Sweden

Statista (2023) *Politics and society. Coronairus (COVID-19) in the Nordics*. <https://www.statista.com/study/71530/coronavirus-covid-19-in-the-nordics/>, retrieved 11/05/2023.

SCB (2023). *Olika mått på överdödlighet ger liknande resultat för Sverige*. <https://www.scb.se/hitta-statistik/artiklar/2023/olika-matt-pa-overdodlighet-ger-liknande-resultat-for-sverige/>, retrieved 11/05/2023.

Folkhälsomyndigheten (2023). *Statistik för vaccination mot covid-19*. <https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/folkhalsorapportering-statistik/statistikdatabaser-och-visualisering/vaccinationsstatistik/statistik-for-vaccination-mot-covid-19/>, retrieved 11/05/2023.

Folkhälsomyndigheten (2023). *Pandemiberedskap. Hur samhällets aktörer kann förbereda sig – ett kunskapsstöd för beredskapsplanering*. Stockholm: Folkhälsomyndigheten.

Wockelberg, H., & Ahlbäck Öberg, S. (2016). *Ex Post Control of Mature State Agencies: Swedish Governments'*. Performance Information Demands over Time and Across Policy Sectors, Utrecht August 24–26, 2016.

Glenngård, A.H. (2017). Sweden. In E. Mossialos, & A. Djordjevic (Eds.). *International Profiles of Health Care Systems*, (147-150). The Commonwealth Fund. Retrieved from: <https://www.commonwealthfund.org/publications/fund-reports/2017/may/international-profiles-health-care-systems>.

European Commission (2019). *The Joint Report on Health Care and Long-Term Care: Sweden*. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/joint-report-health-care-and-long-term-care-systems-and-fiscal-sustainability-country-documents-2019-update_en.

Socialstyrelsen, *Beredskapsplanering för en pandemisk influensa*, december 2005.

Socialstyrelsen, *Beredskapsplanering för en pandemisk influensa*, december 2012, (rev. april 2015).

www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se.

SOU 2022:10, *Sverige under pandemin, Förutsättningar, vägval och utvärdering*, Volume 2, 2022.

SOU 2021:89. *Sverige under pandemin. Sjukvård och folkhälsa*. Volume 2, 2021.

Johansson, B., & Vigsø, O. (2021). Sweden: Lone Hero or Stubborn Outlier? In D. Lilleker, I. A. Coman, M. Gregor & E. Novelli (Eds.), *Political Communication and COVID-19. Governance and Rhetoric in Times of Crisis*. New York, NY: Routledge.

Pierre, J. (2020). Nudges against pandemics: Sweden's COVID-19 containment strategy in perspective. *Policy and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2020.178378>

Gerdin, Bengt (2021). *"Intensivvården i Sverige under covid-19-pandemin"*. Background report for SOU 2021:89 *Sverige under pandemin* [Sweden during the pandemic].

(<https://tt.omni.se/stefan-lofven-alla-maste-gora-mer/a/dl7a3w>).

(<https://www.aftonbladet.se/nyheter/a/bnkRBq/sverige-stanger-gransen-mot-danmark>).

"Vaccinet levererat enligt plan — Folkhälsomyndigheten". www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se. 26 december 2020. Retrieved 11/05/2023

Obminska, Ania (30 december 2020). "[Det här vet vi om vaccin mot covid-19](#)". *Ny Teknik*. Retrieved 11/05/2023.

Socialstyrelsen (2021) *Dödlighet i covid-19 har koppling till inkomstnivå*. <https://www.socialstyrelsen.se/aktuellt/dodlighet-i-covid-19-har-koppling-till-inkomstniva/>, retrieved 28/04/2023.

<https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/folkhalsorapportering-statistik/statistikdatabaser-och-visualisering/vaccinationsstatistik/statistik-for-vaccination-mot-covid-19/uppfoljning-av-vaccination/>. Retrieved 10/05/2023.

"[Restriktioner tas bort 9 februari](#)". *www.krisinformation.se*.

"[Sverige slopar inreseförbudet från alla länder](#)". *Sweden Abroad*.

Regeringskansliet, Regeringen och (15 september 2020). "[Besöksförbudet på äldreboenden upphör 1 oktober](#)". *Regeringskansliet*. Retrieved 11/05/2023.

Regeringskansliet, Regeringen och (3 mars 2022). "[Upphävande av covid-19-lagen och lagen om tillfälliga smittskyddsåtgärder på serveringsställen](#)". *Regeringskansliet*. Retrieved 11/05/2023.

Jönsson & Oscarsson (2021). *Den svenska coronastrategin. SOM-undersökningen om coronaviruset 2021*. Gothenburg: The SOM Institute.

Bengt Johansson, Jacob Sohlberg & Peter Esaiasson (2023). Institutional trust and crisis management in high-trust societies, in Bengt Johansson & Öyvind Ihlen, Jenny Lindholm & Mark Blach-ørsten (Eds.). *Communicating a pandemic*, pp 285-301. Gothenburg: Nordicaom.

Vårdfokus (2022). *Så hårt har pandemin drabbat vårdpersonalen*. <https://www.vardfokus.se/nyheter/sa-har-vardpersonalen-paverkats-av-pandemin/>. Retrieved 28/04/2023.

Folkhälsomyndigheten (2020). *Konsekvenser för personer 70 år och äldre av smittskyddsåtgärder mot covid-19*. <https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/livsvillkor-levnadsvanor/psykisk-halsa-och-suicidprevention/psykisk-halsa/covid-19-och-psykisk-halsa/>, retrieved 11/05/2023.

Riksrevisionen (2022). "Bristfällig beredskap av skyddsutrustning under pandemin", <https://www.riksrevisionen.se/om-riksrevisionen/kommunikation-och-media/nyhetsarkiv/2022-05-17-bristfallig-beredskap-av-skyddsutrustning-under-pandemin.html>. Retrieved 10/05/2023.

4.10 England

<https://dls.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/12/NHS-Responsibilities.pdf>

The NHS budget and how it has changed (2022) The King's Fund. Available at: <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/projects/nhs-in-a-nutshell/nhs-budget> (Accessed: April 25, 2023).

Public Health England (PHE) (2013) Policy Navigator. Available at: <https://navigator.health.org.uk/theme/public-health-england-phe#:~:text=supporting%20the%20public%20to%20protect,conducting%20research%20and%20collecting%20data> (Accessed: April 25, 2023).

http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/shared/bsp/hi/pdfs/19_10_05_bird_flu.pdf

<http://data.parliament.uk/DepositedPapers/Files/DEP2007-0135/DEP2007-0135.pdf>

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/213717/dh_131040.pdf

Dyer, C. (2021). Pandemic preparedness: UK government kept coronavirus modelling secret. *BMJ*. doi:10.1136/bmj.n1501

The COVID-19 inquiry: Learning the lessons. (2022, July 15). Retrieved April 20, 2023, from <https://www.nhsconfed.org/publications/covid-19-inquiry-learning-lessons>

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/52674073>

Walker, P. (2020, March 19). Boris Johnson: UK can turn tide of Coronavirus in 12 weeks. Retrieved April 25, 2023, from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/19/boris-johnson-uk-can-turn-tide-of-coronavirus-in-12-weeks#:~:text=Striking%20a%20notably%2C%20if%20cautiously,outlined%20%20that%20is%20vital.>

Majeed, A., Maile, E. J., & Bindman, A. B. (2020). The primary care response to covid-19 in England's National Health Service. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 113(6), 208-210. doi:10.1177/0141076820931452

The COVID-19 inquiry: Learning the lessons. (2022, July 15). Retrieved May 2, 2023, from <https://www.nhsconfed.org/publications/covid-19-inquiry-learning-lessons>

https://www.adalovelaceinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Ada-Lovelace-Institute_COVID-19_Contact_Tracing_Confidence-in-a-crisis-report-3.pdf

Fraser, C., & Briggs, A. (2021, June 3). What have we learned from a year of NHS Test and Trace? Retrieved April 20, 2023, from <https://www.health.org.uk/news-and-comment/blogs/what-have-we-learned-from-a-year-of-nhs-test-and-trace>

<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-health-security-agency-launches-with-a-relentless-focus-on-keeping-the-nation-safe>

Neuman, S. (2021, October 12). The U.K.'s early approach to the pandemic cost thousands of lives, a new report says. Retrieved April 25, 2023, from <https://www.npr.org/sections/coronavirus-live-updates/2021/10/12/1045219737/the-u-k-s-early-approach-to-pandemic-cost-thousands-of-lives-a-new-report-says>

Imperial College COVID-19 Response Team. (2020). *Report 9: Impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) to reduce COVID-19 mortality and healthcare demand* (p. 7). Imperial College London. Retrieved from <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/medicine/sph/ide/gida-fellowships/Imperial-College-COVID19-NPI-modelling-16-03-2020.pdf>

Newsdesk. (2021, December 15). Government warned of need for PPE stockpiles four years before pandemic. Retrieved April 20, 2023, from <https://www.jerseyeveningpost.com/morenews/uknews/2021/10/08/government-warned-of-need-for-ppe-stockpiles-four-years-before-pandemic/>

Person. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/uk/britons-turn-critical-governments-pandemic-response-2021-08-25/>

NHS encourages most vulnerable people to covid to get jabbed for winter. (2022, December 5). Retrieved April 26, 2023, from <https://www.england.nhs.uk/2022/12/nhs-encourages-most-vulnerable-people-to-covid-to-get-jabbed-for-winter/>

Community champions programme: Guidance and resources. (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2023, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/community-champions-programme-guidance-and-resources/community-champions-programme-guidance-and-resources>

Community champions to give covid-19 vaccine advice and boost take up. (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2023, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/community-champions-to-give-covid-19-vaccine-advice-and-boost-take-up>

<https://www.health.org.uk/sites/default/files/upload/publications/2021/NDL%20Briefing%20Assessing%20the%20impact%20of%20COVID-19%20on%20the%20clinically%20extremely%20vulnerable%20population%20201021.pdf>

McKinlay, A. R., Simon, Y., May, T., Fancourt, D., & Burton, A. (2023). How did UK social distancing restrictions affect the lives of women experiencing intimate partner violence during the covid-19 pandemic? A qualitative exploration of survivor views. *How Did UK Social Distancing Restrictions Affect the Lives of Women Experiencing Intimate Partner Violence during the COVID-19 Pandemic? A Qualitative Exploration of Survivor Views*. doi:10.31234/osf.io/d8rvk

Groarke, J., Berry, E., Graham-Wisener, L., McKenna-Plumley, P., McGlinchey, E., & Armour, C. (2020). Loneliness in the UK during the COVID-19 pandemic: Cross-sectional results from the COVID-19 psychological wellbeing study. *Loneliness in the UK during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Cross-sectional Results from the COVID-19 Psychological Wellbeing Study*. doi:10.31234/osf.io/j2pce

4.11 Wales

UK Government (2020) “Joint Committee on Vaccination and Immunisation: advice on priority groups for COVID-19 vaccination”. 30 December 2020 (<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/priority-groups-for-coronavirus-covid-19-vaccination-advice-from-the-jcvi-30-december-2020/joint-committee-on-vaccination-and-immunisation-advice-on-priority-groups-for-covid-19-vaccination-30-december-2020#vaccine-priority-groups-advice-on-30-december-2020>)

Welsh Government (no date a) “Strategy and evidence: coronavirus”, (<https://www.gov.wales/strategy-evidence-coronavirus>)

Welsh Government (no date b) “Impact assessments: coronavirus”, (<https://www.gov.wales/impact-assessments-coronavirus>)

Annex 1 Country Report Template

Annex 2 Country Frames

Annex 3 Cross-country Indicators

Annex 1 D5.7 Standardised Questionnaire for Country Reports

2.1.1. Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

1. **How is your government/the public health system/the civil society ecosystem/the crisis communication structured** (We want to know the structure: who is responsible, what kind of resources are available, etc.)?
2. **How was the response in your country planned** (we are looking for documents on how to deal with pandemic/crisis pre COVID)?

2.1.2. Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

3. **How was the crisis management implemented at the beginning of the pandemic?** (What happened when the pandemic hit? How did the government/ people in charge/authorities responsible for crisis management react? What documents did they follow? Who held the responsibility?)
 - 3.1. What were barriers to implementation of what was planned?
4. **How did these (referring to question 1-2) change over time** (2 points in time: 1.) COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures, 2.) Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022)
5. **What changes in crisis response occurred and why?** (We are looking for barriers, problems, structural change/change of responsibilities, occurrence of multiple crisis, positive developments, solutions that made measures obsolete, (lack of) support of measures, content with government. Please, address explicitly issues on data collection if available) (here also add insights from the Expert interviews)
6. **Reflections on pandemic management taking changes into consideration**
 - 6.1.1. Highlight issues or successes and talk about reflections based on the expert interview
 - 6.1.2. Lessons learned
7. **How did the public react to the crisis management and its changes?** (Discuss social and cultural factors that influenced the public health responses.)

2.1.3. Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

8. **What vulnerabilities were acknowledged and addressed by the government/the public health system/civil society organisations/in crisis communication in the beginning of the pandemic? How did this change over time (over T1 and T2), were there new vulnerable groups defined and acknowledged in the course of the pandemic? Please address explicitly the group of health care workers here and if they were acknowledge as a vulnerable group.**
9. **How was the response in relation to vulnerable groups implemented at the beginning of the pandemic? How were vulnerable groups supported? How did it change over time, especially if new vulnerable groups were acknowledged?**
10. **Describe briefly how did measures affect vulnerable groups or created new vulnerabilities? (e.g., lockdown affected domestic violence victims, people living in overcrowded conditions, chronically ill people, ageing people living alone etc.).**

ANNEX 2
WP5 country frames

The Ostrom model consists of five sub-systems below which we have operationalised as follows:

Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to in a country and to manage a (health) crisis

Governance Systems (GS) – describes the basic structure of how a country is governed in relation to a (health) crisis

Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis management in a country

Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the health crisis management and response

Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. Here it describes measures taken to manage the health crisis (e.g., lockdowns, testing, vaccination roll-out etc.).

AUSTRIA

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Health resources available: health expenditure 41,483 million euros or 10.4% of GDP (increase of 3.9% since 2004), 74.0 % of health expenditure is public health expenditure
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 531,8 in 2019
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 1037,34 in 2019
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 718,9 in 2019
- ICU beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 28.9 in 2018

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Age structure: 18.8% above 65, 66.5% between 20-65, 19.4% under 20 in 2019
- Gender structure: 50.8% female, 49.2% male in 2019
- Migrant population: 1.2% in 2019
- Population living in poverty: 13.3% in 2019
- Income inequality: 4.2 in 2019
- Housing density (overcrowding): 10% in 2019

Governance System (GS)

How is the governance system structured and who is responsible?

- The Parliament and Federal government: central role
- The Federal Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection (BMSGPK) – policy and legislation drafting, supervision and coordination of key actors
- The provinces/states: responsible for hospitals and other public health facilities
- Providers of statutory social security and the [Main Association of Austrian Social Security Organizations](#) as an umbrella organization
- Providers of healthcare services.
- Interest groups (e.g. social partners: employer and employee associations and professional interest groups): AGES, Oberste Sanitätsrat
- National Vaccination Committee: medical experts and national and state administrative representatives
- The Safety Board working group (part of Vaccination committee): vaccine safety with a focus on COVID-19

What preparedness plans already existed for health crises?

- Austrian epidemic act
- Influenza plan from 2006, not updated, focused only on Influenza

Vulnerable groups

- Vulnerable groups included in a generic way in the Influenza plan. No definition of who are the vulnerable, sensitive or predisposed

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Rudolf Anschober (HM) and der Ministries
- Sebastian Kurz (Chancellor)
- Karl Nehammer (IM)
- Gernot Blümel (FM)
- ORF
- ÖGK (Österreichische Gesundheitskrankenkasse)
- BVA
- BVAEB
- SVS

Who are the main target populations?

- General population

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

AUSTRIA T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system?

- Increase resources for health sector fighting COVID-19
- Increase in spending for hospitals
- Reorganization of hospitals: Covid units created
- Triage in front of hospitals
- Medical staff redirected to COVID-19 units
- AGES hotline focused on COVID-19
- Epidemiological Reporting System (EMS) used for COVID-19
- Testing: initially restricted testing, permanent, free, and easily accessible population wide testing since Jan 2021
- Vaccination: free
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 534,65 in 2020; 545,24 in 2021
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 1048,32 in 2020;

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Special COVID-19 laws, incl. amendment allowing the government to introduce stricter measures (Sept 2020)
- The Early Warning System, initially Ministry of Health, then moved to the Austrian Agency for Health and Nutrition Security
- National crisis and catastrophe management was used also for COVID-19
- Corona Traffic light – risk assessment
- Measures: lockdown in March 2020; relaxation and re-introduction based on number of cases; November 2020 – second national lockdown
- Epidemiological reporting system (EMS): shared data base of regional, state and national authorities on diseases, and a dashboard
- Strategic plans for testing
- Vaccination strategy (end of 2020): prioritization in three phases (recommendation by the Vaccination Commission and The Safety Board)
- Contact tracing (Austrian Red Cross App)
- COVID-19 stockpile act
- 2G-Rule introduced Nov 2021, free testing restricted. 2G dropped

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- Younger people with chronic disease, pregnant women, older people in general
- New and amended legal definition for vulnerable groups in May 2020 (medical categories)
- Specific screening programs in vulnerable settings

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from dashboard)

- Hospital occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 889,92 in 2020; 997,71 in 2021
- ICU occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 179,72 in 2020; 290,67 in 2021
- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 7171 in 2020; 14.493,6 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 7486 in 2020; 16.815 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 356.063 in 2020; 1.270.811 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 3.778.483 in 2020; 123.579.209 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 73,42% in 2021
- Other health related outcomes: restricted access to elective surgeries, chronic illness support, and others

Vulnerable groups affected

- Chronically ill persons, elderly and people with disabilities
- Collective accommodation and overcrowded homes (homeless, asylum seekers, seasonal workers)
- Occupational groups at risk (essential workers with no protective equipment)
- Single parents

Governance System (GS)

Changes in governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research: regulates school closures

Changes to preparedness plans?

- Austrian Vaccination Strategy
- National strategic framework for action (2021)

Actor Systems (A)

Decision makers and key professionals:

- Rudolf Anschober, Health Minister
- Sebastian Kurz, Chancellor
- Alexander Schallenberg, Chancellor
- Karl Nehammer, Chancellor
- Gerhard Karner, Interior Minister
- Magnus Brunner
- ORF
- Univ.-Prof. Dr. Heinz Faßmann, Minister of Education

Expert sources:

- COVID-19 Future Operations Platform: multi- and interdisciplinary platform for experts from science and the public sector
- WHO, National experts, Health professionals (mental and physical)
- AGES
- COVID-prognose-consortium as forecasting body
- Corona-Commission as risk assessment body
- Corona Taskforce: MoH employees, Austrian Red Cross, medical professionals, scientists and other public health stakeholders
- Oberste Sanitätsrat and Vaccination Commission

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- Elderly people
- People with chronic illness and comorbidities

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)
 What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Vaccines third and fourth booster available
- Restricted number of free tests from April 2022 onwards
- ICU beds – regional shortages during OMICRON
- Testing – regional disparities

Interaction Area (I)

Changes in response implementation?

- General vaccine mandate proposed Nov 2021 for Feb 2022, cancelled in July 2022
- Lockdown for unvaccinated people
- Slow removal of restriction measures for gathering, and public places opening
- Visits to nursing homes and hospitals were allowed
- Changing in quarantine rules: isolation times shorter, contact isolation cancelled (differences for vaccinated and unvaccinated people). No quarantine for vaccinated population since Dec 2021

Changes in people in charge's reaction?

- Shift from lockdowns measures to vaccination
- Slow lifting of measures

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in governance structure?

- GECKO committee

Changes to preparedness plans?

- The COVID-19 Pandemic: Stocktaking and Framework for Action (updated in April 2022)

Vulnerable groups

- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Wolfgang Mückstein, Health minister
- Johannes Rauch, Health minister
- Katharina Reich & Rudolf Striedinger (GECKO)

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- Elderly
- Chronically ill

TIMEFRAME

T2: Omicron + Lifting of Restrictions/Current situation (December 2021 until September 2022 or more current data if available)

Outcomes (O)

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- Contact tracing became difficult after Omicron spread

How was crisis response lived and practiced?

- Polarisation of population around vaccination
- Tiredness of measures
- Masks in public transport remained

BELGIUM

BELGIUM TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Expenditure on health in 2017 was 3554 euro per capita (10.3 % of GDP).
- 22.5% of health expenditure in Belgium is from private spending
- Many Belgian health workers' wages are low – for example, an assistant nurse (*zorgkundige*) earns 1,000 euros less per month than the average Belgian wage
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 316,32 in 2019
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: data not available
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 556,72 in 2019
- ICU beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 17,4 in 2019

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators:

- Age structure: 18.9% above 65, 64% between 20-65, 22.4% under 20 in 2019
- Gender structure: 50.7% female, 49.3% male in 2019
- Migrant population: 1.3% in 2019
- Population living in poverty: 14.8% in 2019
- Income inequality: 3.6 in 2019
- Housing density (overcrowding): 3.1% in 2019

Governance system (GS)

How is the public health system structured and who is responsible?

- Compulsory health insurance system
- Financing is based on proportional social security contributions from taxable income
- Care is provided by private not-for-profit organizations under state framework
- Specialist outpatient care is given in hospitals or private practices while inpatient/day care is in hospitals
- Pandemic preparedness involves federal government agencies and public health institute Sciensano

What preparedness plans already existed for health crises?

- National pandemic influenza plan 2006
- Advisory report regarding national pandemic influenza plan 2009
- 2006 plan emphasizes tailored communication strategies for different audiences but lacks specificity on vulnerable populations, recovery, and evaluation of mitigation measures.

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Belgian health system is managed by Federal Public Service (FPS) and 3 community Ministries of Health
- Regional governments are responsible for certain areas such as maternity and child health, health promotion, some elderly care, and hospital accreditation standards
- Primary health care is provided by GPs, physiotherapists, nurses, and other healthcare professionals

Who are the main target populations?

- General population

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system?

- Hospitals expanded ICU capacity
- Normal care activities were paused
- New emergency care shifts were created
- Additional hygiene measures and procedures were instituted
- In July 2020, 500 million euros invested in healthcare workers' wages over two years, 100 million for better working conditions, and 400 million previously approved for extra personnel.
- In November 2020, hospital staff received COVID-19 compensation: 985-euro incentive bonus, and staff in other care centers received a one-time "consumption cheque" of 300 euros before tax.
- A structural wage increase for Flemish health workers was announced and rolled out in summer 2021.
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 321,28 in 2020

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Slow to implement lockdown
- Initial distribution of face masks to health workers was slow and chaotic; shortage of PPE in spring 2020
- Vaccination campaign in Belgium reached high levels by August 2021
- From October 2021, COVID-19 cases increased, and strict measures were reintroduced, including the use of a "corona barometer" with three phases.

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- Communication became more tailored

Governance System (GS)

Changes in governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- Federal consultation structure: 2 medical advisory groups, economic risk management group, and expert strategy exit group.
- Expert strategy exit group replaced by Celeval in August 2020.
- Federal responsibility taken over by Consultative Committee in October 2020.
- Federal measures via ministerial orders, guidelines from National Crisis Centre.
- Crisis communication coordinated by Information Unit, jointly chaired by FPS Public Health and NCCN.
- Key decisions made at federal level, regional/local governments can enact (stricter) measures.
- Governors of Belgian provinces and mayors have power to enforce local measures.

Changes to preparedness plans?

- EDC report evaluates SARS-CoV-2 testing policy in Belgium from June to December 2021
- Sciensano publishes thematic report on vaccination coverage and epidemiological impact of COVID-19 vaccination campaign in Belgium in October 2021

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Hospital occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 2183,31 in 2020; 1613,02 in 2021
- ICU occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 457,18 in 2020; 413,49 in 2021
- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 17.081,6 in 2020; 20.213 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 19.528 in 2020; 28.331 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 646.496 in 2020; 2.105.343 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 6.966.831 in 2020; 27.361.349 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 75,77% in 2021
- Other health related outcomes: restricted access to elective surgeries, chronic illness support, and others

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- Division of responsibilities at federal, regional and local level led to confusion and inefficiency in the COVID-19 response.
- Problems with care homes – lack of PPE . See Amnesty International report 2020
- Controversy around face masks
- Small country with high population density 'small beehive in heart of Europe'

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Prime Minister, Health Minister, COVID-19 Commissioner Pedro Facon, Minister of Security and Internal Affairs, Annelies Verlinden
- Government and federated entities
- Epidemiologists from Sciensano and other health risk experts
- Governors of Belgian provinces and mayors of cities

Expert sources

- GEMS (Expert Committee on Management Strategy) consisting of 24 medical experts
- Interfederal task force on testing policy
- Working Group on the Social Impact of the COVID-19 crisis (WG SIC) to monitor and evaluate socio-economic impact and identify risk groups
- Taskforce for Vulnerable Groups to focus on impact on different vulnerable groups

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- At-risk groups, including elderly, adults with type 2 diabetes, severe chronic cardiovascular, lung or kidney disease, decreased immunity and/or cancer

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

BELGIUM T2

Germany

GERMANY TO

GERMANY T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system?

- Persistent shortage of personal protective equipment among health care workers and in health institutions; protective masks had to be reused
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 446,79 in 2020
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 1206,1 in 2020; data not available for 2021

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Key justification for health policymaking during the COVID-19 crisis has been the protection and maintenance of the social welfare state, in particular the social health system.
- Important responses include:
 - February 2020: initial measures taken by the federal government
 - March 22 – May 4 2020: first lockdown
 - Second lockdown (longer but less restrictive)

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- March 2020: Preliminary definition of at-risk group by RKI: elderly persons, smokers, and those suffering from pre-existing heart conditions, lung conditions, liver conditions, diabetes, cancer, or a weakened immune system
- Autumn 2020: more precise information on physical/health risk factors by RKI (risk factors include age, underlying diseases, suppressed immune system, intersecting physical/health vulnerabilities)
- A wider range of social and communications vulnerabilities are acknowledged on an implicit level via targeted support policies (e.g. housing assistance programmes for the homeless, funding programme for culture workers and institutions)

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- ICU occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 1522,87 in 2020; 2753,28 in 2021
- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 24.500 in 2020; 88.390,51 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 33.071 in 2020; 111.602 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 1.719.737 in 2020; 7.109.182 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 35.172.907 in 2020; 92.472.500 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 70,93%% in 2021

Vulnerable groups affected

- Socioeconomically weaker people, ethnic minority groups
- Women (reduced their paid work to compensate for the loss of childcare during lockdowns)

Governance System (GS)

Changes in public health governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- February 2020: a joint crisis task force was set up by Federal Minister of the Interior Horst Seehofer and Federal Minister of Health Jens Spahn
- Corona Expertenrat

Who held the responsibility for public health decisions?

- The Federal Ministry of Health (BMG) and the Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) were the key actors in the COVID-19 response

Actor Systems (A)

Decision makers and key professionals:

- Bundesregierung – Bund-Länder (Government in cooperation with the federal states)
- Federal Ministry of Health
- Robert-Koch-Institut (RKI)
- Ständige Impfkommision (STIKO), scientific committee at the RKI responsible for vaccine schedule
- Federal Institute for Vaccines and Biomedical Products
- Bundesinstitut für Arzneimittel und Medizinprodukte (BfArM), drug approval
- Deutsche Forschungsgesellschaft (DFG), Central self-governing organization of science in Germany
- Deutscher Ethikrat, ethical, societal, scientific, medical and legal issues

Greece

GREECE TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Decade-long austerity, privatization and deregulation of the healthcare system
- Health expenditure: 1623 euro per capita (8% of GDP) (2017)
- The economic crisis and relevant financial consequences had an impact on the healthcare infrastructure, equipment and healthcare personnel adequacy which has been intensified and became more apparent during COVID-19, both at the beginning and later phases.
- According to official reports (Tsiodras & Lytras, 2022), the healthcare system faced significant disparities in relation to the status quo in regional municipalities in comparison to Attica, Athens.
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 616,12 in 2019
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 338,11 in 2019
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 418,01 in 2019
- ICU beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 5,3 in 2018

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Age structure: 22% above 65, 64.2% between 20-65, 19.4% under 20 in 2019
- Gender structure: 51.4% female, 48.6% male in 2019
- Migrant population: 1.2% in 2019
- Population living in poverty: 17.9% in 2019
- Income inequality: 5.1 in 2019
- Housing density (overcrowding): 14% in 2019

Governance System (GS)

How is the public health system structured and who is responsible?

- Mixed (public/private) healthcare system
- Centralised governance structure
- The Ministry of Health is the main national authority responsible for the national public health strategy and policies
- The National Public Health Organization (EODY) has as its main objective to provide services towards the protection and improvement of health of the population.
- Greek Center for Disease Control (CDC): underfunded due to austerity measures

What preparedness plans already existed for health crises?

- National Influenza Pandemic Action Plan (2005; latest update 2009)

Vulnerable groups

- Focus on people at high risk of severe or fatal complications from an influenza infection

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Ministry of Health
- The National health service (ESY) and the National Organization for the Provision of Health Services (EOPYY), both fall under the supervision of the Ministry of Health
- Regional health and welfare authorities exist since 2004, but have limited rights

Who are the main target populations?

- General population

GREECE T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system:

- Private sector staff redeployed into the public sector as a strategy to increase the public health system's surge capacity
- Regular leaves of absence of NHS experts in hospitals and primary health facilities are revoked
- The Greek government recruits a total of 6.800 nursing, medical, paramedical and administrative staff
- The Ministry of Interior allocated funds to first- and second-degree Local Authorities for supplies and other services acquisition related to preventative measures against COVID-19 spread
- EODY provides free rapid COVID-19 tests to citizens
- Even though there is a significant amount of doctors and nurses in both the public and private sector, the COVID-19 outbreak demonstrated that there was an immense shortage of specialised healthcare personnel to handle with these cases.
- Despite mitigation efforts such as the employment of the new healthcare personnel, systemic insufficiencies continued to persist which is also confirmed by Lytras & Tsiodras (2022).
- The amount of hospital beds increased, as beds that were intended to be utilised for the hospitalisation of non-covid-19 related cases, would be turned into COVID-19 related beds and spaces.

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Since the outbreak of the pandemic, the Greek government launched a range of protection and prevention policies; important responses include:
 - January 2020: 13 reference COVID-19 hospitals with a sufficient number of specialized facilities, equipment, and medical staff are appointed
 - February 2020, all the carnival events and school excursions abroad are cancelled;
 - February 2020: information campaign launched by the Ministry of Health
 - March 23 – May 4 2020: first national lockdown
 - November 7 – December 7 2020: second national lockdown
- Various organisations and institutions (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, the Medical university, the Ministry of health and many more NGO's, universities and hospitals) created a 24/7 phone line for psychological support for COVID-19 impacts

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- Greek Roma communities
- Prisoners
- Refugees and asylum seekers
- Single parent families and low SES societal groups

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 5978,6 in 2020; 23.794,1 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 4838 in 2020; 20.790 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 138.850 in 2020; 1.210.853 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 3.382.488 in 2020; 47.248.945 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 67,80%in 2021
- Other health related outcomes: restricted access to specialised surgeries, chronic illness support was insufficient, diagnosis and treatment of everyday life non-COVID-19 related cases were postponed
- Overall mortality and morbidity rates increased

Vulnerable groups affected

- People with underlying health conditions (cancer, cardiovascular, chronic respiratory disease or diabetes)
- Social vulnerability and the impact of the economic recession (low-income households; single parents living in poverty; substance abuse; mental health problems)
- Greek Roma communities

Governance System (GS)

Changes in public health governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- Head of the Expert Committee on Infectious Diseases appointed as the Spokesperson for the Ministry of Health, responsible for providing the public with the latest updates on the pandemic

Changes to preparedness plans?

- There were no significant changes on the plans drawn from previous literature, which built upon the previous response action towards cases such as influenza. The governmental response utilised the plans for influenza and continued to build on them while tailored their response according to these documents.

Who held the responsibility for public health decisions?

- The COVID-19 response was led by the National Public Health Organization (EODY) and the Ministry of Health
- Public health representatives - scientific committee (advisory role), Prime Minister and the Minister of Health played a key role in announcing new rules and regulations

Actor Systems (A)

Decision makers and key professionals

- The Ministry of Health was in charge of announcing all rules and regulations
- Decisions were made by a consortium of scientists, Ministers, deputy ministers and the Prime Minister

Expert sources

- The Expert Committee on Infectious Diseases

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- Vulnerable population such as individuals with socio-economic and health vulnerabilities identified by the governmental mechanism.

Italy

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available?

- 24.4% of healthcare expenditure in 2015 came from out-of-pocket payments and private insurance
- Italy spends 52.2% of long-term care spending on cash benefits
- 65% of institutional long-term care beds are provided by private providers
- 68% of acute hospital beds are public, 4% are private not-for-profit, and 28% are private for profit
- Italy had 12,828 residential care facilities with 390,689 beds in 2016, mostly providing both social and health care services
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 405,07 in 2019
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 615,59 in 2019
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 316,28 in 2019

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Governance system (GS)

How is the public health system structured and who is responsible?

- Italy's National Health Plan (Servizio Sanitario Nazionale) is universal and mostly free, with income and age-based co-payments for specialist services
- Decentralized system based on three levels: State, region, and local boards
- Ministry of Health sets main health goals
- Regions organize and deliver healthcare within their jurisdiction
- Local Health Authorities provide care through public hospitals or accredited private providers
- SSN is funded by national/regional taxes and co-payments for pharmaceutical and outpatient care

What preparedness plans already existed for health crises?

- Multiphase Emergency Plan for an Influenza Pandemic was first issued in 2002 and updated in 2006.

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators:

- Age structure: 22.9% above 65, 64.9% between 20-65, 18% under 20 in 2019
- Gender structure: 51.3% female, 48.7% male in 2019
- Migrant population: 0.6% in 2019
- Population living in poverty: 20.1% in 2019
- Income inequality: 6.0 in 2019
- Housing density (overcrowding): 17.2% in 2019
- Over 14 million people in Italy live with chronic diseases, and 8.4 million of them are over 65 years old.

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Actors: Ministry of Health. National Institute of Health (ISS), National Agency for Regional Health Services (AGENAS), National Center for Disease Prevention and Control (CCM), National Institute for Scientific Research (IRCS), and National Authority for Pharmaceutical Regulation (AIFA): specialized agencies supporting the Ministry of Health. National Health Council (CSS). State-Regions Conference: Regions. Regional Council. Regional agency for health. Local Health Authorities (ASL). Districts. General practitioners (GPs). Municipal authorities

Who are the main target populations?

- PNEP (2002) identified vulnerable groups in an influenza pandemic
 - People aged over 65 years old
 - People with chronic diseases or diabetes or HIV positives
 - Pregnant women
 - Children above 14 years old
- NIPPRP (2006) stratified population into six categories and determined order of priority:
 - Health care providers
 - Security and emergency services personnel
 - Essential workers
 - People at high risk of severe or fatal complications due to influenza
 - Children
 - Healthy adults

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system:

- 3.6% GDP increase for public health expenditure in 2020
- Law approved on Sep 9, 2020 to prevent violence against HCWs with up to 5000 euro sanctions and 16 years imprisonment penalties
- COVID-19 Response Threshold Values: Rt <1, ICU beds <30% occupancy, new cases per 100,000 inhabitants in a week <250
- Triple Ts strategy (testing, tracing, and treatment) adopted by Italian government to prevent COVID-19 spread
- Inconsistent testing strategy across regions, with Lombardy conducting fewer tests than Veneto and Emilia Romagna.
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 400,08 in 2020; 412,51 in 2021
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 627,53 in 2020; 625,89 in 2021
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants (data not available)
- ICU beds per 100.000 inhabitants : 8,6 in 2020

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Lockdown issued on Mar 9, 2020, closing non-essential activities, schools, and businesses
- Govt. established procedure in Oct 2020 to identify regions with restrictive measures during the 2nd wave
- Weekly results of health risk monitoring published on Ministry of Health's website
- Regions classified by epidemiological risk, with higher-risk regions receiving more restrictive measures
- Measures defined by DPCM.

Governance System (GS)

Changes in governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- Decision makers: Government led by Giuseppe Conte
- State of emergency announced in Jan 2020
- Giuseppe Conte led for 10 months. Opposition to measures. Led to new government led by Mario Draghi sworn in Feb 13, 2021
- Decrees of the President of the Council of Ministers (DPCM) used as administrative procedure
- Ministry of Health responsible for publishing monitoring results and classifying regions by epidemiological risk
- PM, Minister of Health, and region's president responsible for identifying regions with restrictive measures
- Scientific Technical Committee established for consultation and coordination
- Regions implemented own measures and protocols
- National exit strategy began on May 4, 2020
- Change in exit strategy on May 17, 2020, transferred responsibility to regions under Ministry of Health's supervision.
- 13th March 2021: A new decree was issued imposing a strict lockdown for 10 of the 20 Italian regions from the 15th of March to the 6th of April.

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 99.615,81 in 2020; 167.105,9 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 74.159 in 2020; 137.402 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 2.107.166 in 2020; 6.125.683 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 26.598.607 in 2020; 140.137.606 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 75,79%in 2021

Vulnerable groups affected

- Groups disproportionately affected: elderly, women, children, disabled, migrants
- Migrants and minorities faced barriers in accessing information and care during lockdown
- Nursing homes severely affected, with high mortality rate and PPE/training shortages

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- Multi-level governance structure allowed for tailored responses but led to tensions
- Some regional prioritization decisions not in line with national guidance on vaccination, Italian Commissioner issued ordinance requiring all regions to follow national strategy
- Legal framework for COVID measures faced challenges with confusion and inconsistency in implementation due to several urgent decrees.

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Actors: Gov't, Civil Protection, Ministry of Health, CTS, regional coordinators, public admin & CTS entities
- Gov't has decision-making powers and issued decrees for lockdowns, restrictions, masks & social distancing
- Civil Protection led command-and-control to coordinate interventions; CTS consulted, supported, and coordinated activities
- Ministry of Health issued protocols, regions implemented in their own way
- Regional coordinators implemented decisions, public admin & CTS entities provided expertise and support.

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Portugal

PORTUGAL T0

PORTUGAL T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system?

- Medical staff redirected to COVID-19 units
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 561,58 in 2020
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 728,45 in 2020

Interaction Area (I) MEASURES

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Government website shares information about the pandemic to control the pandemic
- Communication by prime minister after meeting with experts
- Development of two apps: STAYAWAY COVID app,
- Covid Vaccination plan: with Priority groups for COVID-19 vaccination (especially age groups and professionals: in three phases)
- National Testing Strategy for SARS-CoV-2: "Test-Track-Trace-Isolate", at four levels + focus on vulnerable groups
- Local institutions focused on the implementation

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until Noveber 2021 (Omicron)

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (from dashboard)

- Hospital occupancy (annual average of daily occupance) - covid specific: 1061,82 in 2020; 1261,395 in 2021
- ICU occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 166 in 2020; 214,26 in 2021
- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 9548,6 in 2020; 20808 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 6906 in 2020; 18.955 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 413.678 in 2020; 1.389.646 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 5.681.817 in 2020; 26.804.825 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 82,99% in 2021
- Highest peak of infections in summer 2021
- Portugal has remained among the OECD countries with the lowest rates of hospitalization for health problems sensitive to primary health care and the decrease in permanent disability

Governance System (GS)

Changes in governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- Vaccination Technical Commission against COVID-19 (CTVC)

Changes to preparedness plans?

- New COVID-specific plans: Guiding principles for risk and crisis communication based on risk perception, National Plan of Preparation and Response for Disease of the New Coronavirus (COVID-19), Health Plan for the Autumn-Winter 2020-21
- New decree-laws that establish exceptional measures for specific sectors

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Ministry of Health (Ministério da Saúde) and the General Department of Health (DGS).
- Taskforce

Who/what are ere the expert sourcess?

- WHO and European Center for Disease Prevention and Control
- National risk assessment, institutional partners

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- Physical/health vulnerability: elderly; people with heart diseases, breathing diseases, chronic diseases; people with compromised immune systems, in treatment for autoimmune diseases, HIV / AIDS infection or transplant patients
- Social vulnerability: health professionals; people who must use public transport frequently; people unable to work from home; people with large households; single parent families; homeless people; socio-economically vulnerable people; people with disabilities, Communication vulnerability: people with little reliable information about the virus; people with few means of accessing information

Spain

SPAIN TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Following the economic crisis, health spending decreased for several years, but started to increase again from 2015.
- 8.9 % of its GDP is dedicated to health spending (2017)
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 330,79 in 2019
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 589,02 in 2019
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 294,6 in 2019
- ICU beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 9,7 in 2017

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Age structure: 19.4% above 65, 66% between 20-65, 19.6% under 20 in 2019
- Gender structure: 51% female, 49% male in 2019
- Migrant population: 1.6% in 2019
- Population living in poverty: 20.7% in 2019
- Income inequality: 5.9 in 2019
- Housing density (overcrowding): 2.6% in 2019

Governance System (GS)

How is the public health system structured and who is responsible?

- Spain has a decentralized governance structure that is divided in three levels: national, regional and local.
- At the regional level, the territory is divided in 17 autonomous communities plus two autonomous cities (Ceuta and Melilla); all autonomous communities are (partly) governed by their respective autonomous governments
- Health is a shared policy responsibility between the national level and the level of the autonomous communities

What preparedness plans already existed for health crises?

- National flu response plan (2005; latest update 2006)

Vulnerable groups

- Minors under 14 years old.
- Elderly people, particularly who lived in residential homes or were disabled.
- People who needed housing assistance.
- People who were labelled as a consumers, since they had no access to food or other basic products or services of the daily life.
- Women that might be suffering gender or domestic violence who lives with the aggressor.

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- The institutional design in Spain is divided in three levels: national, regional and local. The policymaking process depends on the policy responsibilities that are assigned to each level.
- Health is a shared policy responsibility between the different institutional levels
- Conference of Presidents: meetings between national and regional presidents
- Sectorial Conference on Health: meetings between the national and the regional ministers of health

Who are the main target populations?

- General population

SPAIN T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system:

- After almost a decade of austerity, the central government allocated €2800 million to all regions for health services and created a new fund with €1000 million for priority health interventions
- Scaling up of accessible intensive care beds
- Increased testing capacity
- Free PCR-tests for citizens at their local care centres
- The State of Alarm allowed hiring graduates without specialisation, final year medical and nursing students, and extending contracts of medical residentes
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 337,06 in 2020
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 610,39 in 2020

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Important responses include:
 - March 14 2020: the Spanish Government approved Royal Decree 463/2020, which declared a State of Alarm for the management of the health emergency caused by COVID-19; the State of Alarm had to be validated every 15 days by the Spanish Parliament
 - Strict confinement measures were installed
 - April 28 2020: the Plan for the Transition to a New Normality was approved by the Council of Ministers
 - June 2020: the strict confinement started to be more flexible depending on the health situation of each autonomous community
 - June 21 2020: State of Alarm was ended
 - A de-escalation plan was created by the Single Authority
 - End of October 2020: a new State of Alarm was declared
- Testing & tracing efforts: different interpretations in different regions, and considerable differences in regions' testing agility
- COVID Radar app: only half of the autonomous regions used the application

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- The elderly

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Hospital occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 12.597,33 in 2020; 8462,89 in 2021
- ICU occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 1904,21 in 2020; 1716,17 in 2021
- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 69.670,2 in 2020; 96.592,42 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 50.837 in 2020; 89.405 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 1.928.265 in 2020; 6.294.745 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 22.859.368 in 2020; 73.454.765 in 2021

Vulnerable groups affected

- The elderly
- Women (victims of gender-based violence as a result of the lockdown; single mothers)
- Low-income households or individuals, migrants, refugees, unemployed or temporary workers

Governance System (GS)

Changes in public health governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- The Single Authority, i.e. the President of the Spanish Government, was installed by the State of Alarm

Who held the responsibility for public health decisions?

- The Single Authority, i.e. the President of the Spanish Government, was responsible for leading and coordinating the policies that had to be implemented to control the evolution of the pandemic and mitigate its consequences
- The Autonomous Communities kept on managing their health systems, but had to follow general instructions from the Single Authority.

Actor Systems (A)

Decision makers and key professionals

- The Single Authority, i.e. President of the Spanish government Pedro Sánchez
- Four delegated ministers were identified as managers of the most relevant policy areas to control the spreading of the COVID-19: Minister of Health; Minister of Defence; Minister of Interior and Minister of Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda.
- Director of the Coordination Centre of Health Emergencies (Fernando Simón)
- The Sectorial Conference on Health had a relevant role coordinating technical aspects between the Minister of Health and the autonomous councillors
- The Interterritorial Council of the National Health System (CISNS) was responsible for the intergovernmental coordination between the Ministry of Health and the Autonomous Communities to manage the health crisis.

Expert sources

- WHO, The Ministry of Health, The Ministry of Foreign Affairs, The CCAES, The AEMPS, Autonomous Community Health Departments and Regional Health Services, The CISNS, The ISCIII.

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Vaccination is carried out as vaccine doses become available
- The General State Budget for 2023 consolidates the Government's commitment to strengthening the National Health System.
- The Ministry of Health will have 2,746.17 million euros in 2023, 7.83% more than in 2022.
- The Mental Health and COVID 19 Action Plan increases its allocation in 2023, exceeding 43 million euros.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Omicron + Lifting of Restrictions/Current situation (December 2021 –September 2022 or more current data if available)

Interaction Area (I)

Changes in response implementation?

- Vaccination roll-out
- Elimination on the mandatory use of mask in public transportation

Changes in people in charge reaction?

- An excessive politicisation of the health crisis led to changes in the transcendental, social and interpersonal beliefs of Spaniards, producing and increase in polarisation ever since.
- Is found that Spain has a low level of interpersonal trust but places a high importance on the values of conformity and obedience.

Changes in how new/different vulnerable groups were accounted for?

- Vulnerable groups were well defined since the beginning, measures to be taken were update, although, groups were still.

Outcomes (O)

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- Public confidence in vaccines compromised due to a lack of uniform criteria between countries/regions as well as the lack of compliance with contracts on the part of some of the big pharma.

What positive developments, solutions were used?

- The crisis helped in negotiating and building a dialogue between political decision-makers with different interest and the scientific community, resulting in evidence-based health measures

How was crisis response lived and practiced?

- According to the experts, although the measures were defined in detail, sometimes those were broader than what made sense from a transmission control point of view, but that was what allowed them to be implemented

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in public health governance structure?

- No changes

Changes to preparedness plans?

- No changes since July 2020

Who held the responsibility?

- 5 fases from the start to this day:
 - i. Decentralized strategy
 - ii. Total centralization
 - iii. Autonomous communities participated again
 - iv. Softer centralization after the second state of emergency in October 2020
 - v. Back to normal after May 2021

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- The Ministry of Health / The Ministry of Foreign Affairs./ The CCAES /The AEMPS/ Autonomous Community Health Departments and Regional Health Services./ The CISNS./ The ISCIII.

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Technical-scientific evidence

Who are the main target populations?

- children, the elderly, women, people with functional diversity, people with intellectual disabilities, immigrants in an irregular administrative situation, people with unshared family responsibilities, people deprived of their liberty or addicted to substances, and people who are chronically ill or without a regular income

Sweden

SWEDEN TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What kind of resources were available (services provided by organizations)?

- Expenditure on health care in 2017 was EUR 3,872 per capita (11 % of GDP)
- Doctors per 100.000 inhabitants: 428,51 in 2019
- Nurses per 100.000 inhabitants: 1085,07 in 2019
- Hospital beds per 100.000 inhabitants: 207,1 in 2019

Interaction Area (I)

n/a

Governance System(GS)

How is the public health system structured and who is responsible?

- All three levels of Swedish government (national, regional, local) are involved in the health care system:
 - National level: the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs is responsible for overall health and healthcare policy; works closely with national government agencies, especially the National Board for Health and Welfare (NBHW) and the Public Health Agency (PHA) that are responsible for establishing principles and guidelines, and establishing the overall political agenda for Swedish health care.
 - Regional level: 12 county councils and 9 regional bodies are responsible for financing and delivering health services to citizens.
 - Local level: 290 municipalities are responsible for care of the elderly and the disabled

What preparedness plans already existed for health crises?

- Contingency planning for a pandemic influenza (2005; later updates 2019, 2023)
- Guide on communication in the event of a pandemic written by the Swedish Public Health Agency (PHA)

Vulnerable groups

- Medical risk groups
- 'Groups with specific needs' (elderly, parents, people travelling, people who do not speak Swedish and people with disabilities that affect their information retrieval)

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Age structure: 19.9% above 65, 62.2% between 20-65, 23,3% under 20 in 2019
- Gender structure: 49.7% female, 50.3% male in 2019
- Migrant population: 1.1% in 2019
- Population living in poverty: 17.1% in 2019
- Income inequality: 4.3 in 2019
- Housing density (overcrowding): 10% in 2019

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- The Swedish governance system is characterized by a high degree of decentralization and autonomous authorities
- Some of the power, responsibility and functions for health lie with decentralized elected levels of government; the central government still has a role within the health management system.
- Responsibility for healthcare services lies with the 21 regional councils
- Responsibility for elderly care lies with 290 local municipalities.

Who are the main target populations?

- General population

SWEDEN T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system:

- Extra funding for agencies, regions and municipalities to manage the pandemic
- Scaling up of accessible intensive care beds
- Increased testing capacity
- Free PCR-tests for citizens at their local care centres

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- Three general principles guide crisis management in Sweden: responsibility principle, parity principle and principle of proximity
- Between February and September 2020, the Government made 400 decisions related to the pandemic; important responses include:
 - February 1 2020: The Swedish Government classifies COVID-19 as a danger to society.
 - March 11 2020: Extra funding for agencies, regions and municipalities are allocated to manage the pandemic.
 - April 1 2020: The National ban is announced for visiting care homes.
 - April 4 2020: The Government proposes temporary law changes in order to take measures against COVID-19 more rapidly.
 - May 20 2020: A national vaccine program is presented.
 - June 5 2020: The Government urges to secure more extensive testing capacity.
 - August-December 2020: The Government (as a part of EU) signs agreements with a number of different pharmaceutical companies providing COVID-19 vaccine.

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- The elderly, persons with a heart-/lung disease or impaired immune system
- Cancer patients, people having a recent transplantation of organs, people with diabetes, liver or kidney diseases.
- Lifestyle factors, especially obesity; people with Down's syndrome; pregnant women
- Social vulnerability; income; educational level; type of job; living situation; immigrant groups

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators

- Hospital occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 1041,50 in 2020; 918,44 in 2021
- ICU occupancy (annual average of daily occupancy) - covid specific: 175,30 in 2020; 153,63 in 2021
- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 7421,1 in 2020; 9791,5 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 8727 in 2020; 15.310 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 437.379 in 2020; 1.314.784 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 4.179.271 in 2020; 15.158.251 in 2021

Vulnerable groups affected

- The elderly, persons with a heart-/lung disease or impaired immune system
- Cancer patients, people having a recent transplantation of organs, people with diabetes, liver or kidney diseases.
- Lifestyle factors, especially obesity; people with Down's syndrome; pregnant women
- Social vulnerability; income; educational level; type of job; living situation; immigrant groups

Governance System (GS)

Changes in public health governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- June 2020: the Swedish government appointed the Corona Commission (CC) as an independent commission to evaluate the implemented Swedish strategy.

Changes to preparedness plans?

- December 2020: presentation of a national vaccination plan by the PHA

Who held the responsibility for public health decisions?

- The central government relied heavily on the Public Health Agency (PHA) for deciding its strategy to handle the pandemic
- The PHA has primary responsibility for coordinating surveillance, testing and communications during the pandemic

Actor Systems (A)

Decision makers and key professionals

- The Swedish Government through the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs and the Minister Lena Hallenberg (all government decisions are collective)
- Regional level: 21 county councils.
- Local level: 290 municipalities

Expert sources

- The national Swedish Public Health Agency is responsible for coordinating efforts to combat Covid-19, to systematically prevent spreading of infection, carry out microbiological analysis, asses risks and development of outbreak.
- A national Vaccine Coordinator, appointed by the Government, also tasked on leading a study on access to COVID-19 vaccines.
- Swedish Association of local authorities and regions (SALAR)
- Regional Infection Control Doctors with their agencies (Smittskydd) responsible for coordinating regional and local pandemic preparedness, for preventing and reducing the spread of COVID-19. and regional infection control doctors
- Health professionals (mental and physical), e.g. hospital managers, health advisers etc,
- The Corona Commission: 15 experts from different sectors, chaired by judge Mats Melin

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- Specific vulnerable groups (see Interaction Area and Outcomes)

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

England

ENGLAND TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system:

- On 28 May 2020, the government in England announced the launch of a new testing service called the National Health Service Test and Trace (NHST&T)
- The government has provided £22 billion funding for NHST&T in 2020-21 and £15 billion for 2021-22.
- NHST&T rapidly expanded UK testing capability for COVID-19 from 100,000 to over 800,000 a day between May 2020 and January 2021.
- The COVID-19 contact-tracing app was launched on 24 September 2020, using low-energy Bluetooth to record close contacts.

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Interaction Area (I) MEASURES

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- UK lockdown: Mar 23, 2020 - Mar 8, 2021
- England: similar approach to Wales, with timeline variations
- Three-tier system introduced: Oct 14, 2020
- Second lockdown announced: Oct 31, 2020; enforced Nov 5, 2020
- Increasing areas entered Tier 4: Dec 19-26, 2020
- England entered third national lockdown: Jan 6, 2021
- NHS England and NHS Improvement achieved all key targets up until July 2021.

Were new/different vulnerable groups defined and accounted for?

- Vulnerable in UK: 70+, <70 with health conditions, pregnant women
- 2.2M advised to shield at home for 12 weeks from March 2020
- Identified through health records and COVID-19 risk assessments
- Care home workers also vulnerable; twice as likely to die
- Ethnic minority groups more likely to have COVID-19 and severe outcomes

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (UK-wide)

- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 77.627,59 in 2020; 136.447,2 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 94.998 in 2020; 177.397 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 2.488.780 in 2020; 12.937.886 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 49.127.610 in 2020; 393.314.236 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 70,26% in 2021

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- England had a general risk management plan in place since 2005 called the National Risk Assessment, but it focused heavily on influenza instead of other diseases.
- The government carried out an exercise called Exercise Alice in 2016, which modelled the impact of a coronavirus outbreak.
- The government missed opportunities while preparing for the pandemic and failed to apply Exercise Alice, which specifically modelled MERS-Cov, when preparing and responding to the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Delays in meeting vaccination objectives for 12-15 year olds by late October 2021

What positive developments, solutions were used?

- UK became the first country in the world to authorize the administration of Pfizer/BioNTech's COVID-19 vaccine

Governance System (GS)

Changes in governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- A 2021 report by the 'Committee on Risk Assessment and Risk Planning' found that the UK needs to improve its capacity to anticipate and respond to different risk scenarios.
- The National Audit Office (NAO) report on England's preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic found that resources were diverted from other risk and contingency preparations while preparing for England's exit from the EU.
- Intention to establish UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA). Launched in April 2021.

Changes to preparedness plans?

- Coronavirus Act
- Coronavirus Action Plan
- Introduction of COVID-19 Response: Autumn and Winter Plan'.

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Government ministers, led by the Secretary of State for Health and Social Care, Matt Hancock,
- The Local Action Committee
- Ministers have the power to implement restrictions under the Public Health (Control of Disease) Act 1984.

Who/what were the expert sources?

- The Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE) reports into the Civil Contingencies Committee (CCC), which coordinates the government's response to emergencies.

Who are the main target populations?

- General Population

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

- Third vaccine available and booster administration as well
- NHS sets out package of measures to boost capacity ahead of winter
- Limited number of free testing

Interaction Area (I)

Changes in response implementation?

- Gradual lifting of measures
- Switch from lockdowns to vaccination
- Self-isolation after testing positive for COVID-19 was removed from 24 February 2022 and swab tests are no longer free for most people from 1 April 2022.
- Objectives met for vaccinating the majority of adults with two doses in a short time.

Changes in how new/different vulnerable groups accounted for?

- Phase 1 and 2 focused on vaccinating high-risk individuals and the first 9 priority groups with a single dose.
- Phase 3 included vaccinating 16-17 year olds, 12-15 year olds, booster vaccines, and third doses for the immunocompromised.
- Efforts were made to target hard-to-reach populations, including migrants in the UK.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government structure?

- England's Department of Health and Social Care set out vision for transforming England's public health system by disbanding the agency of Public Health (PHE) and creating new bodies informed by the COVID-19 pandemic (DHSC)
- VTF becomes permanent part of government structure by merging into UKHSA as new directorate

Changes to preparedness plans?

- Joint statement between UK government, CEPI and Industry Associations (March 2022)

Who held the responsibility for public health decisions

- Department of Health and Social Care

Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

- Pregnant women, people who have a learning disability or serious mental illness, and other health conditions stated in the Green Book.

TIMEFRAME

T2: Omicron + Lifting of Restrictions/Current situation (December 2021 until September 2022 or more current data if available)

Outcomes (O)

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- AstraZeneca vaccine supplies expired due to age restrictions, 1.9M doses destroyed
- Weaknesses include minority communities' vaccine access, addressing vaccine hesitancy, and addressing concerns of health workers

What positive developments, solutions were used?

- Early and decisive action, pursuing multiple solutions, using existing infrastructure, and effective use of data
- People in the UK were given more freedoms once they were vaccinated

How was crisis response lived and practiced?

- Gradual distrust in government due to COVID-19 response
- Masks in public transport remained, and later on in pandemic, encouraged.

What happened in practice?

- Tailor plans for vulnerable and marginalized groups
- Learn from other disruptive events to strengthen crisis response
- Transparency and trust are crucial in pandemic response
- Multi-stakeholder engagement is important in pandemic response
- Digital access has brought positive changes but usability issues must be addressed

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Sajid David Sec of State for Health; Nadhim Zahawi Vaccines Minister

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Professor Chris Whitty (Chief Medical Officer for England); Sir Patrick Vallance (Government Chief Scientific Advisor)
- Vaccination Board; Health Professionals, e.g., NHS and NICE; Ministerial-led taskforces; Department of Health and Social Care
- Experts and Scientific Advisory Groups, e.g., The Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE)
- Sub-groups of SAGE, e.g., New and Emerging Respiratory Virus Threats Advisory Group, Scientific Pandemic Insights Group on Behaviours, Scientific Pandemic Influenza Group on Modelling, PHE Serology Working Group, COVID-19 Clinical Information Network, New and Emerging Respiratory Virus Threats Advisory Group, Environmental Modelling Group, Children's Task and Finish Working Group, Hospital onset COVID-19 Working Group, Social Care Working Group, Ethnicity Sub-Group.
- Cabinet Office Briefing Rooms (COBR); Technical Advisory Cell (TAC) and Technical Advisory Group (TAG)

Who are the main target populations?

- Targeted communications to increase vaccine uptake in Bangladeshi, Muslim, Indian, Black and migrant communities. Pregnant women also targeted. This is for increased vaccine uptake.

Wales

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

What were the main changes in the resources in the public health system:

- Public Health Wales launched a well-being campaign in April 2020 with help and advice on how to look after yourself and others during the pandemic

Interaction Area (I) MEASURES

How was the response implemented when it hit?

- First positive Coronavirus tests in UK: Jan 29, 2020
- COVID-19 crisis began in Wales: Feb 28, 2020
- UK initially worked together to respond to pandemic
- UK lockdown announced by Boris Johnson on Mar 23, 2020
- Welsh Parliament approved Coronavirus Restrictions on Mar 25, 2020
- Wales managed pandemic independently
- Restrictions began to ease on Mar 15, 2021 with reopening of primary schools for all children.

Governance System (GS)

Changes in governance structure? New institutional bodies created?

- SAGE advises CCC for emergencies
- Welsh Government manages public health response
- Public Health Wales and ECC(W) coordinate multi-agency response

Changes to preparedness plans?

- Guidance for Health and Care Research Wales Support and Delivery Service regarding pandemic preparedness and response to COVID-19 outbreak - March 2020
- Evaluation of testing and tracing (auditor for wales) March 2021
- Evaluation of COVID-19 vaccination auditor for Wales (June 2021)

Actor Systems (A)

Decision makers and key professionals:

- Prime minister UK, Welsh govt

Who are the main target populations?

- Welsh Government recognizes vulnerable groups for COVID-19
- 'Increased risk' group: age 70+, <70 with underlying health conditions, pregnant women
- 'Extremely vulnerable' group: transplant recipients, specific cancer patients, severe respiratory conditions, single organ disease, rare diseases, immunosuppression, Down's syndrome, pregnant women with significant heart disease
- Other vulnerable groups: elderly, BAME, blind/partially sighted, hearing impairments
- Physical and social vulnerability can interact
- Some groups face challenges accessing pandemic support services (sex workers, migrants, dementia patients, homeless)

Outcomes (O)

Country status/ indicators (UK-wide)

- Cumulative excess deaths at the end of the year: 77.627,59 in 2020; 136.447,2 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 deaths: 94.998 in 2020; 177.397 in 2021
- Cumulative COVID-19 cases: 2.488.780 in 2020; 12.937.886 in 2021
- Cumulative Covid-19 tests: 49.127.610 in 2020; 393.314.236 in 2021
- Vaccination rate: 70,26% in 2021
- Audit Wales states that by late September, 2021 laboratories were processing over 10,000 tests a day for Welsh residents

What barriers, problems were encountered?

- Wales had low testing capacity during the first phase of the pandemic
- England's National Risk Assessment plan focused mainly on influenza, dating back to 2005
- In 2016, the government conducted Exercise Alice to model a coronavirus outbreak
- The government failed to apply Exercise Alice, which specifically modelled MERS-Cov, when preparing and responding to the COVID-19 pandemic, missing opportunities to better prepare.

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 March 2020 until November 2021 (Omicron)

Annex 3: Health-related outcome indicators for the COVINFORM target countries from 2019-2021.

	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021
	AUSTRIA			BELGIUM			GERMANY			GREECE			ITALY		
Health Spending ¹	75.08%	76.45%	78.62%	76.03%	78.68%	-	84.02%	85.09%	86.02%	61.51%	61.83%	-	73.75%	76.08%	75.58%
Doctors ²	531.8	534.65	545.24	316.32	321.28	-	439.39	446.79	-	616.12	-	-	405.07	400.08	412.51
Nurses ²	1037.34	1048.32	-	-	-	-	1179.4	1206.1	-	338.11	-	-	615.59	627.53	625.89
Hospital beds ³	718.9	-	-	556.72	-	-	791.48	-	-	418.01	-	-	316.28	-	-
ICU beds* ⁴	28.9	-	-	17.4	-	-	33.4	-	-	5.3	-	-	-	8.6	-
COVID-19 Hospital Occupancy ⁵		889.92	997.71		2183.36	1613.03		-	-		-	-		-	-
COVID-19 ICU Occupancy ⁵		179.72	290.67		457.18	413.49		1522.87	2753.29		-	-		-	-
Pre-existing health conditions (%) ⁶	41.67%	-	-	23.58%	-	-	19.66%	-	-	12.65%	-	-	16.78%	-	-
Excess mortality (%) ⁷		11.1	11.2		16.3	3.3		5.5	9.4		7.7	18.8		16.2	10.2
COVID-19 Death rate ⁸		84.1	188.2		169.5	245.2		39.8	134.2		45.1	194.7		124.3	232.0
COVID-19 Case rate ⁹		4000.2	14226.6		5610.8	18220.6		2067.8	8549.3		1295.4	11,339.0		3533.1	10,341.1
COVID-19 Test rate ¹⁰		42,449.8	1,383,453.0		60,463.2	236,797.1		42,292.1	111,204.9		31,557.3	442,462.5		44,597.5	236,574.2
COVID-19 Vaccination rate (%) ¹¹		-	73.4		-	75.8		-	70.9		-	67.8		-	75.8
COVID-19 Health Intervention stringency (0-1) ¹²		0.34	0.52		0.37	0.55		0.35	0.42		0.34	0.44		0.42	0.49

(-) Missing data/not available.

() not relevant

*Latest data available 2018.

¹ Reported as the proportion of government/compulsory health spending. <https://data.oecd.org/healthres/health-spending.htm>

² Medical staff rate – Doctors/Nurses (per 100,000 inhabitants). Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/hlth_rs_spec

³ Hospital beds per 100,000 inhabitants. Source EU: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tps00046>, Source UK: <https://data.oecd.org/healthqt/hospital-beds.htm>

⁴ ICU beds per 100,000 inhabitants. Source: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/e5a80353-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/e5a80353-en> & <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/en/data-insights/intensive-care-beds-capacity>

⁵ Yearly average of daily occupancy in hospital beds or ICU beds (COVID-19 patients). Source EU: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/download-data-hospital-and-icu-admission-rates-and-current-occupancy-covid-19>

Source UK: <https://coronavirus.data.gov.uk/details/healthcare>

⁶ Proportion of population with a longstanding health problem described as being at increased risk of severe COVID-19 outcomes. Data last collected in 2011. Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/hlth_dp020

⁷ Average monthly excess mortality. Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_mexrt/default/table?lang=en

⁸ Annual Population rates (per 100,000). Source EU: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/data-daily-new-cases-covid-19-eueea-country> Source UK:

<https://coronavirus.data.gov.uk/details/deaths?areaType=nation&areaName=England>

⁹ Annual Population rates (per 100,000). Source EU: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/data-daily-new-cases-covid-19-eueea-country> Source UK: <https://coronavirus.data.gov.uk/details/cases>

¹⁰ Annual Population rates (per 100,000). Source EU: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/covid-19-testing> Source UK: <https://coronavirus.data.gov.uk/details/testing>

¹¹ Proportion of population fully vaccinated for COVID-19. Source: https://ourworldindata.org/covid-vaccinations?country=OWID_WRL

¹² Intensity of non-pharmaceutical health interventions in response to COVID-19 pandemic. Global score based on policies for masks, curfew, domestic lockdown, state of emergency. Source: <https://response2covid19.org/>

Annex 3: Health-related outcome indicators for the COVINFORM target countries from 2019-2021.

	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021
	PORTUGAL			SPAIN			SWEDEN			UK		
Health Spending ¹	60.85%	64.52%	63.96%	70.61%	73.26%	-	85.12%	85.91%	85.56%	79.36%	82.84%	82.90%
Doctors ²	545.17	561.58	-	330.79	337.06	-	428.51	-	-	2.95	3.03	3.18
Nurses ²	707.72	728.45	-	589.02	610.39	-	1085.07	-	-	8.2	8.46	8.68
Hospital beds ³	350.6	-	-	294.6	-	-	207.1	-	-	2.45	2.43	2.34
ICU beds* ⁴	4.2	-	-	9.7	-	-	-	5	-	6.6	-	-
COVID-19 Hospital Occupancy ⁵		1061.82	1261.39		12597.33	8462.89		1041.51	918.44		-	-
COVID-19 ICU Occupancy ⁵		166	214.26		1904.215	1716.17		175.29	153.63		-	-
Pre-existing health conditions (%) ⁶	40.37%	-	-	26.14%	-	-	41.06%	-	-	28.86%	-	-
Excess mortality (%) ⁷		11.4	10.5		18.2	7.3		7.9	0.9		-	-
COVID-19 Death rate ⁸		67.1	184.1		107.4	188.6		84.5	147.5		141.6	263.4
COVID-19 Case rate ⁹		4017.9	13,494.0		4073.9	13,280.4		4235.1	12,667.4		3710.1	19,209.7
COVID-19 Test rate ¹⁰		55,185.2	260,285.2		48,295.2	154,972.1		40,467.1	146,043.2		73,236.0	583,979.5
COVID-19 Vaccination rate ¹¹		-	82.9		-	79.6		-	69.2		-	70.5
COVID-19 Health Intervention stringency (0-1) ¹²	-	0.34	0.57	-	0.40	0.54	-	0.21	0.27	-	0.42	0.54

(-) Missing data/not available.

() not relevant

*Latest data available 2018.